

ASPECTS OF AGREEMENT RELATIONS IN
HAUSA CLAUSE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The present study examines the role of operative relations in Hausa clause structure. These relations are shown to be agreement relations which determine ultimate convergence, and are also morphologically marked by agreement markers which are themselves functional elements in the sense of Abney (1987).

Chapter one is a general introduction. It discusses previous studies that relate to categories, relations amongst categories in clause structure and movement in Hausa. The chapter also discusses the theoretical orientation of the study. The theoretical framework under which the present study is carried out is the Principles and Parameters approach to linguistic theory, especially its exposition in a version referred to as the Minimalist theory (Chomsky 1991, 1992).

Chapter two examines issues of agreement as depicted in the noun phrase structure.

Chapter three examines issues of agreement in the verbal component and an articulated clause structure for Hausa. The clause structure of Hausa is examined in the light of recent insights into and modifications to the structure of the universal clause as in Pollock (1989)

and refinements in Chomsky (1991, 1992).

Chapter four examines the nature of agreement relations in the articulated clause structure of Hausa. The study identifies three principal agreement relations in a simple clause structure of Hausa: (i) subject agreement relations (ii) temporal cum aspectual agreement relations and (iii) agreement relations in the verbal component.

Chapter five examines aspects of movement and the agreement issue in Hausa clause structure. The chapter re-examines the operations of two principal conditions on movement, namely the subjacency condition and the empty category principle (ECP) vis-a-vis Tuller's (1986) conclusions on same.

Chapter six contains concluding observations.

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CERTIFICATION

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ABBREVIATIONS

N	noun
V	verb
ADJ/Adj	adjective
NF	non-future
ADV	adverb
Q	quantifier
aux	auxiliary verb
P	preposition
DET	determiner
TNS	tense
INFL	inflection node
C	complementizer
AGR	agreement
AGR-S	subject agreement element
AGR-O	object agreement element
DEM	demonstrative
SPEC	specifier
PRM	previous reference marker
FOC	focus marker
GEN	genitive marker
ASP	aspect
PERF	perfective

ABBREVIATIONS

N	noun
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P	preposition
DET	determiner
TNS	tense
INFL	inflection node
C	complementizer
AGR	agreement
AGR-S	subject agreement element
AGR-O	object agreement element
DEM	demonstrative
SPEC	specifier
PRM	previous reference marker
FOC	focus marker
GEN	genitive marker
ASP	aspect
PERF	perfective

CONT	continuative
FUT	future
SUB	subjunctive
HAB	habitual
NP/N''	noun phrase
VP/V''	verb phrase
PP	prepositional phrase
AP	adjective phrase
DP	determiner phrase
AGRP	agreement phrase
TP/T''	tense phrase
CP	complementizer phrase
masc.	masculine
fem.	feminine
sing.	singular
PL	plural
MS	masculine singular
FS	feminine singular
1	first person
2	second person
3	third person
t	trace
e	empty, zero object
H	high tone

L	low tone
V	vowel
VV	long vowel
C	consonant
UG	universal grammar
GB	government-Binding theory
PF	phonetic form
LF	logical form
subj	subject
obj	object
loc.	locative
suf.	suffix
ř	rolled /r/
ˈ	High tone
ˌ	Low tone
ˆ	Falling tone
∅	phonetically unrealized
pre _m	prenominal marker
post _n	postnominal marker
Pron	Pronominal
Trans	Transitive
Unacc	Unaccusative

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Preliminaries

The primary goal of the present study is to examine basic (operative) relations in Hausa clause structure, and in particular, relations in the verbal component of the clause with a view to establishing proper agreement relations in the clause. The study also examines the role played by these basic relations in movement structures.

Basic operative relations are those relations holding amongst constituents in the clause such as the relation between a verb and its complement; between subject and verb; between tense and verb and so forth, and are stated in X-bar theoretic terms. Those basic relations which involve sharing of common features between elements are said to be agreement relations. For example, subject-verb relation in English is an agreement relation which involves sharing of features, i.e. the features person, gender and number. The present study argues in the chapters ahead that in Hausa at least, basic (operative) relations in the clause must be agreement relations since feature-sharing and/or identification is always involved.

1.1 Previous Studies

Previous studies that are directly relevant to the themes of the present study are grouped into three: group one constitutes previous studies on categories and their projections (1.1.1); group two constitutes previous studies dealing with agreement relations amongst categories, especially relations in the verbal component of the clause (1.1.2); and group three constitutes previous studies on movement in Hausa (1.1.3).

1.1.1 Previous Studies on categories and their projections

Previous studies in Hausa on categories that are relevant to our purpose include Galadanci (1969, 1976) and Yusuf (1991) both on Hausa NP structure and Tuller (1986) on the category 'adjective' and the 'auxiliary verb' in Hausa. The 'grade' as an integral component of the Hausa verb was also discussed, especially in Parsons (1960) but was never clearly categorized. These studies contain issues that necessitate revisitation.

1.1.1.1 The Noun Phrase (NP)

Hausa has single determiner -NP constructions such as (1), and double-determiner -NP constructions such as (2).

- (1) (a) wání yaáròò¹
 DET N
 some boy (some/a certain boy)
- (b) yaárínyà ã̃
 N DET
 girl the (the girl)
- (2) (a) wání yaárò ã̃
 DET N DET
 some boy the (another boy)
- (b) yaárínyà ã̃ nán
 N DET DET
 girl the that (that particular girl
 previously referred)

Double determiner-NP constructions receive no deserving attention in both Galadanci's traditional phrase structure analysis of the Hausa NP and in Yusuf's Determiner Phrase (DP) analysis of same. In fact, there is no specific study in the literature which addresses itself solely to the phenomena of double determiner-NP constructions. In chapter two of the present study we propose an agreement-oriented account of the Hausa double determiner-NP constructions.

1 The tone marking convention used in this work in respect of long vowel is that only the second vowel of the high-toned long vowel sequence is marked high (e.g. aá) and the first vowel of the low-toned long vowel sequence is marked low (e.g. àa).

1.1.1.2 The Category 'auxiliary verb'

It is assumed in the literature (Jaggar (1977), Tuller (1986)) that Hausa has a set of verbs described as 'auxiliary verbs'. Tuller (1986) cited some of these auxiliary verbs which include faàrà 'start', dáinà 'stop', dáďà 'add/increase', fyà 'know how to do something', kaásà, 'unable to do something'. It is not clear why these verbs are referred to as auxiliary in the traditional literature. We shall assume that perhaps the reason might not be unconnected with the fact that they constitute a small, closed class whose members are capable of co-occurring with other verbs. It must be pointed out that besides being a member of a closed class and having the ability to co-occur with other verbs, an 'auxiliary' verb shares all other characteristics with other verbs. To show that 'auxiliary verbs' are simply verbs, we consider an important morpho-syntactic argument of quantitative vowel mutation. One major characteristic of the Hausa regular verb is that it alters its final vowel (i.e. mutates) with changes in the form of the element (or syntactic environment) that follows it directly. Generally, the form of the final vowel of the verb is short before a noun direct object as in (3a) and long before a pronoun

object, zero object and trace of movement as shown in (3b-d) respectively.

(3) (a) Áudù $yá$ $á$ $kaámà$ $kiffif$
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF catch fish
 noun object
 (Audu caught a fish)

(b) Áudù $yá$ $á$ $kaámàa$ $shí$
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF catch it
 pronoun object
 (Audu caught it)

(c) Áudù $yá$ $á$ $kaámàa$ e
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF catch something
 zero object
 (Audu caught something)

(d) $Kiffif_i$ (nèe) Áudù $yá$ $\emptyset$ $kaámàa$ t_i
 fish FOC Audu 3MS NF-PERF catch trace
 (Fish (it is) (that) Audu caught)

It turns out that each of the so called 'auxiliary verbs' (aux) in Hausa exhibits same mutational behaviour as the other verbs in respect of its final vowel. This is corroborated by the examples in (4).

(4) (b) Audù yá á iyà taádii
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF aux noun object
 know chat
 how to

(Audu knew how to chat)

(b) Audù yá á iyàa shí
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF aux pronoun object
 it

(Audu knew how to do it, i.e. chatting)

(c) Audù yá á iyàa e
 Audu 3MS NF-PERF aux zero direct object

(Audu knew how to do (something))

(d) Taádii_i (née) Audù yá ø iyàa t_i
 chat FOC Audu 3MS NF-PERF aux trace

(Chat (it is) (that) Audu knew how to do)

The examples in (4) show that the 'auxiliary verb' also exhibits an important characteristic of true verbs, namely the mutational behaviour in respect of its final vowel. In (4a), the auxiliary verbal base iy- takes a short vowel, -a before a noun object. It takes long vowel -aa before a pronoun object (4b), zero object (4c) and trace (4d).

We therefore conclude that the 'auxiliary verb' is actually a true verb.²

1.1.1.3 The category 'Adjective'

A fundamental question with respect to inventory of categories in Hausa is whether or not Hausa contains the category adjective. Hausa scholars have always held varying opinions in respect of the category adjective in Hausa. Early views on the matter include those of Kraft and Kirk-Greene (1973), Skinner (1977) and Newman (1977). Kraft and Kirk-Greene (1973:129) point out that there is no separate category of words in Hausa corresponding to what are termed adjectives in the European languages, especially English. Skinner (1977:51) argues that Hausa does not have the standard category adjective but has 'controlled nouns' which is a large class of morphemes that corresponds to adjectives. The morphemes, according to Skinner, include words for colour, size and any other sort

2 In Abney's (1987) functional classification of elements, the same features [-N, -F] are used to define the auxiliary and the true verb, suggesting that either the two are indistinguishable as in Hausa where both are true verbs or the line of demarcation between the two elements is very thin.

of conditions such as tsoóhoó 'old', saáboó 'new', doógoó 'tall' and gàjeéree 'short'. Newman (1977:xi) believes that there are adjectives in Hausa but "most adjective words in Hausa are nouns as well as adjectives and are labelled noun and adjective." To illustrate, Newman points out that gúrgùu is identified as 'lame' (adjective) but it can also mean 'a lame person' (noun).

Modern views on the category adjective in Hausa as in Tuller (1986) and Yusuf (1991) assume the existence of the category in the language. Tuller (1986:35) observes that "Hausa does have a category adjective, though, adjectives are very often indistinguishable from nouns since most adjectives may also function as nouns", Yusuf (1991:169) observes that "adjectives comprise stem and agreement suffix marking gender or number" as shown in the following examples.

(5)	<u>Adjective</u>	<u>Stem</u>	<u>Agreement suffix</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
(a)	fárif	far-	-ii (MS)	white
(b)	fáraá	far-	-aa (FS)	white
(c)	fàràareé	far-	-aaree (PL)	whites

Yusuf observes further that "the choice of agreement suffix on adjectives is lexically determined." We

illustrate this view as follows

(6)	<u>Adjective</u>	<u>Stem</u>	<u>Agreement suffix</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
(a)	saáboó	sab-	-oo (MS)	new
(b)	saábúwá	sab-	-uwa (FS)	new
(c)	sàbàbbí	sab-	-abbi (PL)	new

(7)	<u>Adjective</u>	<u>Stem</u>	<u>Agreement suffix</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
(a)	bákí	bak	-i (MS)	black
(b)	báká	bak	-a (FS)	black
(c)	bákàké	bak-	ake (PL)	blacks

The stem saab- 'new' in (6) uses agreement suffixes -oo, -uwa and -abbi while bak- 'black' in (7) uses -i, -a and -ake agreement suffixes. It will be shown in (8) that what Yusuf considers agreement suffix in (5) is actually a combination of an agreement suffix and a location marker. The location marker indicates the positioning of the adjective relative to the head noun (N). There are two such location markers, namely prenominal location marker which marks prenominal occurrence of the adjective and post-nominal location marker which marks postnominal occurrence of the adjective. To illustrate, consider once more the adjective stem far-

'white' in (5). The examples in (5) are clear cases of postnominal adjectives because each carries a postnominal location marker as shown in (8).

(8)	<u>Adjective</u>	<u>Stem</u>	<u>Agreement suffix</u>	<u>Postnominal marker</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
a)	fárif	far-	-i (MS)	-i	white
b)	fáraá	far-	-a (FS)	-a	white
c)	fáraareé	far-	-aare (PL)	-e	white

The postnominal location marker is a copy of the final vowel of the agreement suffix. Thus, where agreement suffix comprise of a single vowel only, that vowel is the one to be copied as postnominal location marker as in (8a) and (8b). This is always the case where the agreement element carries the feature [+singular]. Where the agreement suffix carries the feature [+plural], it is always realized as V_1CV_2 . V_2 is therefore the final vowel of the agreement suffix and is to be copied as the postnominal location marker as indicated in (8c). The prenominal location marker, on the other hand, is realized as -a (for masculine singular and plural adjectives) and -r (for feminine singular adjectives). The prenominal location marker is located between the adjective and the

noun. The prenominal location marker, being an enclitic (bound morpheme), cliticizes to the adjective at PF. The prenominal location markers for the adjective stem far- 'white' are illustrated in (9).

(9)	<u>Stem</u>	<u>Agreement suffix</u>	<u>Prenominal marker</u>	<u>Adjective</u>	<u>Noun</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
(a)	far	-i (MS)	n	fárín	doókii	white horse
(b)	far-	-a (FS)	r	fáráǎ	ákúyaa	white goat
(c)	far-	-aare (PL)	n	fáràarén	gídàajeé	white horses

In view of the internal composition of adjectives depicted in (8) and (9), we claim that an adjective is basically stem, agreement suffix and a location marker (which indicates prenominal or postnominal occurrence with a given noun). In this regard, the adjective is like other specifiers in Hausa which are also marked for prenominal or postnominal occurrence. In chapter two of the present study we shall discuss in some detail the nature of adjectival modification in Hausa.

1.1.1.4 The category 'grade'

A general assumption in the Parsonian verbal system, as in all previous works on the Hausa verb structure, is

that all verbs in Hausa, without exception, fall into two major types: regular verbs and irregular verbs. The basis for the division is exclusively morphological, with the regular verbs comprising two morphological units, verbal base and final vowel termination. A tone pattern is superimposed on this verb structure. This is the bi-morphemic theory of the structure of the verb ((10) below) advocated by Parsons (1960) and Eulenberg (1972) among others.

(10)

The final vowel or termination and the tone pattern according to Parsons (1960: 29-36), constitute the 'grade' of the verb. The 'grade' combines with the abstract verbal base to allow surface realization of a full verb. The examples under (11) illustrate the structure of the Hausa di-syllabic verb in the Parsonian system.

(11) <u>Full verb</u>	<u>Verbal base</u>	<u>Termination</u>	<u>Tone Pattern</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
kaámà	*kaam-	-a	High-Low	catch
sàyí	*say-	-i	Low-High	buy
káshè	*kash	-e	High-Low	kill
zúbáǎ	*zub-	-aǎ	High-High	throw away
koómoó	*koom-	-oo	High-High	return
dáfú	*daf-	-u	Low-High	be well cooked
shigá	*shig-	-a	Low-High	enter

Seven grades have been identified (see (13) below) and every abstract verbal base must operate at least one of the seven grades in order to attain surface realization as full verb. Consequently, all regular verbs in the language have been classified into seven morphologically distinct groups on the basis of 'grade'. Each grade is further subdivided into forms which are syntactically determined. Parsons (1960, 1962) referred to the forms as A-form, B-form, C-form and D-form and are defined in (12).

(12)

- A-form:** The form of the 'grade' used if the verb is intransitive or transitive but with a suppressed or zero object.
- B-form:** The form of the 'grade' used if a pronoun object follows the verb.
- C-form:** The form of the 'grade' used if a noun object follows the verb.
- D-form:** The form of the 'grade' used if a dative phrase follows the verb.

Following Newman (1973:300), we present in (13) the Parsonian verbal grade system showing the phonological shape of the recurring forms of the seven grades.

(13)

	<u>Grade</u>	<u>A-Form</u>	<u>B-Form</u>	<u>C-Form</u>	<u>D-Form</u>
1	Termination	-aa	-aa	-a	-aa
	Tone	H-L(H)	H-L(H)	H-L(L)	H-L(H)
2	Termination	-aa	-ee	-i	-aa
	Tone	(L)L-H	(L)L-H	(L)L-H	(H)L-H
3	Termination	-a	-	-	-
	Tone	L-H(L)	-	-	-
4	Termination	-ee	-ee	-e	-ee
	Tone	H-L(H)	H-L(H)	H-L(L)	(H)L-H

	<u>Grade</u>	<u>A-Form</u>	<u>B-Form</u>	<u>C-Form</u>	<u>D-Form</u>
5	Termination	-ar	-ar	-ar	-ar
	Tone	H-H(H)	H-H(H)	H-H(H)	H-H(H)
6	Termination	-oo	-oo	-oo	-oo
	Tone	H-H(H)	H-H(H)	H-H(H)	H-H(H)
7	Termination	-u	-	-	-
	Tone	(L)L-H	-	-	-

Assumptions about the grade include the suggestion that it comprises final vowel and tone pattern which are added to the verbal base (Newman (1973:298)).

The grade also carries semantic property (Parsons (1961:13-28)). Strict subcategorization in verbs is marked by the 'grade'. Despite this description of the 'grade' element, it was never given any specific category status in the literature. In chapter three of the present study, the 'grade' will be categorized as a functional element 'grade' following ideas in Abney (1987) and it is claimed to play a more prominent role than is assumed in the Parsonian verbal system.

1.1.2 Previous studies on relations amongst categories in Hausa clause structure

Previous studies on relations amongst categories in the clause are essentially on relations in the verbal component of the clause. These studies include the pioneering work of Parsons (1960) 1962, 1971/72), Newman (1973) and Halpern (1991). The studies are on verbal base-grade relation and on verb-syntactic environment relation. It must be pointed out however that these are not the only relations obtaining amongst categories in the clause. The present study identifies other relations such as head-complement relation and chain-link relation.³ Meanwhile, we shall revisit works on verbal base-grade relation and on verb-syntactic environment relation. The revisitation of these works is necessary in view of the inaccuracy of the claims made in their basic assumptions.

³ These relations are discussed in chapter four of the present study where all relations obtaining in the clause are analysed using an agreement-oriented analysis.

1.1.2.1 Verbal Base-Grade relation

Assumptions about the verbal base in the Parsonian verbal system include the observation according to Parsons (1962:10) that a verbal base is entered into the lexicon 'bare' without tone and final vowel. The basic generalized meaning of the verb is carried by this underlying form (i.e. the 'bare' verbal base, e.g., *kor- 'drive away'; *zub- 'throw away'; *say- 'buy'). The tone and termination (or final vowel) which constitute the 'grade', add their semantic properties to the verbal base but do not change its essential meaning as shown by the following examples.

- (14) (a) koóráa (grade 1) 'drive away' V.
 (b) koóróó (grade 6) 'drive towards oneself'
 (c) sáyí (grade 2) 'buy' V.
 (d) sáyóó (grade 6) 'buy and bring forward'.

Verbal bases are supposed to be neutral free-floating morphemes that can only achieve surface realization by the selection and incorporation of a grade. The Parsonian verbal grade system upholds that verbal bases select grades. Similarly, Eulenberg (1972) points out that a

verb is listed in the lexicon as a base (or stem) and is then subjected to a determinative insertion rule which adds a grade to it. The determinative insertion rule is as follows.

(15) $\text{H stem H} \rightarrow \text{H stem + grade H}$

A major defect of Parsons-Eulenberg's account of the verbal base-grade relation is the failure of the determinative insertion rule (15), which arbitrarily adds a grade to a verbal base, to specify what actually governs the selection of a 'grade' by a verbal base. That is to say, why does a given verbal base select particular grade form? We intend to propose in chapter four a 'matching theory' based on the assumption that verbal bases select grade forms with matching features. This being the case, it follows that verbal bases cannot be 'bare' in the lexicon as proposed in the Parsonian account. We shall assume that a verbal base must carry relevant features, including tone feature for it to be identified by a grade form with matching features. We shall show further that the 'grade' also contains more features than just the tone feature mentioned

in the Parsonian account to enable it fully identify a given verbal base. The matching theory advocated in the present study is indicative of an agreement relation in the 'verbal base-grade' relationship.

1.1.2.2 Verb-Syntactic environment relation

We turn to the relation between verb and the syntactic environment⁴ that follows it immediately. The Parsonian verbal system upholds the view that the syntactic environment determines the grade form. A crucial issue in respect of verb-syntactic environment relation is to establish whether or not the syntactic environment actually determines the grade form as claimed in the Parsonian verbal system. Notice that the Parsonian position on this matter is based on the assumption that the verbal base is always 'bare' (i.e. devoid of features) and that for the verbal base to function (i.e. take a grade and become a full verb), a predetermined syntactic

4 'Syntactic environment' (as used here and generally in Hausa grammar) is a cover term for those particular elements that follow the full verb immediately, the elements being noun object, pronoun object, trace, dative phrase, clausal complement and zero object. Notice that adverbial and prepositional phrases only apparently follow the verb immediately hence the verb does not take them as complements. Notice also that

environment has to follow it. This being the case, it was concluded that the grade form of the verb is determined by the syntactic environment. In chapter four of the present study, we shall show that contrary to the position taken in the Parsonian framework, the syntactic environment does not determine the grade form but that essentially, the grade relates to the verbal base to form the full verb. It is the full verb, with all its attendant syntactic and semantic characteristics, that determine the kind of syntactic environment to follow it. Our position is based on the strong observation that the verbal base cannot be 'bare' in the Parsonian sense. In the previous section, we hinted that the verbal base must carry relevant features for it to associate with a matching grade form to produce a full verb.

1.1.2.3 Alternation in grade forms

In (13) above, it was shown that a given grade may have up to four forms (A,B,C and D forms) each form accommodating a particular syntactic environment. These forms are referred to as 'grade forms'. The general assumption is that since the 'grade forms' are variants

here 'syntactic environment' is used narrowly to refer to only postverbal elements. In the wider linguistic literature, the term is not restricted to postverbal elements.

of a single grade, they must relate to one another. The relationship between grade forms is captured through an 'alternation' theory. Consequently, various theories of alternation in the grade forms such as the shortening theory of alternation, the lengthening theory of alternation and the theory of hierarchy of relative strength have been proposed in the literature. We present below a summary and a critique of each.

SHORTENING THEORY

Shortening theory of alternation in the forms of the grade is advocated by Parsons (1960, 1962, 1971/72), Eulenberg (1972) and Halpern (1991). Parsons and Eulenberg on the one hand advocate derivational approach to shortening, while Halpern on the other hand advocates a context-sensitivity approach. The basic idea of shortening is that the grade form is basically represented by a long vowel but gets shortened if followed immediately by a noun object. The Parsonian verbal grade system upholds that relationship between the various forms of a grade is established through a rule of shortening. One form of the grade is considered basic and other forms

are said to derive from the basic form. Parsons, following the tradition of Hausa lexicographers, also chooses the A-form as basic or citation form. Parsons (1960:23) states that "form A is the form under which a verb is quoted in isolation ... and this may therefore logically be considered as basic form." Now, to relate A-form with other forms and in particular the C-form⁵ (see (13) above), a derivational rule is required. The fact that A and B forms are phonologically identical (the vowel termination in both forms is long) precludes the need for any special rule to derive B-form from A-form.⁶ C-form must however be derived from A-form, and Parsons postulates a shortening rule (16) in which the long vowel termination of the basic A-form shortens before a non-pronominal direct object.

5 With the exception of grades 5 and 6, C-form is represented by a short vowel in all grades, hence the special attention given to it.

6 This statement might not hold true if (13) is taken into account. However, in chapter four, we shall show that the only grade forms of grade 3 and 7, -a and -u respectively, are indeed C-forms. The -ar grade form of grade 5 is also considered a long form.

C derived from the intransitive A-form which is considered basic form. That is to say, it is difficult to justify how transitive forms could be derived from intransitive forms. We maintain that the derivational account of shortening does not plausibly account for the functional dissimilarity (transitivity versus intransitivity) in the grade forms.

Eulenberg (1972:12-15) considers yet another angle of arguing in support of the shortening rule⁷ which appeals to economy in the scope of rule application, suggesting that a rule that has a smaller domain of application is more economical than one that applies to a wider domain. Thus, whereas suffix (=final vowel) shortening is required in only one environment (one in which the element following the verb is the direct noun object), suffix lengthening on the other hand is required in three environments (in which the element following the verb is either zero object, trace or dative phrase). This argument culminates into what Eulenberg refers to as

⁷ We shall see on p 31 that Eulenberg (1972) also advocates a lengthening theory of alternation as a possible alternative to the shortening theory.

environmental complexity in terms of whether or not a rule applies positively. An environment in which a rule applies may be stated positively, i.e., "the rule applies in the following environment ..." or negatively as "the rule applies in all environments except ..." or "the rule blocks in the following environment ...". A positively stated rule, argued Eulenberg, is more natural than one stated negatively. By this analogy, Eulenberg assumes that the suffix shortening rule is more natural than the suffix lengthening rule. A strong objection to this judgement is that it is quite subjective since no objective assessment can really be made to determine the positivity or negativity of an environment. Another objection is that the positive or negative application of the rule cannot just allow one to derive a transitive form from an intransitive basic form.

Halpern (1991), following Hayes (1990), proposes a rule of lexical phonology, the Hausa shortening rule, to deal with the alternation in the form of the grade of the verb. Halpern assumes a context-sensitivity approach to shortening. Thus, phonologically realized syntactic context such as the lexical noun object attracts the short form of the grade of the verb, while phonologically non-

verb in particular prepositional phrases (PPs) do not license the short vowel form." This observation is illustrated in (19).

(19) (a) $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ $y\acute{a}$ $\acute{a}$ $*ka\acute{a}m\grave{a}a/ka\acute{a}m\grave{a}$ $kiffif$
 Audu 3MS NF PERF catch noun object
 fish
 (Audu caught a fish)

(b) $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ $y\acute{a}$ $\acute{a}$ $f\acute{u}r\check{t}\grave{a}/f\acute{u}r\check{t}\grave{a}n$
 Audu 3MS NF PERF mention
 [$c\hat{e}ewa\acute{a}$ $L\acute{a}w\grave{a}n$ $za\acute{a}$ $y\grave{a}$ $zo\acute{o}$]
 CP that FUT 3MS come
 (Audu mentioned that Lawan will come)

(d) $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ $y\acute{a}$ $\acute{a}$ $*ka\acute{a}m\grave{a}/ka\acute{a}m\grave{a}a$ [$d\grave{a}$ $k\acute{a}rfif$]
 Audu 3MS NF PERF PP
 catch with strength
 (Audu held (something) tightly)

Halpern also draws attention to the fact that "Hausa Shortening is oblivious to the internal structure of the object that follows the verb" without mentioning why that should be so. In example (20) below, from Halpern (1991: 10), an NP object to the verb $s\grave{a}y\acute{í}$ 'buy' has been

realized variously in (i) through (iv) as a noun, a noun + modifier, a noun + a genitive NP complement and a noun + a relative clause modifier.

(20)

i) Audù yá á sáyí [NP gídaá]
 Audu 3MS NF PERF buy house

(Audu bought a house)

ii) Audu yá á sáyí [NP gídaá babbá]
 Audu 3MS NF PERF buy house big

(Audu bought a big house)

iii) Audù yá á sáyí [gída [-á Lával]]
 NP N GEN NP
 Audu 3MS NF PERF buy house of Lawal

(Audu bought Lawal's house)

iv) Audù yá á sáyí [gída -à [dà múkèe sò]]
 NP N DET REL
 CLAUSE

Audu 3MS NF PERF buy house the which we like

(Audu bought the house that we like)

We point out that Halpern's assumption that "Hausa

shortening is oblivious to the internal structure of the object that follows the verb" follows from the natural fact that the context-sensitivity requirement of the Hausa shortening rule is essentially to the N, head of NP and not to any optional element in the NP. This requirement is satisfied in (20). A controversial aspect of Halpern's context-sensitivity theory of shortening however relates to the issue of phonological status of pronominal direct object. Halpern assumes that pronominal direct objects are phonologically non-realized syntactic contexts which attract the long form of the grade. But pronominal direct objects are indeed phonologically realized syntactic contents. This being the case, Halpern's Hausa shortening cannot explain why a pronominal direct object, which is a phonologically realized element, cannot trigger shortening as shown in (21).

(21)	Áudù	yá	á	•kaámà/kaámà	shí
	Audu	3MS	NF	PERF	pronoun object
				catch	it/him

(Audu caught it/him)

we wish to observe that the failure of shortening in (21) follows from the natural facts of Hausa that shortening occurs only with direct noun objects. Thus, Halpern's position that all phonologically realized syntactic contexts must necessarily trigger shortening cannot be quite correct. Another defect of the context-sensitivity Hausa shortening rule is that it cannot account for cases involving grades 3 and 7 which are traditionally considered intransitive verbs.⁸

Intransitive verbs do not take a complement and by Hausa shortening rule, grades 3 and 7 verbs cannot therefore shorten their terminal vowels since they do not take a complement. However, grades 3 and 7 verbs have short terminal vowels, even though they do not take phonologically realized complements. Thus, the Hausa shortening rule cannot explain the situation involving grades 3 and 7 verbs as shown in (22).

⁸ But grades 3 and 7 verbs are inherently passive in their meaning which renders the traditional intransitivity account inappropriate. A recent analysis of grades 3 and 7 (Tuller 1990) captures their real status as unaccusative verbs. That is to say, their passive morphology renders them incapable of assigning (objective) Case, hence their inability to allow a direct object.

(22) (a) Mángwàrò yá á nuúná
 mango 3MS NF PERF ripe (grade 3)
 (Mango has ripen)

(b) Mútàaneé sú ń kàarú
 people 3PL NF PERF increase (grade 7)
 (People have increased)

LENGTHENING THEORY

The lengthening theory of alternation in the form of the grade of the verb is advocated by Eulenberg (1972) (cf Eulenberg (1972:7-16)) and by Newman and Jaggar (to appear) as substantiated in Halpern (1991). Eulenberg (1972) and Newman and Jaggar (to appear) advocate a derivational approach to the operation of the lengthening theory. The basic idea of lengthening as in Eulenberg (1972) is that there is an underlying form with a short final vowel which is lengthened in all environments except before a noun direct object. Newman and Jaggar also assume an underlying form with a short final vowel, but add that the underlying form should have a high tone on the short final vowel and from which a surface form with long final

vowel and low tone is derived. Halpern dubbed the tone changing requirement as 'Hausa Weakening'.

Eulenberg (1972:9-11) gives two arguments in support of the augmentative (lengthening) rule. The first argument relates to the fact that there exists some Hausa verbs such as shaá 'drink', bíyaá 'pay' and all grade 6 verbs (ventives) with long terminal vowels when followed by direct noun object as in the following examples.

(23)

(a) Áudù yá á shaá rúwaá
 Audu 3MS NF PERF drink water

(Audu drank water)

(b) Áudù yá á bíyaá kúdíí
 Audu 3MS NF PERF pay money

(Audu paid in money)

(c) Áudù yá á kaáwoó kuúraá
 Audu 3MS NF PERF bring hyena

(Audu brought a hyena)

Examples in (23) would seem to be counter-example to the Hausa lengthening theory which requires that a verb must take a short final vowel if followed by a noun direct object. However, Eulenberg points out that an obvious explanation for why the verbs in (23) do not have short terminal vowels is that they are 'phonologically unusual'. We wish to point out that there is nothing 'unusual' in the phonological behaviour of the verbs under consideration (i.e. grade 6 ventives)⁹. The fact that verbs in this grade have a long terminal vowel (instead of short) with a following direct noun object is no anomaly at all. To insist, as does Eulenberg, that this grade must conform with other grades in having a short vowel before a noun direct object (as would be demanded by a typical phonological account) is a clear testimony that a phonological account is perhaps not the most suitable for explaining the phenomenon. An alternative analysis has been proposed in the present study in which the relation between a verb and the following syntactic environment is considered.

9 The phonological rule of lengthening also fails with grade 5 operating verbs (causatives). The rule fails to capture relation between grade forms of grade 5 verbs since no short form of the grade is available. All grade 5 forms are long as will be shown in chapter four.

agreement relation involving matching features (see chapter four).

Another argument against the lengthening theory relates to the existence of a large number of verbs assumed to be intransitive verbs in the Parsonian system. These verbs end in a short vowel. Eulenberg (1972) specifically cites the grade 7 verbs dàfú 'fully cooked', dàdú 'get increased', rùfú 'be well closed' etc.) all of which terminate in -u (short) with -Low-High tone pattern. Eulenberg assumes that all verbs operating grade 7 are intransitive verbs and should terminate in a long vowel. But recent developments in the study of Hausa verbs, in particular, Tuller (1990), have shown that grades 3 and 7 verbs are unaccusative verbs and not intransitive verbs (see footnote 6). Assuming the unaccusativity status of grades 3 and 7 verbs, the present study will consider the grade forms -a (for grade 3) and -u (for grade 7) as C-form not A-form as in the Parsonian verbal system.

The Hausa Lengthening rule of Newman and Jaggard is stated as follows.

(24) $V \rightarrow VV / \text{---} H$

(The rule applies to a verb with an overt object)

As for the Hausa Weakening rule, Newman and Jagggar state that "the tone change would seem to represent weakening of an unstressed light syllable." Newman and Jagggar's rules also obey an ordering constraint, with the lengthening rule preceding the tone-changing rule. Their proposal assumes an underlying form of verbs with a short final vowel and a high tone on the final vowel. The derivation of a surface form from an underlying representation such as kařanta 'read' proceeds as follows.

(25) Underlying representation:	kářántá
	H L H
Hausa Lengthening:	kářántáá
	H H H
Hausa weakening:	-----
Derived Verb:	kářántáá
	H L H

Rule ordering in Newman and Jagggar's proposal is strict, with the lengthening rule (Hausa Lengthening)

necessarily preceding the tone rule (Hausa Weakening). A reversal in the order of application of these rules leads to ill-formed surface derivations as in the following example.

(26) Underlying representation:	<u>káǎántá</u>
	H L H
Hausa Weakening:	<u>káǎántà</u>
	H $\bar{L}$ $\bar{L}$
Hausa Lengthening:	<u>káǎántáa</u>
	H $\bar{L}$ $\bar{L}$
Derived Verb:	* <u>káǎántáa</u>
	H $\bar{L}$ $\bar{L}$

A major weakness of Newman and Jaggar's Lengthening rule is that it fails to capture the real phenomena for which it sought to explain. Evidence of this comes from the numerous counter-examples to the basic assumptions of their lengthening rule. Cases abound where the rule applies to verbs with overt objects. Thus, all ventives

(grade 6 verbs) and causative (grade 5 verbs) and a handful of verbs such as shaá 'drink', bíyaá 'pay' kíraá 'call', jíraá 'wait' are counter-examples to the lengthening rule as shown by the following examples.

(27)

(a) Alí yá á kaáwoó [kúdíí]
 Ali 3MS NF PERF bring NP money
 (Ali brought some money)

(b) Alí yá á kíraá [Muúsaá]
 Ali 3MS NF PERF call NP Musa
 (Ali called Musa)

(c) Alí yá á sáyáãr dà [moótàrsà]
 Ali 3MS NF PERF sell NP car his
 (Ali sold out his car)

Notice that in (27), each of the verbs kaáwoó, kíraá and sáyáãr has a long grade form and is followed by a direct NP object. Newman and Jaggar's rule of lengthening does not allow a long grade form to be followed by a direct NP object!

THE THEORY OF HIERARCHY OF RELATIVE STRENGTH

In addition to the use of phonological rules (shortening and lengthening) to explain the alternation in the form of the grade of the verb, Eulenberg (1972:17) also suggests a theory of hierarchy of relative strength. Eulenberg points out that the motivation for the theory derives from the fact that "in all transitive verbs whose form before a pronoun direct object is different from that before a noun direct object, the pre-pronoun form is longer than the pre-noun form". These facts are illustrated using the transitive verb koónà 'burn'.

(28)

(a) Áudù yá á koónà [tákàĩdaá]
 Audu 3MS NF PERF burn NP direct noun object
 paper

(Audu burnt a paper)

(b) Áudù yá á koómàa [tá]
 3MS NF PERF burn pronominal direct object
 it

(Audu burnt it)

The theory of hierarchy of relative strength assumes that the alternation in the form of the grade of the verb

(-a ~-aa) as depicted above, signifies 'hierarchical relationship holding among the categories noun, verb, and pronoun, with the relationship between verb and noun being the strongest and that between verb and pronoun the weakest. Eulenberg argues that translating the relative strength in terms of reductive (shortening) rule would mean that "a noun is strong enough to shorten the ending on the verb to which it is linked as direct object, but a pronoun object, being weaker than the verb, would not be able to effect such a shortening". Eulenberg argues further that the relative strength is also translatable in terms of augmentative (lengthening) rule. The verb is said to be stronger than the direct object pronoun. That being the case, the verb "asserts this strength by means of lengthening"; conversely, the noun is stronger than the verb, and "the verb could not lengthen in the presence of noun, the noun itself would belong to a stronger category". The claim that alternation in the form of the verb in Hausa embodies an abstract system of relative strength cannot be justifiably substantiated taking into account the fact that there is no empirical means of determining strength as it is

perceived in the theory of hierarchy of relative strength.

So far we have shown the inadequacies of the alternation theories in accounting for the relationship obtaining between grade forms. The real issue in the relation between grade forms of a particular grade is that they differ in their feature composition and that it is this feature composition which determines their selection by a verbal base. In chapter four we shall show that each grade form is a bundle of features and that two or more grade forms may share features, though there is always a feature, at least, to distinguish one grade form from another grade form.

1.1.3 Previous Studies on Movement in Hausa

One important work on movement in Hausa that is particularly relevant¹⁰ to the theme of the present study is Tuller's (1986) account of the operation of the Subjacency Condition and the Empty Category Principle (ECP) in Hausa. Subjacency condition and the ECP are two

¹⁰ Recall that one of the goals of the present study as stated in section 1.0 is to investigate the effect of agreement relations in movement, hence the relevance of Tuller's work.

universal conditions on movement in the Principles and Parameters framework. Subjacency condition ensures that movement of elements from extraction site to landing site may not be more than a certain distance. ECP ensures that the trace left behind by an antecedent is properly governed. Tuller (1986) discusses extensively the wh-movement in Hausa, observing that several syntactic constructions in the language display the properties of this $\bar{A}$ -movement such as containing a gap and being successive cyclic (or comp-to-comp). In addition, universal conditions on movement, namely the subjacency condition and the ECP, also operate in the language.

1.1.3.1 Subjacency operation in Hausa

Tuller's discussion on extraction centers around the standard subjacency islands, namely embedded question clauses, the complex noun clauses (relative clauses and noun complement clauses) and the sentential subject, all of which are said to abound in Hausa. According to Tuller, examples such as (29a) illustrate a typical case of extraction out of a subjacency island (= the wh -question clause) by the movement process of

wh-interrogation. Examples such as (29b and c) on the other hand, typically illustrate extraction out of wh-question clause by the movement process of relativization and focus-fronting, respectively.

(29) (a) Wh-interrogation out of wh-question clause

(Which book do you think Ali bought?)

(b) Relativization out of wh-question clause

(The book which they think who bought)

governed by the verb sàyaá. The movement of littaáfii to matrix specifier position had been successive cyclic and did not therefore violate subjacency. The movement of littaáfii in (29b) is to relativize the matrix clause hence it is referred to as relativization.

In (29c), a definite NP wáni littaáfii 'a certain book' was originally in the object position of the embedded sàyaá -clause before it was first focused to the specifier position of the embedded clause and later to the specifier of the matrix clause. The definite NP move successive cyclic and this is referred to as focus-fronting since its main objective was to focus the embedded object. The trace *t* of wáni littaáfii is lexically governed by sàyaá and subjacency could not have been violated since the movement had been successive cyclic. Tuller's discussion in respect of the operation of the subjacency condition in Huasa focuses essentially on the varied extraction facts exhibited by relativization on the one hand and by other forms of extraction notably focus-fronting and wh-interrogation on the other hand. The discussion centers around the standard subjacency islands mentioned earlier on. Extraction out of these subjacency

islands is generally excluded by the wh-island constraint, the complex noun phrase constraint and the sentential subject constraint. These constraints are the core cases that the subjacency condition, as a single universal condition on movement, is meant to replace. Tuller (1986:80) examines a collection of Hausa data on extraction out of subjacency islands by relativization, wh-interrogation and focus-fronting, and arrives at the following acceptability judgements.

- (30) (a) elements may be relativized out of a subjacency island as shown by examples (31a), (32a) and (33a) below.
- (b) elements may not be extracted out of subjacency islands by wh-interrogation and focus-fronting as shown by examples (31b and c), (32b and c) and (33b and c) below.

(31) Extraction out of embedded wh-question clause

(a) by relativization

littaáfi-n dà_J [S ká ø sán

book-the which 2MS NF know
PERF

[S' waa₁ [S e₁ yá ø ãubùutaa e_J]]]

who 3MS NF write
PERF

(The book (that) you know who wrote)

(b) by wh-interrogation

* wàné littaáfi_J [S ká ø sán

which book 2MS NF know
PERF

[S' waa₁ [S e₁ yá ø ãubùutaa e_J]]]

who 3MS NF write
PERF

(Which book do you know who wrote?)

(c) by focus-fronting

* wání mûtúm_J [S ká ø sán
 ↑
 certain man 2MS NF know
 PERF

[S' mée₁ [S e_J yá ø rúbùutaá e₁]]]
 ↑ ↑
 what 3MS NF write
 PERF

(A certain man you know wrote what)

(32) Extraction out of embedded relative clause

(a) by relativization

Mùtúmí-n dà₁ [S ká ø sán
 ↑
 man-the who 2MS NF know
 PERF

[NP líttaáfi-n dà_J [e₁ yá ø rúbùutaá e_J]]]
 ↑ ↑
 book-the which 3MS NF write
 PERF

(The man that you know the book that wrote)

(b) by wh-interrogation

* wàné mùtùm₁ [ká ø sán
 S
 which man 2MS NF know
 PERF

[líttaáfi-n dà_j [e₁ yá ø řúbùutaá e_j]]]
 NP
 book-the which 3MS NF write
 PERF

(Which man do you know the book that wrote?)

(c) by focus-fronting

* wání mùtùm₁ [ká ø sán
 S
 certain man 2MS NF know
 PERF

[líttaáfi-n dà_j [e₁ yá ø řúbùutaá e_j]]]
 NP
 book-the which 3MS NF write
 PERF

(A certain man you know the book wrote)

(33) Extraction out of sentential subject

(a) by relativisation

Mùtúmi-n dà₁ [céèwáá
 ↑ S'
 man-the who that

[e₁ yá á ãrúbùutà wánnàn líttááfií]
 S

3MS NF write this book
 PERF

yá baá ní màamaákíí

3MS NF give me surprise
 PERF

([The man that wrote this book] surprised me)

(b) by wh-interrogation

* [wáá₁ [céèwáá [e₁ yá á ãrúbùutà wánnàn líttááfií]]]
 S' comp S

who that 3MS NF write this book
 PERF

yá ø baá ní màamaákíí

3MS NF give me surprise
 PERF

(c) by focus-fronting

*wání mùtùm₁ [cêewaá [e₁ yá á řúbùutà littaáfíi]]
 S' S

certain man that 3MS NF write book

yá ø baá ní màamaákíi

3MS NF give me surprise
 PERF

([A certain man that wrote a book] surprised me)

Tuller attempted an explanation of the well-formedness of the (a) options of examples (31), (32) and (33) and the ill-formedness of the (b) and (c) options of the same examples. She observes that since wh-interrogation and focus-fronting obey subjacency, it should be concluded that S is in fact a bounding node in Hausa. She observes further that in the data above, something must be responsible for the consistent violation of the subjacency condition by relativization. Tuller points out that the subjacency violation of relativization structures in Hausa follows from the assumption that relativization may be base-generated and also from the fact that Hausa allows null subjects and null objects. These facts force the following major conclusion.

- (34) There is an asymmetry in Hausa regarding facts of extraction out of subjacency islands; that is to say, while elements may be relativized out of subjacency islands, they may not be extracted out of the subjacency islands by wh-interrogation and focus-fronting (Tuller (1986:80)).

Other conclusions in respect of movement and subjacency condition in Hausa are the following.

- (35) Hausa has null subject and null object and that the null subject-null object hypothesis for Hausa has direct relevance to subjacency facts. (Tuller (1986:319-320)).
- (36) Hausa has the phenomena of relative aspect marking (RAM) which plays a crucial role in Hausa movement structure. (Tuller (1986:109-110)).
- (37) Hausa has s-structure resumptive strategies for circumventing subjacency violations. (Tuller (1986:157-159))

I will show in chapter five of the present study that current insights into movement theory as in the Minimalist

theory (Chomsky 1992), a version of the Principles and Parameters framework, together with the crucial roles played by agreement relations in Hausa clause structure will have far reaching consequences on Tuller 's findings.

1.1.3.2 ECP operation in Hausa

Tuller's discussion of proper government of traces (or ECP) centers around the popular issue of 'that-trace' effect. Tuller (1986:159) argues that contrary to standard position in the Principles and Parameters framework which regards that-t configuration as an ECP violation, in Hausa, the gap t in the that-t configuration is a 'null pronoun' rather than a trace and is therefore not subject to the ECP. Notice that Tuller offers this explanation involving 'null pronoun' to justify why that-t configuration in Hausa does not constitute an ECP violation. In chapter five of the present study, we shall argue that Tuller's position on that-t effect in Hausa is untenable and that the postulation of the 'null pronoun' is counter-intuitive. We shall then offer an alternative agreement-oriented account which explains the possibility of that-t configuration in Hausa.

Tuller also discusses a case of purpose clause headed by the preposition dóm 'for'. She points out that such a clause, when used as complement clause, will always produce a structure in which ECP is violated. Thus, Tuller would exclude from well-formed structures, the structure (38) below containing a purpose clause headed by dóm.

(38)

'	Aishà	tá	nàa	neémán	mùtùm	[	dóm	[	tà	∅	àuraá	e	]]
	Aisha	3FS	NF	looking	man	PP	for	3FS	NF		marry		
			CONT	for						SUB			

(Aisha is looking for a man to marry)

But native judgement declares (38) a well-formed structure. In chapter five of the present study, I will give a detailed presentation of Tuller's movement analysis of (38) which is claimed to have rendered (38) an ECP violation. I will also propose an alternative non-movement, agreement-oriented account which captures native intuition, thereby declaring (38) a well-formed structure.

1.2 The Present Study

The present study will examine the Hausa clause structure in the light of recent insights into and modifications to the universal clause structure as in Pollock (1989) and refinements to Pollock as in Chomsky (1991, 1992). These insights include proposals on nature and content of categories, on split INFL and on the postulation of AGR-O or object agreement, the latter being very crucial in the analysis of agreement relations in the Hausa verbal component. We shall also propose an agreement-oriented approach to the study of the clause structure of Hausa and for accounting for the movement facts of Hausa. The study argues that aspects of movement such as distance of movement and traces of movement are best accounted for in Hausa in terms of agreement relations rather than solely by the standard subadjacency and the Empty Category Principle (ECP).

1.3 Theoretical Orientation

1.3.1 Preliminaries

The theoretical framework within which the present study is conducted is the Principles and Parameters framework, the most current syntactic theory in Chomskyan

linguistics. Principles and Parameters framework, as the name indicates, is an approach to linguistic analysis which allows principles of universal grammar (UG) to be parameterized (within limits) in order to accommodate idiosyncracies of individual languages.

1.3.2 Outline of Principles and Parameters Framework

It has been pointed out by Cook (1988) that classic Chomskyan models express the insight that language is a relationship between sound and meaning and that syntax connects the two. A crucial task of a grammar is therefore to find ways of describing actual sounds, of representing meaning and of describing the syntactic structure that connects them. How is the grammar organized so as to capture this insight? The organization of grammar in the Principles and Parameters framework is such that there are two levels of syntactic representation: d-structure and s-structure. The two levels of representation are related via the movement operations Move Alpha (Move α). D-structure is the level in which elements in the sentence are in their original location. Movement of elements in d-structure creates a new structure, the s-structure. Traces in s-structure

indicate original locations of the elements that were moved. Cook (1988:30) points out that "the essential bridging level between sound and meaning is s-structure, leading on the one hand to phonetic form (PF), on the other to logical form (LF)." Thus, s-structure is interpreted by both PF and LF components in their respective ways. The overall organization of grammar depicting relationship between levels of representation is shown in figure (39) adopted from Cook (1988).

(39)

The Principles and Parameters framework upholds that grammar entails 'continuous interaction between components (i.e. d-structure, s-structure, PF and LF) and sub-theories (or modules) embodying different principles and parameters' (Cook 1988:31). Some modules or principles of UG operate at d-structure level, ensuring possible d-structures. They include the X-bar theory, the Projection Principle, the Theta theory and the Case theory. The Projection Principle ensures that subcategorization properties of lexical items are observed at all levels of representation (d-structure, s-structure and LF). Theta theory deals with the assignment of Theta roles (semantic roles) such as Agent, Theme, etc. to elements in theta positions in the sentence and the theory is constrained by the Theta Criterion. Case Theory assigns abstract Cases to noun

phrases.

At s-structure, other principles operate, ensuring possible s-structure. They include the Projection Principle, the Case Filter, the Subjacency Condition and the Empty Category Principle (ECP). Case Filter ensures that there are no phonetically realized NPs without Case. The Subjacency Condition (or Bounding Theory) ensures that no movement from extraction site to landing site crosses more than one containing bounding node, the universal bounding nodes being NP, S and S-bar. The Empty Category Principle (ECP) ensures that empty categories (=traces of movement) are properly governed.

At LF, UG principles, including the Projection Principle, the Theta Criterion, the ECP, the Control Theory and the Binding theory operate to ensure possible LF representation. The Theta Criterion ensures that each argument bears one and only one theta role, and each theta role is assigned to one and only one argument. The Control theory is concerned with the choice of antecedent for PRO. The binding theory 'characterizes the interpretive relation between NPs and covers among

other things the distinction of pronouns and reflexive pronouns; in addition it plays an important role in the distribution of empty categories' (Sells, 1985: 67).

1.3.3 Modifications in the Principles and Parameters framework

The outline of the Principles and Parameters framework given in section 1.3.2 represents classic GB, the initial version of the Principles and Parameters framework. Classic GB had been subjected to reviews by Chomsky (Chomsky 1986a, 1986b, 1991, 1992) and by other researchers, for example Abney (1987) and Pollock (1989) Issues so far reviewed and which are particularly relevant to the themes of the present study include those related to classification of categories (including content and projection of INFL), clause structure and some aspects of movement theory.

1.3.3.1 Modifications pertaining to classification of categories

The classic GB approach to the classification of categories as in Chomsky (1981:48) is based on a version

of the X-bar theory which recognizes two categories of traditional grammar, namely substantive (or nominal) represented by the feature [+N] and include nouns and adjectives, and predicate represented by the feature [+V] and includes as its members verbs and adjectives. Chomsky refers to the substantives and the predicates as lexical categories and assumes further that a system based on the features [+N] and [+V] would yield the major lexical categories noun [+N, -V], verb: [-N, +V], adjective [+N, +V] and preposition-postposition [-N, -V]. This became known as the standard [+N, +V] category tetrachotomy. In the Barriers Framework, Chomsky (1986b:2) assumes further that the complementizer and the INFL (including tense and agreement elements and modals) are the non-lexical categories.

The feature analysis of categories is based on the assumption that categories are composite elements. For example, the substantive, represented by the feature [+N], defines a natural class 'a kind of super category'. Nouns and adjectives are members of this natural class and may be collapsed into a single category [+N] on the basis of this feature unification.

Abney (1987) challenges Chomsky's position in the Barriers framework on issues pertaining to the classification of categories in natural languages. For example, Abney (1987:62) was reluctant in adopting the standard category tetrachotomy especially the [+V] category. Abney assumes that categories are not necessarily defined by their feature compositions. Rather, the features define classes of categories. Abney also resists the designation 'non-lexical categories' for complementizer and INFL, arguing that complementizers and modals have lexical entries like any other word. Abney suggests that they should be referred to as 'Functional categories or elements' in contradistinction to 'non-functional (or thematic) elements'. On the whole, Abney proposes two major features [+F] and [+N] to define four major classes of syntactic categories as shown in (40).

(40)		[-F]	[+F]
	[-N]	V, AUX, P	I, C
	[+N]	N, A, Q, ADV	D

Abney's approach to the classification of

categories as outlined above led to his radical proposal of the DP Hypothesis. DP hypothesis entails that the traditional NP, which comprise Determiner (DET) and NP, should now be considered a projection of the functional category Determiner (D) with NP as its complement as indicated in (41).

(41)

It will be shown in chapter two of the present study that Abney's proposed DP hypothesis seems to be inadequate in respect of the analysis of double determiner NP constructions in Hausa.

Pollock (1989), following Abney's category classification, also challenges Chomsky's stand in the Barriers framework on the content and projection of INFL, arguing for a split-INFL. That is to say, AGR and TENSE, which used to be the two constituents of INFL, are now considered two independent Functional elements, each capable of projecting maximally to AGR phrase (AGRP) and Tense phrase (Tense P) respectively. The present study adopts the

split-INFL analysis for Hausa considering the fact that the split-INFL is quite consistent with the natural facts of Hausa. A detailed account of the Hausa INFL comes up in chapter three.

Another radical approach to issues in the Principles and Parameters framework is contained in the "Minimalist Programme for the Linguistic Theory" (Chomsky 1992) and is referred to as the minimalist framework. A refinement to Pollock's idea of having an independent agreement element AGR in the clause as in the Minimalist framework, posits that in addition to Pollock's single AGR element which is essentially subject agreement element (AGR-S), there is also an object agreement element (AGR-O). In chapter four, we shall provide evidence in support for the existence of AGR-O in the verbal component of the Hausa clause. The Hausa verb, whose maximal projection constitutes the verbal component of the clause, comprises essentially a verbal base plus an agreement element (AGR-O) which is traditionally referred to as 'grade'. It will be shown in chapter three of the present study that the Hausa verbal component is indeed the projection of the agreement

element (AGR=0) or the 'grade'.

1.3.3.2 Modifications pertaining to clause structure

The insights on category classification and projection discussed in the previous section (1.3.3.1) led to the ultimate modification to the structure of the clause. In the Barriers version of the Principles and Parameters framework (Chomsky 1986), the structure of a standard clause is given as in (42).

I contains (abstract) agreement element (AGR) and Tense. Finite clauses are [+AGR, +TENSE], meaning that they contain both agreement and tense features. Non-finite clauses are [-AGR, -TENSE].

Pollock (1989) revisited the clause structure, challenging the validity of the phrasal projection of

I. Pollock then proposes a split-INFL, arguing that each of the two components of I i.e. AGR and Tense, is a functional head and projects maximally into agreement phrase (AGRP) and Tense phrase (TenseP) respectively. The split-INFL analysis derives support from the extended endocentricity principle, a rigid X-bar theoretic condition on single headedness. The extended endocentricity principle, as in Radford (1990), is stated thus

- (43) Every phrase is a symmetrical projection of a single head word category, and every word category projects symmetrically into a corresponding phrase category.

A clause structure incorporating Pollock's split-INFL is as in (44).

Chomsky (1991, 1992) modifies Pollock's (1989) clause structure (44) above, arguing that there are two agreement elements in a clause. The articulated clause structure as in Chomsky (1992) is given in (45).

It was suggested in Chomsky (1991) that VP or V'' might contain an optional pre-VP adverb. The VP-adverb seems to be base-generated in the pre-verb position under VP adjoined to another VP as shown in (46).

Chomsky (1992) contains a refinement of the pre-verb VP-adverb analysis. The incorporation of the VP-internal subject hypothesis into the Minimalist framework forces the adoption of a [SPEC, VP] position from which the clausal subject NP raises to [SPEC, AGR-S] as shown in (47).

(47)

1.3.3.3 Modifications pertaining to movement theory

The classic GB approach to movement theory as in Chomsky (1981, 1986) posits a major movement operation, the rule $\text{move } \alpha$ which has the effect of moving anything anywhere. Chomsky (1982:55) observes that the following properties hold between a moved element and its trace

after move α had applied.

- (48)
- a) The trace is properly governed, i.e. it is subject to the ECP.
 - b) The antecedent of the trace is not in a theta position.
 - c) The antecedent-trace relation satisfies the subjacency condition.

The movement operation move α and the two conditions on movement, namely the subjacency condition and the Empty Category Principle (ECP) have been challenged recently leading to new insights in respect of their operations.¹¹ Major modifications to subjacency condition and the ECP appear in the Minimalist framework. The Minimalist framework, like the Barriers framework (Chomsky 1986b) and the Relativized minimality framework (Rizzi 1990), is a model of the Principles and Parameters approach to linguistic theory. The Minimalist approach to movement theory crucially differs from the classic GB approach owing to some radical assumptions embodied in the Minimalist framework. The radical assumptions concern the real motivation of movement, the position

¹¹ Chomsky (1986b:93) for example contemplates the idea that subjacency and the ECP are perhaps conditions on representations not conditions on movement.

of move α and the justification for the levels of representation d- and s-structures among others. A totally different view of these issues as in the Minimalist framework creates an essentially new outlook to the theory of movement. An important assumption of the Minimalist framework on movement concerns the motivation of movement, which in this framework, is assumed to be solely a morphological necessity. Morphological necessity includes requirement for Case (NP movement), scope of wh- operators and quantifiers (LF movement) and checking morphological properties of lexical elements (verb movement, tense raising, etc.) Movement is only allowed if motivated by any of those necessities, otherwise it would not be sanctioned within the Minimalist framework. The efficacy of this assumption in relation to Hausa is discussed in chapters three and four of the present study.

Another crucial assumption of the Minimalist framework is that the basic transformational operation move α is indeed operation Form chain. That is to say, move α can move anything anywhere, but such movement must yield chain or the derivation crashes at LF. This

assumption supports the previous one on motivation; i.e. only well motivated movements can form chains as indicated by the following examples.

(49) John_i seems [t_i to like Mary]

(50) * Mary_i John likes t_i

John and t in (49) form a chain (John, t) and the movement of John is motivated by Case requirement. In (50), (Mary, t) does not form a proper chain because the movement of Mary has no apparent motivation.

In summary, the Minimalist theory of movement upholds that the essential prerequisite for any movement is its motivation. A well motivated movement must yield a proper chain. This can be achieved through 'shortest movements' which will ultimately produce the required proper chain. An idiosyncrasy of Hausa is that agreement amongst constituents in the clause is more significant than the "shortest movement" strategy for yielding proper chains in a well motivated case of move α . In chapter five we outline the agreement-oriented approach to movement, showing how agreement relations in the clause serve to yield proper chains

(legitimate objects) without appealing to the 'shortest movement' strategy.

1.3.4 Application of the Principles and Parameters framework in the present study

The approach of the study in the adoption of the Principles and Parameters framework as a theoretical framework of analysis will be the amalgamation of relevant insights and ideas from the various versions of the Principles and Parameters framework to handle, albeit parametrically, specific issues. This is necessary in view of the fact that the present study comprises wide range of issues linked up together systematically and that no single version of the Principles and Parameters framework can satisfy the total needs of the study.

The adoption of the Principles and Parameters framework as the theoretical framework for the present study is not arbitrary. The study contains issues relating to the establishment of categories and their projections; the establishment of

an articulated clause structure; the establishment of agreement relations in the articulated structure and the establishment of the role of agreement in movement structures. Hausa has some peculiarities in respect of these issues and a theoretical framework, such as the Principles and Parameters framework which handles idiosyncracies of individual languages, is quite adequate for the analysis of the Hausa data. The Principles and Parameters framework is particularly suitable in two important respects. In the first place, the Principles and Parameters framework allows existing principles of UG to be parametrized so as to accommodate the idiosyncracies of Hausa; for example, agreement relations in the Hausa clause structure. Agreement in the Principles and Parameters framework and especially in the Minimalist version of the theory (Chomsky 1992:8-26), entails feature identification or feature checking. Feature checking as stipulated by checking theory, is conducted under a structural relation determined by c-command and government and by a functional element that shares morphological features with the element to be checked. Consider for example the issue of structural

case assignment in the Principles and Parameters framework. Structural Case assignment, in which an object NP is assigned accusative Case, is done under spec-head agreement relation. It has been suggested in the Minimalist theory as pointed in chapter three that AGR-O, the head of AGR-O phrase (AGR-O''), is a functional element that checks the morphological properties of object NP. The checking domain is the specifier position of AGR-O'', and object NP moves into this position to receive accusative Case from AGR-C under spec-head agreement. In Hausa, however, it is not only the canonical object NP that enters into agreement relation with AGR-O. As an idiosyncrasy, all elements (direct NP object, pronoun object, zero object, trace, clausal complement) that follow the verb directly in the verbal component must agree with AGR-O as well. This 'unusual' agreement relation is morphologically marked the way agreement relation involving direct NP object is marked. How is this 'unusual' agreement relation to be accounted for? I propose in the present work that the checking theory of the Minimalist framework be parametrized to account for the 'unusual' agreement relation, taking note of the fact that no Case is assigned in the 'unusual' agreement relationship. Detailed

discussion is presented in chapters three and four.

Secondly, the Principles and Parameters framework, apart from allowing parametrization of its principles, also allows the improvization of an alternative account to handle particular data. In this regard, we may consider the subjacency condition on movement. Every existing model of the principles and Parameters framework has its own formulation of the subjacency condition depicting peculiar insight into the operation of the condition. In classic Government and Binding theory (Chomsky 1981 for instance), subjacency is regarded as a condition on movement, with emphasis on distance of movement from extraction site to landing site. Long movement of an antecedent is likely to cross one or more bounding nodes, thereby violating the subjacency condition. Subjacency as a condition on chain-link has been advocated in the Barriers framework (Chomsky 1986b) and emphasis is on antecedent-trace relation. Antecedent and trace must form a chain, single or composite. Distance of movement between links

of a chain does not matter as long as chain link condition is satisfied. In the Minimalist framework, subjacency is reduced to an economy principle known as 'shortest movement condition'. The idea here is that if every linguistic expression must contain only legitimate objects, then in movement structures, only shortest movement can yield a proper chain. A proper chain is a legitimate object. Economy in movement is expressed in terms of shortest movement and movement of alpha is therefore restricted to shortest movement if only to allow yielding of legitimate objects. An idiosyncrasy of Hausa makes it necessary that agreement factors be taken into account in stating 'facts' of movement in Hausa. But none of the available approaches to subjacency condition mentioned above is sufficiently equipped to capture such facts. Another idiosyncrasy is that Hausa independently allows null subjects and null object and this makes it difficult to determine whether a given movement is subjacency violation or not. We shall show in chapter four that the null subject-null objects phenomenon of Hausa is an agreement issue and ideas in the Principles and Parameters framework will be exploited to formulate a more befitting alternative

agreement-oriented account to cater for movement in the language.

1.4 The Data

The present study intends to use Standard Hausa as its principal data source. Standard Hausa is the variety of Hausa used in all formal transactions as in broadcasting and newspaper writing; in textbooks and formal school teaching; in government documents and Hansard, etc. etc.

I provide most of the Hausa data, which is further verified by other native speakers. Other sources of data include written material such as written texts on grammar and literature, dictionaries of Hausa and academic dissertations.

Hausa is an Afro-asiatic language, belonging to the Chadic group. It is spoken mainly in Northern Nigeria and Southern Niger Republic. There are sizeable number of speakers in Northern Ghana, the Chad, the Cameroon, the Sudan and pockets of speakers in

Libya and several countries in West and Central Africa.

CHAPTER TWO

THE NOMINAL PHRASE (NP)

2.0 Preliminaries

The noun phrase (NP) is an important constituent of the clause. It occupies the subject and object positions, two argument positions that are crucial for agreement relations in the clause structure. In this chapter therefore, the internal complexity of the Hausa NP will be discussed, pointing out the various agreement relations obtaining between elements in the phrase and how these agreement relations affect the X-bar structure of the NP.

2.1 The Hausa NP Revisited

The NP is generally headed by a noun. In addition, the head noun may be optionally modified by an element such as the determiner (DET). The lexical head noun of the Hausa NP is optionally modified prenominally and/or post-nominally. Modifiers agree in gender and (in) number with the lexical head noun, with gender being neutralized in the plural. That is to say, with plural nouns, gender distinction is insignificant. These descriptive facts are captured by the NP constructions

in (51) in which a head noun of the NP is modified by a determiner prenominally in (51a-c), postnominally in (51d-f) and prenominally and postnominally in (51g-h).

- (51) (a) wání yaároò
 DET N
 3MS 3MS
 some boy (some/a certain boy)
- (b) wátá yaárínyàà
 DET N
 3FS 3FS
 some girl (some/a certain girl)
- (c) wádánsú yaaraá
 DET N
 PL PL
 some children (some/certain children)
- (d) rīigá ã̃
 N DET
 3FS 3FS
 gown the (the gown)

(e) wàndó	à		
N	DET		
3MS	3MS		
trousers	the		(the (pair of) trousers)
(f) gídàájé	à		
N	DET		
PL	PL		
houses	the		(the houses)
(g) wánf	yaárò	à	
DET	N	DET	
3MS	3MS	3MS	
some	boy	the	(another boy)
(h) wátá	riigá	ǎ	
DET	N	DET	
3FS	3FS	3FS	
some	gown	the	(another gown)

2.1.1 Nominal Modifiers

Three nominal modifiers are commonly identified in Universal Grammar (UG). They are Determiners, Adjuncts and Complements. These three universal modifiers are also available in Hausa. We discuss below their forms and function in the language.

2.1.1.1 DETERMINERS

Galadanci (1969, 1976), Jaggar (1977) and Yusuf (1991) among others, have discussed the determiner in Hausa. The present study identifies three major classes only. These are the Previous Reference Marker (PRM), The Demonstrative (DEM)¹² and the Quantifier (Q). The study also considers very closely the morphology of the determiners, pointing out that each determiner is a bundle of features, with each feature performing a particular function.

The Previous Reference Marker (PRM)

The previous reference marker marks definite reference (in a similar fashion with the English definite article). The noun that occurs with PRM must have been previously implied. PRM occurs only post-nominally. It is represented morphologically by a clitic -r (for feminine singular nouns) and -n (for masculine singular nouns and plural nouns). The PRM carries inherent gender and number agreement as shown

¹² The demonstrative subsumes Galadanci's (1976:34) indefinite specifier and interrogative specifier.

in the following examples

- (52) (a) yaárò ñ
 N PRM
 MS MS
 boy the (the boy)
- (b) riigá ð̣
 N PRM
 FS FS
 gown the (the gown)
- (c) mútáané ñ
 N PRM
 PL PL
 people the (the people)

The Demonstrative (DEM)

The demonstrative in Hausa is shown in the following paradigm.

(53)

	Prenominal occurrence	Postnominal occurrence
Masculine and feminine singular	wánnàn 'this'	nân 'this'
Plural	wádànnân 'these'	nàn 'these'

Examples

- (54)¹³
- a. wánnàn yaáròò 'this boy'
 - b. wánnàn yaárfínyàn 'this girl'
 - c. wádànnân yâaraá 'these children'
 - d. yaárò ò nân 'this boy'
 - e. yaárfínyà ÿ nân 'this girl'
 - f. yâará ñ nân 'these children'

(55)

	Prenominal occurrence	Postnominal occurrence
Masculine singular	wáncàn 'that'	cân 'that'
Feminine singular	wáccàn 'that'	cân 'that'
Plural	wádàncân 'those'	cân 'those'

Examples

- (56)
- a. wáncàn yaáròò 'that boy'
 - b. wáccàn yaárfínyàn 'that girl'
 - c. wádàncân yâaraá 'those children'
 - d. yaárò ò cân 'that boy'
 - e. yaárfínyà ÿ cân 'that girl'
 - f. yâará ñ cân 'those children'

13 The head N of the NP construction and its modifier (here the demonstrative nân) must agree in the features gender and number. This agreement is marked by the agreement markers n (for masculine singular and plural nouns) as in (54d and f), and ñ (for feminine singular nouns) as in (54e).

(57)

	Prenominal occurrence	Postnominal occurrence
Masculine singular	wàncán 'that'	nán 'that'
Feminine singular	wàccán 'that'	nán 'that'
Masculine and feminine singular	wànnán 'that'	nán 'that'
Plural	wàdànnán 'these'	wàdàncán 'those'

Examples

- (58) a. wànnán yaárò 'that boy' (referred)
 b. wànnán yaárínyà 'that girl' (referred)
 c. wàdànnán yâaraá 'those children' (referred)
 d. wàncán yaárò 'that boy' (referred)
 e. wàccán yaárínyà 'that girl' (referred)
 f. wàdànnán yâaraá 'those children (referred)
 g. yaárò ò nán 'that other boy'
 h. yaárínyà ò nán 'that other girl'
 i. yâarà ò nán 'those other children'

(59)

	Prenominal occurrence only	
Masculine singular	wání	'certain/some'
Feminine singular	wátá	'certain/some'
Plural	wádánsú ¹⁴	'certain/some'

Examples

- (60) a. wání yaárò 'a certain boy'
 b. wátá yaárínyà 'a certain girl'
 c. wádánsú yâará 'certain children'

(61)

	Prenominal occurrence only	
Masculine singular	wàné	'which'
Feminine singular	wàcè	'which'
Plural	wádànnè	'which'

Examples

- (62) a. wàné yaárò 'which boy?'
 b. wàcè yaárínyà 'which girl?'
 c. wádànnè yâará 'which children?'

I will show in the present study that prenominal

¹⁴ short form wású.

demonstrative is a bundle of features comprising location (prenominal) marker, agreement element (which marks gender and number agreement with the qualified noun)¹⁵ and a realization of the demonstrative proper as shown in (63).

15 The motivation for this analysis derives largely from the fact that the qualifier, which is also a determiner exhibits similar characteristics.

(63) Demonstrative 16	Prenominal marker	Gender- number agreement	Demonstrative proper
a) wánnàn 'this'	wá	ń	nàn
wáđànnan 'these'	wá	đàn	nan
b) wáncàn 'that'	wá	ń	càn
wáccàn 'that'	wá	ć	càn
wáđàncan 'those'	wá	đàn	can
c) wànnán 'that'	wà	̀n	nán
wáđànnán 'those'	wà	đàn	nán
wàncán 'that'	wà	̀n	cán
wáccán 'that'	wà	̀c	cán
wáđàncán 'those'	wà	đàn	cán

Notice that whereas the demonstrative proper is realized by the locative adverb nan/nàn/nán 'here' or càn/can 'there' in two forms of the demonstrative, i.e. this and that as shown in (53), (54) and (63) above, its

16 Notice that each of these demonstratives comprises a proper demonstrative stem, a location marker and gender-number agreement marker. Despite this composition, we must continue to refer to the chunk as 'demonstrative' in view of the fact that the location marker and the gender-number agreement

realization is however not so clear in the case of wání, wátá, wádánsú 'some/certain' and wàné, wàcè, wádànnè 'which'. Here there is a zero or non-phonetic realization of the demonstrative.

The Quantifier (Q)

Quantifiers in Hausa are represented by koówàné, 'every, each' (for masculine singular nouns) koówàcè 'every, each' (for feminine singular nouns), koówádànnè 'every, each' (for plural nouns), dúk 'all', kádán 'few' and dà yáwàa 'much, many'. The quantifiers representing 'every, each' occur only preminally as shown in the following examples.

- (64) (a) Koówàné yaáròo 'every child'
 (b) Koówàcè yaárínyàa 'every girl'
 (c) Koówádànnè mútàanéé 'every people'

The quantifier dúk 'all' occurs both preminally and postminally as shown in (65).

- (65) (a) dúk yáaraá 'all children'
 (b) yáaraá dúk 'all children'

The preminally occurring quantifiers koówàné, koówàcè and koówádànnè 'every, each', like the preminally occurring demonstratives enumerated in (63), are a bundle of features and Yusuf (1991:169) assumes that the quantifier "comprises

marker are obligatory components of the demonstrative and whose functions are to specify the demonstrative stem for location relative to and agreement with the modified noun.

a stem and an agreement suffix marking number and gender as shown in (66).

(66)	- <u>stem</u>	<u>AGR</u>
(a)	koówà	nè (MS)
(b)	koówà	cè (FS)
(c)	koówà	dànnè (PL)

Yusuf's analysis as presented in (66) above, is not exhaustive enough with respect to the composition of features that make up the prenominal quantifier. In the present study, we shall show that each of the prenominal quantifiers in (66) has the following feature composition.

(67)	Quantifier	Quantifier proper	Prenominal marker	Gender-number agreement marker	17
	<hr/>	<hr/>	<hr/>	<hr/>	
a)	Koówàné 'every'	koó	wà	nè (MS)	
b)	Koówàcè 'every'	koó	wà	cè (FS)	
c)	Koówàdànnè 'every'	koó	wà	dànnè (PL)	

2.1.1.2 ADJUNCTS

The adjunct in an NP is a maximal projection that gives additional information about the head N. Adjuncts in Hausa

17 Perhaps we may say here that with nè, n represents gender (masculine) and e number (singular); with cè, c represents gender (feminine) and e number (singular). dànnè may represent only number (plural) since gender is neutralized in the plural. Notice that in (63) we had a variant of dànnè in the form of dàn. See also footnote 23.

nominal phrase occur prenominally and/or postnominally. The prepositional phrase (PP), the adjective phrase (AP) and the relative clause (RC) are the maximal projections that serve as adjuncts in the Hausa nominal phrase. The prepositional phrase and the relative clause occur as postnominal adjuncts only. The adjective phrase occurs both as prenominal and postnominal adjunct. Consider the following example.

- (68) Maálàmiif [dàgà Tuúrái]
 N P NP PP
 teacher from Europe
 ((A) teacher from Europe)

We claim that (68) comprises a head N maálàmiif and a PP adjunct dàgà Tuúrái. In a head-adjunct structure such as (68), an adjunct expands an intermediate projection to another intermediate projection as represented in (69).

18 We observe that the adjective phrase in Hausa comprise only of the head adjective. A location marker is however encliticized to the adjective at PF.

Since adjuncts only expand intermediate projections, insertion is therefore possible between a head N (a zero level category) and an adjunct, hence the well-formedness of (70).

- (70) maálámif fárif [dàgà Tuúrái]
 N Adj P NP PP
 teacher white from Europe
 (a caucasian teacher from Europe)

An adjective phrase (AP) modifies a head N either prenominally as in (71a) or postnominally (71b).

(71) (a)

(new clock)

There is also an NP structure in Hausa comprising a head N and a relative clause modifier. The relative clause modifier is an adjunct as shown in (72).

((a) student who joined the army)

2.1.1.3 COMPLEMENTS

In Hausa, a noun N may take an NP complement, giving rise to one form of noun+noun construction.¹⁹ A typical noun+noun construction in Hausa is the genitive NP construction. In such constructions, there is always a genitive marker which marks a genitive relationship. Consider the following examples.

- (73) (a) daálibí [ń náháwù]
 N GEN N NP
 student of syntax (student of syntax)
- (b) mútàané [ń koògoó]
 N GEN N NP
 people of cave (people of the cave)
- (c) riigá [r̄ r úwáá]
 N GEN N NP
 gown of rain (rain coat)

The genitive marker is realized as ń (masculine singular and plural) in (73a and b) respectively and as r̄ (feminine singular) in (73c).²⁰ The genitive NP is an NP structure in

19 The appositive construction such as [$\text{Álì} \text{ àlkaálibí}$]
 N N
 (Ali the judge) is another form of N-N construction in Hausa.

20 Notice the phonetic similarity between the PRM's in (52) and the genitive markers in (73). Notice also that both carry gender-number features. However, the two elements differ in respect of tone pattern: whereas the genitive markers carry high tone, the PRMS carry low tone.

(74) (a) **bák-** **-f** **-ń** **gídaá**
 Adj AGR LOC N
 stem suf suf

[+Masc]
 [+Sing]

[+Masc]
 [+Sing]

bákín gídaá (black house)

(b) **gídaá** **bák-** **f-** **-f**
 N Adj AGR LOC
 [+Masc] stem suf suf
 [+Sing]

[+Masc]
 [+Sing]

gídaá bákif (black house)

Notice that a mismatch of features between the noun and the adjective produces ill-formed constructions as in (75).

(75) (a) ***bák** **-á** **-ń** **gídaá**
 Adj AGR LOC N
 stem suf suf [+Masc]
 [+Fem] [+Sing]

(b) ***gídaá** **bák-** **-á** **-á**
 N Adj AGR LOC
 [+Masc] stem suf suf
 [+Sing] [+Fem]
 [+Sing]

(c)	*bák-	àké	-ń	gídaá
	Adj	AGR	LOC	N
	stem	suf	suf	+Masc
		+PL		+Sing

(d)	*gídaá	bák-	-àké	-é
	N	Adj	AGR	LOC
	+Masc	stem	suf	suf
	+Sing		+PL	

So far, I have described the category adjective in Hausa. I have shown that adjective is so much related to the noun it modifies because they share all nominal features. This being the case, one may argue that Chomsky's (1981, 1986) standard feature analysis of the category adjective as [+N, +V] does not define the category adjective in Hausa since the adjective element in the language is wholly nominal. On the other hand, Abney's (1987) feature characterization of adjective as [+N, -F] describes fully the adjective element in Hausa which is wholly nominal [+N] and non-functional [-F].

2.1.2.1 Prenominal Modification

An important aspect of the relationship between noun and adjective in Hausa that has received considerable attention (cf Galadanci (1969), 1976), Tuller (1986), Yusuf (1991)) is the nature of prenominal modification of noun by adjective. A noun is modified by an adjective to its left (i.e. prenominally). As an idiosyncrasy, Hausa requires what is traditionally referred to as a linker n or r between the prenominal adjective and the noun as shown in (76).

(76) Adjective - -n/-r - noun

The status of the 'linker' has generated so much controversy in the literature, leading to different analyses for the structure in (76). We shall consider Tuller's compounding analysis, Yusuf's KP analysis and an alternative NP analysis advocated in the present study.

2.1.2.2 Tuller's account of prenominal adjectival modification: The Compounding Analysis

Tuller (1986:35) observes that adjectives in Hausa may appear prenominally or postnominally, "giving two possibilities for adjectival modification of a noun" as

illustrated in the following examples

(77) (a) saábó ñ zánèe
 Adj linker N
 new cloth
 (new cloth)

(b) zánèe saáboó
 N Adj
 cloth new
 (new cloth)

Tuller observes further that in structures like (77a) above, there is always a suffixed -n/-r linker between prenominal adjectives and the nouns they modify. As regards the status of the linker, Tuller suggests that it is not a case assigner and that following an idea by Stowell (1981) for English, the prenominal adjectives in Hausa are the result of word formation rule. Tuller concludes that the sequence adjectives plus noun (Adj. + N) in Hausa is a compound noun. Tuller's claim for Adj+N compounding leads to two other major claims in respect of scope and stacking facts. We shall now present Tuller's arguments for Adj+N compounding

and the scope and stacking arguments which Tuller claims to have supported the compounding analysis.

Tuller's Arguments

Firstly, fixed expressions, whose meanings are not the function of the meanings of their parts, must use the order Adj+N, forming Adj+N compounds. These compounds are illustrated in (78).

(78) (a)	fárfi	ń	mùtùm	
	Adj	linker	N	
	white		person	(caucasian)
(b)	já	ń	bàakif	
	Adj	linker	N	
	red		mouth	(cardinal bird)
(c)	kàráamá	ř	sállàh	
	Adj	linker	festival	(Ramadan Festival)
	small			

Tuller points out that the same words in the order N + Adj do not form compounds as shown in (79).

- (79) (a) m̀t̀m f̀r̀f
 N Adj
 person white (light skinned person)
- (b) b̀k̀f j̀á
 N Adj
 mouth red (red mouth)
- (c) s̀ll̀h k̀r̀m̀á
 N Adj
 festival small (small festival)

Secondly, that the compounding analysis above is correct, she goes on further to say that in NP constructions ^{containing} both prenominal and postnominal adjectives, the prenominal adjective plus the head noun form a compound noun (due to Adj+ N compounding) and that the postnominal adjective has scope over the sequence Adj+N. To illustrate, Tuller argues that the NP k̀r̀m̀á ́ r̀g̀á b̀k̀á 'small, black gown', comprising prenominal adjective k̀r̀m̀á, linker ́, head noun r̀g̀á and postnominal adjective b̀k̀á must be assigned the following structure.

- (80) [[k̀r̀m̀á ́ r̀g̀á] b̀k̀á]
 NP Adj N Adj

bákaá 'black', a postnominal adjective, has scope over the Adj+N compound kàrámá rígaá 'small gown'.

Thirdly, Tuller presents the stacking argument as follows: whereas more than one postnominal adjective may follow a noun as shown in (81a), stacking of prenominal adjectives is extremely marginal at best, and gets worse with increase in the number of prenominal adjectives being stacked as shown in (81b)

- | | | | | | | |
|------|-----|------------------|---------------|------------------------------|---|-----------------|
| (81) | (a) | <u>zánèe</u> | <u>kàrámi</u> | <u>bákí</u> | | |
| | | N | Adj | Adj | | |
| | | cloth | small | black (small, black, cloth) | | |
| | (b) | *[<u>kàrámi</u> | ń | [<u>bákí</u> | ń | <u>zánèe</u>]] |
| | | Adj | | Adj | | N |

Tuller did not expatiate further on the ill-formedness of (81b). However, we shall assume that the ill-formedness of (81b) follows from the fact that whereas by Tuller's compounding analysis [bákí ń zánèe] forms a compound noun (an Adj + N compound even though it is not a fixed expression), nonetheless, the prenominal adjective kàrámi cannot have scope over the compound [bákí ń zánèe] because of its prenominal location. Hence, the

ill-formedness of (81b).

We shall summarize Tuller's claims as follows:

- (82) (a) There is a category adjective in Hausa.
 (b) Adjective in Hausa may appear prenominally or postnominally.
 (c) N+Adj sequence is a simple NP comprising a head N and a modifying adjective.
 (d) Adj+ N sequence is a compound and gives rise to fixed expressions.
 (e) A postnominal adjective has scope over a preceding Adj+N compound.
 (f) Stacking of prenominal adjectives is marginal and this follows from the fact that a prenominal adjective does not have scope over a following Adj+N compound.

A Critique of Tuller's Claims

Yusuf (1991), quoting Stowell (1981:256), points out that a major critique on the compounding analysis is that "set expressions" enter into the lexicon straight and cannot, in principle, be the result of any productive linguistic process (morphological process of compounding

or syntactic process of phrase formation.

Another argument against Tuller's compounding analysis is that the sequence 'Adj-linker-Noun' is not exclusive to fixed expressions. Non-fixed expressions, which are clearly not compounds, appear in the same sequential order Adj-linker-Noun as shown by the following examples.

- (83) (a) kyàkkyaáwá ñ̃ yaárinnyàa
 Adj linker N
 beautiful girl (beautiful girl)
- (b) saábó ñ̃ zánèè
 Adj linker N
 new cloth (new cloth)
- (c) tsòofàffi ñ̃ gidàajeé
 Adj linker N
 old houses (old houses)

Since non-fixed expressions can as well use the order 'Adj-linker-Noun', it then follows that the compounding analysis must be weak. We consider next Tuller's claim on scope. The scope analysis, as presented above, follows from the compounding analysis. If compounding analysis were correct, then a postnominal adjective has scope over

Adj+N compound. Now that it has been shown that the compounding analysis cannot be correct, the scope argument must also be revisited. Thus, we suggest that the scope argument must be viewed in two ways. One, in established cases of fixed expressions such as the one in (78) above, a postnominal adjunct may have scope over a preceding Adj+N compound. Two, the scope argument does not hold in cases such as (83) above (with regular meanings) where compounding analysis is invalid.

Tuller's stacking analysis also follows from the compounding analysis. Thus, if the compounding analysis were correct, then stacking of a compound (i.e. Adj-linker-Noun compound) is extremely marginal. Here also we argue that the requirement that prenominal adjectives must not stack is not a direct consequence of the compounding analysis. Rather, it is because in Hausa, an adjective must always be followed by the noun it modifies and not by another adjective. Should an adjective be followed by another adjective as in (8A), the structure must be extremely marginal.

Yusuf gives the structure of the adjective^{phrase} as follows.

Notice that in Yusuf's analysis, the linker is considered the genitive K constituent. A string such as fárá ǝ́ moótàa 'white car' is considered an adjectival phrase (AP) in Yusuf's analysis and comprises a head adjective fárá 'white' and a KP complement ǝ́ moótàa 'of car'. ǝ́ is the head of the KP and moótàa 'car' its NP complement. The structure of the AP fárá ǝ́ moótàa is given as (86).

I would like to object to Yusuf's analysis presented above pointing out that r (or its n variant) is not a genitive constituent. r only resembles the real genitive marker in Hausa, having shared similar phonetic form (n or r) and

gender and number features. To distinguish the genitive marker from the linker, we point out that the Hausa genitive marker, in addition to its short forms n or r, has long forms na and ta which are not available to the linker in 'Adjective-linker-Noun' constructions as shown in the comparative examples (87) and (88). Notice that the ill-formedness of examples (88b and d) suggests that the linker cannot have longer forms na and ta.

(87)

(a) maálàmi ñ náháwù
 N GEN N
 teacher of syntax
 (syntax teacher)

(88)

(a) báki ñ zánèè
 Adj linker N
 black cloth
 (black cloth)

(b) maálàmífi ná náháwù
 N GEN N
 teacher of syntax
 (syntax teacher)

(b) * báki ná zánèè
 Adj ? N
 black cloth
 (black cloth)

(c) maálámá ř mákářántáá
 N GEN N
 teacher of school
 (school teacher)

(c) fára ř moótàa
 Adj linker N
 white car
 (white car)

(d)	maálàmaá	tá	mákáǎntaá	(d)	* fára	tá	moótàa
	N	GEN	N		Adj	?	N
	teacher	of	school		white		car

We assume that r in (86) above is a location marker, indicating prenominal occurrence of the adjective fára 'white'. Details of this proposal is given in the next section. Yusuf's attempt to extend an English/French analysis of Adj-N sequence to Hausa fails because in both English and French, an adjective takes a lexical projection, a prepositional phrase (PP) headed by 'of', as complement as shown in (89).

(89) (a) big [of a house] (English)
A PP

(b) un drole [de garçon] (French)
Det A PP
the big of boy

In the Hausa example (86), Adjective (A) takes a functional projection KP as complement. Notice that there is no instance in Hausa where adjective takes a PP complement. Yusuf points out that an important 'positive aspect' of his analysis of 'Adj-linker-Noun' sequence is that linker has been eliminated since in the first place it has no

categorical status in grammar. Linker has therefore been substituted with an independently motivated category K of case particles. We would like to observe that Yusuf's category K of case particles has not also captured the real issue at hand. In other words, it has not successfully replaced the traditional linker.

In actual fact, K is assigned a function in Yusuf's 'Adjective-K-NP' sequence which it does not perform. Notice that in these constructions such as (85) above, no case is assigned and therefore K cannot take an NP complement. We conclude that Yusuf's analysis has not captured the real relationship between the prenominal adjective and the element n/r. Yusuf's analysis only mentioned a PF enclitization of n/r to the prenominal adjective. We must point out that in Adjective-n/r-NP structure, n/r marks prenominal occurrence of the adjective. n/r agrees with the adjective in gender and number and by extension, agrees also with the head N in gender and number since the adjective and the head N also agree in gender and number. Yusuf's account of n/r as a genitive constituent in 'Adjective-n/r-NP' constructions led to a wrong assumption about the structure as an adjectival phrase (AP).

2.1.2.4 Alternative Account of prenominal adjectival modification: The NP Analysis

We have shown in the previous sections the inadequacy of both Tuller's compounding analysis and Yusuf's KP analysis of the prenominal adjectival modification in Hausa. We propose an alternative analysis in which the sequence adjectival-linker-noun is considered an NP, comprising an adjective, a marker which marks the adjective as prenominal and a head N. The prenominal marker also agrees in gender and number with the adjective it marks as prenominal. Furthermore, we assume a corresponding postnominal marking for a postnominal adjective. Attention is also drawn to similar 'location marking' associated with determiners in their association with head nouns. Our present proposal on location marking has not been contemplated in all previous works on NP structure in Hausa.

The present study assumes that in Hausa, a noun head can be optionally modified by an adjective prenominally and/or postnominally. To illustrate, consider the adjective stem gàjeér- 'short'. gàjeér- can be used to modify a noun N prenominally as shown in (90).

(90) gàjeér- N
 Adj
 stem

An idiosyncrasy of Hausa requires that the noun and its modifying adjective agree in gender and number, and in addition, the adjective modifier is also marked morphologically as prenominal modifier. The prenominal markers are n (for masculine singular and plural adjectives) and r (for feminine singular adjectives). The gender and number agreement is also marked morphologically and is lexically determined. In the case of the adjective stem gàjeér-, the suffix for gender and number agreement is e for masculine singular form of the adjective, a for feminine singular form of the adjective and u for plural form of the adjective. A generalization of the structure of a prenominal adjective stem such as gàjeér- is shown in (91).

(91) Prenominal adjective	Adjective stem	Gender and Number agreement suffix	Prenominal marker
gàjeérén 'short	gajeer-	-e (MS)	-n
gàjeéráǎ 'short	gajeer-	-a (FS)	-ǎ
gàjèerún 'short'	gajeer-	-u (PL)	-n

The adjective stem gàjeér-, as a prenominal adjective, will have the following full paradigm (92) indicating gender and number agreement (AGR) and prenominal occurrence (pren).

- (92) (a) gàjeéré ń yaáròò
 Adj AGR pren N
 (MS) (MS) (MS)
 short boy (short boy)
- (b) gàjeérá ǎ yaárinnyàà
 Adj AGR pren N
 (FS) (FS) (FS)
 short girl (short girl)
- (c) gàjèerú ń yáàraá
 Adj AGR pren N
 (PL) (PL) (PL)
 short children (short children)

The adjective stem saab- 'new' has the following full paradigm (93) showing gender and number agreement (AGR) and prenominal occurrence (pren).

(93) (a) saábó ń gídaá
 Adj AGR pren N
 (MS) (MS) (MS)
 new house (new house)

(b) sáábúwá ř moótàn
 Adj AGR pren N
 (FS) (FS) (FS)
 new car (new car)

(c) sàabàbbí ń kùjèeruú
 Adj AGR pren N
 (PL) (PL) (PL)
 new chairs (new chairs)

Notice that the examples in (92) and (93) are rendered ill-formed if the prenominal marking is not effected as shown in (94) and (95) respectively.

(94) (a) * gàjeéré - yaáròò
 Adj AGR pren N
 (MS) (MS)

(b)	*gàjeérá	-	yaárínyàa
	Adj AGR	pren	N
	(FS)		(FS)
(c)	*gàjèerú	-	yaaraá
	Adj AGR	pren	N
	(PL)		(PL)
(95) (a)	*saábé	-	gidaá
	Adj AGR	pren	N
	(MS)		(MS)
(b)	*saábúwá	-	moótàa
	Adj AGR	pren	N
	(FS)		(FS)
(c)	*sàabàabí	-	kùjèeruú
	Adj AGR	pren	N
	(PL)		(PL)

(94) and (95) are surface representations whose ill-formedness is attributed to the absence of the obligatory prenominal marker which allows proper pronunciation at this level of representation. The prenominal marker is a clitic which must be suffixed to the prenominal adjective at PF. The Hausa

adjective, when cited in isolation or in a d-structure representation, does not require location marking since the marker has no semantic content to cause any difference in meaning. In other words, the location of the adjective does not alter the meaning of the noun phrase. We assume the following d-structures (96a and b) for NPs containing prenominal and postnominal adjective respectively.

(96) (a)

(b)

(97) (a)

(b)

2.1.2.5 Postnominal Modification

In the present study we argue that an adjective is morphologically marked as postnominal after taking the necessary postnominal location suffix. The post modifying adjective must also agree with the noun it modifies in gender and number. To illustrate, consider again the adjective stem gajeer- 'short' occurring

postnominally as in (98).

(98) N gajeer-
 Adj

The gender and number agreement suffix for the adjective stem gajeer- is realized as e (for feminine singular form of the adjective) and u (for the plural form of the adjective). The postnominal suffix for each adjective form is represented by a copy of the vowel that serves as gender and number agreement suffix as shown in the following paradigm.

(99)

Postnominal adjective	Adjective stem	Gender and Number agree- ment suffix	Post- ²² nominal marker	Gloss
a. gàjeéreeé	gajeer-	e (MS)	e	'short'
b. gàjeéraá	gajeer-	a (FS)	a	'short'
c. gàjèeruú	gajeer-	u (PL)	u	'short'

Similarly, the adjective stem saab- 'new' exhibits the paradigm in (100) in respect of postnominal marking.

²² While the prenominal markers appear to be restricted to n/r irrespective of adjective type, the situation is not the same with postnominal markers. Notice that they are e, a, u here and o, a, i in (100). The postnominal marker as we have said above, is a copy of the vowel that serves as gender and number agreement suffix. Hausa employs quite a number of sets of gender and number agreement suffixes and the preference of one set over the other by an adjective is governed by factors which require independent stipulation outside the scope of the present study. Suffice it to say that the interest of the present study lies in the agreement suffix only after it might have been established.

(100)

Postnominal adjective	Adjective stem	Gender and Number agreement suffix ²³	Postnominal suffix	Gloss
a. saáboó	saab-	o (MS)	o	'new'
b. saábúwaá	saab-	uwa (FS)	a	'new'
c. saábàbbif	saab-	abbi (PL)	i	'new'

In postnominal modification, as in its prenominal counterpart, the postnominal suffix attaches to the adjective at PF. The NP yaárò gàjeéré 'short boy' will have the following d-structure and PF representations respectively.

(101) d-structure:

²³ In these complex gender-number suffixes we may suggest the following composition: o is a complex comprising both gender and number (masculine singular); uwa comprises uw feminine gender suffix and a number (singular) suffix abbi is only number (plural) suffix since gender is neutralized in the plural.

PF representation:

Notice that the postnominal adjectives in (99) and (100), when used in actual noun phrases without the postnominal marking, will render the NPs ill-formed as shown in (102).

- | | | | |
|-------------|------------|--------|-----|
| (102) (a) * | yaárò | gàjeér | é |
| | N | Adj | AGR |
| | MS | | MS |
| (b) * | yaárinnyàa | gàjeér | á |
| | N | Adj | AGR |
| | FS | | FS |
| (c) * | yâaraá | gàjèer | ú |
| | N | Adj | AGR |
| | PL | | PL |
| (d) * | gídaá | saáb | ó |
| | N | Adj | AGR |
| | MS | | MS |

(e) *	moótàa	saáb	úwá
	N	Adj	AGR
	FS		FS
(f) *	kùjèeruú	sàab	àbbí
	N	Adj	AGR
	PL		PL

Notice that the postnominal suffix also agrees with the postnominal adjective and by extension with the head noun in gender and number since it is a copy of the gender and number agreement suffix of the adjective. This observation accounts for the ill-formedness of (103).

(103) (a) *	yaáròo	gàjeér	á	á
	MS		FS	FS
(b) *	yaárinnyàa	gàjeér	é	é
	FS		MS	MS
(c) *	moótàa	saábó	ó	
	FS		MS	MS

2.1.3 On Double-determiner NP Constructions

A standard X-bar analysis of the nominal phrase as in the Barriers framework, assumes that the nominal phrase

comprises essentially a lexical noun head N (a zero level category) which projects maximally to N' and contains optional modifiers in the form of specifiers (determiners), adjuncts and complements as shown in (10A).

(10A)

Specifiers in Hausa are essentially the determiners mentioned in section 2.2.1.1 above. Erns (1991:191) points out that the general assumption in X-bar theory is that, assuming binary branching, there is only one SPEC position in a given maximal projection such as the N'' in (10A) above. An idiosyncrasy of Hausa is the existence of double determiners with a single noun head in an NP as shown in the following examples.²⁴

²⁴ Determiners in Hausa occur prenominally and/or postnominally. Two determiners may appear in a single NP, one in prenominal position and the other in postnominal position (wání yaárò ò) 'another boy' or all in postnominal position (yaárò ò cán 'that boy'. Perhaps the only restriction is that two determiners cannot occur prenominally as indicated by the ill-formedness of

*wání	wàné	yaárò
DET	DET	N
some	which	boy

- (105) (a) wání yaárò ò
 DET N DET
 some boy the (another boy)
- (b) wáccàn goóná ò̃
 DET N DET
 that farm the (that very farm)
- (c) wádànnè mútàané ò
 DET N DET
 which people the (which other people)

A fundamental question arises in the adoption of the universal NP structure (104) for Hausa: How does the X-bar theory, which provides for only one SPEC position (presumable for a single determiner), account for the double determiner situation in Hausa? A double-determiner NP construction in Hausa is one comprising a head N and two syntactically independent determiners. The determiners however denote some unified sense and which may be captured by a single determiner in other languages. Two determiners in Hausa, the demonstrative (DEM) and the previous reference marker (PRM), are especially involved in double determiner constructions.

2.1.3.1 Pre-theoretic description of double-determiner NP construction

A descriptive generalization in respect of the distribution of the two determiners within a given Hausa NP is that a demonstrative occurs (prenominally or postnominally) together with a postnominal PRM as shown in the following examples.

(106)	wánnà̀n	yaá̀rò	̀n
	DET	N	DET
	DEM		PRM
	this	boy	the (this particular boy)
(107) (a)	wáncà̀n	yaá̀rò	̀n
	DEM	N	PRM
	that	boy	the (that very boy)
(b)	wànná̀n	yaá̀rò	̀n
	DEM	N	PRM
	that- other	boy	the (that other boy)
(c)	yaá̀rò	̀n	ná̀n
	N	PRM	DEM
	boy	the	that- other (that other boy)

(108) wání yaárò ò
 DEM N PRM
 some boy the (another boy)

(109) wàné yaárò ò
 DEM N PRM
 which boy the (which other boy)

The claim that two determiners capture the semantic sense denoted by some single determiner or make special emphasis, follows from the fact that neither of the two determiners, alone, can aptly capture the sense denoted by their semantic alliance. Consider, for instance, (108) above. The two determiners wání 'some' and ò 'the' capture the sense denoted by the single determiner 'another'. Neither wání or ò can achieve this feat alone as shown in (110) and (111).

(110) wání yaárò 'some boy'

(111) yaárò ò 'the boy'

similarly, the determiners wàné 'which' and ò 'the' in (109) above capture the sense denoted by 'which other', an emphatic 'which': wàné yaárò ò 'which

other boy'. Here also, neither wàné 'which' nor n 'the', alone, can capture the sense denoted by the emphatic 'which other' as depicted by (112) and (113).

(112) wàné yaáròò 'which boy'

(113) yaárò n 'the boy'

Similar explanation goes for examples (106) and (107) above.

2.1.3.2 An X-bar structure for the Hausa double determiner constructions

Two standard X-bar approaches can be isolated in respect of the study of the structure of the nominal phrase. These are the standard NP analysis and the most recent DP Hypothesis. A standard NP analysis assumes an obligatory noun head for the nominal phrase and optional modifiers, one of which is the determiner. The DP hypothesis on the other hand, assumes that the string determiner plus noun (DET-N) is indeed a determiner phrase (DP) with the determiner heading the phrase.

2.1.3.3 The NP Analysis

We shall examine four approaches to the NP analysis of the double-determiner constructions in Hausa. These are the Ternary branching analysis, the three-bar maximal projection analysis, the recursive analysis and the broken determiner analysis.

2.1.3.4 Ternary branching analysis

An NP analysis of the Hausa nominal phrase as in Galadanci (1969, 1976) incorporates a ternary branching analysis. Thus, a double-determiner NP construction such as wání yaárò ò 'another boy' will be represented structurally as follows

The ternary branching analysis gives rise to a 'flat' structure which is incapable of distinguishing structurally the hierarchy of constituents in the NP structure. In addition, the analysis in (114) does not

capture the unified semantic sense associated with the two determiners in Hausa double-determiner NPs. As it were, (114) gives the impression that wání and ̀̀ are independent of each other.

2.1.3.5 Three-bar maximal projection analysis

In a two-bar maximal projection, a determiner expands an intermediate projection to a maximal projection. An additional determiner in a phrase as in the double-determiner Hausa NP will create yet a new higher projection, a treble bar projection, assuming that determiners essentially create maximal projections. This is shown in (115).

Assuming (115), the structure of the double determiner NP wání yaárò ̀̀ is (116).

(116)

Notice that the analysis in (116) does not allow for recursion which will obviate the need for the treble-bar projection. And like the previous ternary branching analysis, the treble-bar analysis does not capture the unified semantic sense associated with the two determiners in the Hausa double determiner NP.

2.1.3.6 Recursive analysis

Radford (1988: 255) gives a recursive analysis for maximal projections in which an adjunct recursively projects a two-bar level maximal projection as in (117)

(117)

The motivation for (117) derives from the assumption

that there is the possibility that there may be different types of adjuncts including double bar adjuncts which expand X'' into X''' . If we take into account the functional similarity between determiners and adjuncts - both are modifiers - we can extend the recursive analysis of double bar adjuncts to double bar determiners. We shall then assume a double bar determiner analysis in which of the two determiners in a single noun phrase, one determiner expands an intermediate projection into a maximal two-bar projection, and the other determiner recursively expands the two bar maximal projection into another two-bar maximal projection as shown in (118).

(118)

Assuming (118), the NP wání yaárò ò will now have the structure (119).

(118) preserves the two-bar level X-bar theory of the Barriers framework (Chomsky 1986). However, (118) does not capture the single SPEC requirement for maximal projections advocated in the Barriers X-bar theory. The recursive analysis for the Hausa double-determiner NP as in (119) presupposes that the two determiners wání and ò are independent of each other. The analysis therefore fails to capture the unified semantic sense associated with the determiners.

2.1.3.7 The broken determiner analysis

The present study proposes a broken determiner analysis for the double determiner NPs of Hausa. This analysis is aimed at capturing the fact that in all cases involving double determiners in a single Hausa

NP, the two determiners always represent a unitary sense which is otherwise not captured by either of the determiners. Since the two determiners represent a unified semantic sense, they should appear as a single unit at d-structure in a broken fashion (i.e. DET...DET) to occupy the only SPEC position available in the NP structure. Subsequently, a component of the single unit, the enclitic PRM, attaches to the head N at PF. By this proposal, an NP such as wání yaárò ò 'another boy', will have a d-structure (120) and a PF representation (121).

(120)

(121)

Similarly, an NP such as yaárò ò nán 'the other boy', will have (122) and (123) as d-structure and PF representation respectively.

(122)

(123)

²⁵ With respect to the positioning of SPEC, Hausa is both head-first (115 and 116) and head-last (114) since it allows both prenominal and postnominal occurrence of the determiner.

But notice that an NP such as yaárò ò nân 'this boy', comprising a head noun yaárò 'boy' an agreement marker ò and a determiner nân is not a double determiner NP construction and will therefore have the following d-structure (124) and PF representation (125) respectively.

(124)

(125)

Notice that the agreement marker ò is an enclitic which attaches to the head noun at PF. An obvious question is why is it that yaáro ò nân 'the other boy' is a double determiner NP and yaárò ò nân 'this boy' just a single determiner NP? The real distinction

between the two constructions lies in the two words nán and nán which, though both demonstratives and hence determiners, are semantically distinct words. nán denotes the ordinary demonstrative 'this' (plural nàn). nán occurs as a postnominal determiner and requires an enclitic ñ (for masculine singular nouns), ń (for plural nouns or ř (for feminine singular nouns) to mark gender and number agreement with the head N it modifies.

nán on the other hand denotes 'that' for both masculine and feminine singular nouns and for plural nouns and it means persons and things referred to. Since nán (demonstrative) and n (PRM) share the feature [+ definite] (each refers to a known entity), the two occur together to denote an emphatic definite reference. nán (DEM) and n (PRM) are both determiners and an NP construction containing them both must be a double determiner NP construction.

2.1.3.8 The NP Hypothesis

The other approach to the analysis of the nominal phrase, commonly referred to as DP Hypothesis (Abney

1987), assumes that the co-occurrence relation between determiner and noun is essentially a matter of determiner subcategorising for an obligatory NP complement. The DP hypothesis is based on the assumption that the determiner, as a functional category, projects maximally and heads its maximal projection. Thus, by DP hypothesis, a nominal phrase is actually a determiner phrase (DP), with a determiner (DET) as head of the determiner phrase (DP). DET also takes an NP complement as shown below.

(126)

There are arguments in the literature against the DP hypothesis and moreso why it cannot adequately handle double determiner nominal constructions. Ernst (1991) for instance, discusses two general arguments against the DP hypothesis. The first argument relates to the fact that the nominal constituent following DET and which serves as a complement of DET is not a maximal projection (i.e. not an NP) as claimed by the DP hypothesis. Ernst points out that there is a class of adverbs in English

(and perhaps generally) whose distribution is is such that they occur to the left-most position (i.e. initial position) of any phrasal constituent containing them. The adverbs are even, mostly, and only. Consider the following example from Ernst (1991:195).

(127) Vern likes [EVEN the flowers his mother planted]
NP

In (127), the nominal expression the flowers his mother planted is claimed to be an NP, comprising a DET the and an N' flowers his mother planted. The adverb even appears in the left-most position of the whole NP.

Now consider (128).

(128) *Vern likes [the [EVEN flowers his mother
DP NP
planted]]

In (128), the nominal expression the flowers his mother planted on a DP analysis, comprises a DET the and its NP complement flowers his mother planted. Ernst argues that if the adverb even occupies the left-most position of the NP complement, the resultant structure (128) is ill-formed, indicating that the string flowers his

mother planted cannot be a full N'' but an N'. The second argument against the DP hypothesis goes as follows. If DET were actually a functional head, projecting maximally to determiner phrase (DP), then we would expect a determiner movement to a higher head, parallel to the widely accepted raising of verb to AGR-O or tense (TNS) to AGR-S which I represent as (129) and (130) respectively.

However, there is no evidence for determiner movement and Ernst points out that many of the proposed determiner movements, as in French, are equally analysable as surface (PF) phenomena with no need to invoke any syntactic movement. In particular, the DP hypothesis is confronted with the problem of double headedness in respect of double determiner nominal constructions. Notice that in a DP analysis, determiner D is the head of the DP projection. Now the nature of the problem is such that with double determiner NP constructions, two heads (i.e. two determiners) will project to a single maximal projection DP. Why should two heads share one maximal projection? Notice that our previous analysis of double determiner NP constructions in Hausa presupposes a noun head for the double determiner NP. This being the case, only the head N will project maximally to NP. We postulated that the two determiners constitute a single discontinuous unit. It should be pointed out that the same problem of double headedness led to Pollock's (1989) proposal for a split INFL. Pollock asked why AGR and TENSE, each a head, should project to a single maximal projection INFL.

Another problem for the DP hypothesis in respect of cases such as the example below, is choosing the determiner head for a DP and the implication of such a choice.

(131) duah buah rumah itu
two CL house that (those two houses)

This example is from Lewis (1969) and illustrates the case of Malay nominal construction in which a prenominal classifier phrase (CL) coexists with a postnominal demonstrative itu. If this double determiner NP construction were to be subjected to a DP analysis, which of the two determiners - the prenominal classifier or the postnominal demonstrative - will be chosen as the determiner head of DP? We conclude that the DP hypothesis is incapable of handling the double-determiner NP construction of Hausa.

2.2 Summary

The chapter discusses the internal structure of the Hausa nominal phrase with a view to establishing an X-bar structure that captures the various agreement relations obtaining in the nominal phrase. The NP is

said to comprise an obligatory noun head and three types of optional modifiers, namely determiners, adjuncts and complements. Hausa data, as shown, provide evidence for X-bar distinction between adjuncts and complements. An indepth analysis of noun modification by adjective reveals that an adjective can modify a noun prenominally and/or postnominally, and also noun and adjective must agree in gender and number with the agreement being marked on the adjective. The chapter provides new insight into the traditional linker, an enclitic that occurs between a prenominal adjective and noun, and which encliticizes to the adjective. The traditional linker is now being considered a 'location marker', marking prenominal occurrence of the adjective. The chapter also proposes a similar postnominal marker, which marks the adjective as postnominal. The chapter also makes an indepth analysis of those NP constructions containing double determiners.

CHAPTER THREE

THE VERBAL COMPONENT AND THE CLAUSE STRUCTURE

3.0 Preliminaries

The chapter discusses the important issue of the structure of the verbal component which is a major component in the clause structure. The chapter also discusses the clause structure of Hausa with a view to establishing an articulated clause structure for the language. The inflection node (INFL) of Hausa is revisited because of its major significance in the clause structure. The Functional categories in the clause, especially their role in determining ultimate articulated clause structure is also discussed.

3.1 The Hausa Inflection Node (INFL) Revisited

The Universal inflection element (or INFL for short) is mentioned in Chomsky (1981:18) and comprises of agreement (AGR) and tense (TNS) elements. The Hausa INFL, like the universal INFL, contains two elements, agreement (AGR) and tense-aspect (TNS-ASP). The agreement element carries features similar to those that specify the subject NP. The

lexical head of the subject NP is specified for the features person, gender and number. The agreement element in INFL also bears same features (i.e. person, gender and number), hence the agreement relation between the subject NP and the agreement element in INFL. The tense element (TNS) alone tells whether or not the action denoted by the verb is a past action, present action or future action. Thus, the tense element captures the temporal aspects of the Hausa verb. But the action of the verb must also be specified as whether it is completive (perfective) or continuative (imperfective). This aspectual matter of the verb is captured by the element aspect. A careful study of the notions tense and aspect with reference to Hausa shows that one can suggest for the language a two-way opposition to tense: Future and Non-Future (132a) and another two-way opposition to aspect: Perfective and Imperfective (132b).

(132) (a)

(b)

Notice that the non-future tense (NF) is a cover term for present and past tenses. It should be pointed out that when the future tense (FUT) is used, the action denoted by the verb requires no aspectual specification. Thus, a zero aspect is presupposed for every future tense. But every aspect requires a temporal specification by a non-future (NF) tense. Thus, a perfective aspect is either a present action or a past action. Likewise an imperfective aspect is necessarily a present or a past action. Hence, the descriptions Non-future Perfective, (NF PERF) non-future Continuative (NF CONT) and non-future Habitual (NF HAB). We shall claim for a single tense-aspect element since every action denoted by the Hausa verb must be specified for temporal as well as aspectual features.

Tenses and aspects in Hausa are morphologically represented as shown in (133).

(133)

Tense/Aspect	Tense/Aspect Marker	Distribution
Future (FUT)	1- zaá	precedes subject agreement element (AGR-S)
	11- -à	follows subject agreement element (AGR-S)
Perfective (PERF)	1- á	follows subject agreement elements with the features [1/3 S], [2MS]
	11- ñ	follows subject agreement elements with the features [1/2/3 PL], [2FS].
	111- kà	used when there is an element in [SPEC, CP] and following a subject agreement element with the features [1/2/3 PL], [2FS].
	1v- ø (phonetically non-realized)	used when there is an element in [SPEC, CP] and following a subject agreement element with the features [1/2/3 [1/3 S], [2MS].
Imperfective Continuous (CONT)	1- nàa	follows subject agreement element
	11- kèe	used when there is an element in [SPEC, CP].
Habitual (HAB)	kàn	follows subject agreement element

We illustrate the tenses and aspects enumerated in (133)

as follows.

(13ⁿ)

(a) Audù zaá yà kaámà kifíí
 FUT AGR-S catch fish
 3MS

(Audu will catch a fish)

(b) Audù yá à kaámà kifíí
 AGR-S FUT catch fish
 3MS

(Audu will probably catch a fish)

(c) Audù yá á kaámà kifíí
 AGR-S NF catch fish
 3MS PERF

(Audu caught a fish)

(d) Mútàanéé sú ń kaámà kifíí
 people AGR-S NF catch fish
 3PL PERF

(People caught fish)

(e) [Kifííí]₁ (nèe) mútàanéé sú kà kaámà t₁
 FOC people AGRS- NF catch
 3PL PERF

((It is) fish (that) people caught)

(f) [Kɪfɪfɪ]₁ (nèè) kɪ kà kaámà t₁
 SPEC, FOC AGR-S NF catch
 CP 2FS PERF

((It is) fish (that) you caught)

(g) [Kɪfɪfɪ]₁ (nèè) Áudù yá ø kaámà t₁
 SPEC, FOC AGR-S NF catch
 CP PERF

((It is) fish (that) Audu caught)

(h) [Kɪfɪfɪ]₁ (nèè) ká ø kaámà t₁
 SPEC, FOC AGR-S NF catch
 CP 2MS PERF

((It is) fish (that) you caught)

(i) Áudù yá nàa kaámà kɪfɪfɪ
 AGR-S NF catch fish
 3MS CONT

(Audu is catching fish)

(j) [Áudù]; (néé) t₁ yá kèè kaámà kɪfɪfɪ
 SPEC, FOC AGR-S NF catch fish
 CP 3MS CONT

((It is) Audu (who) is catching fish)

(k) Áudù yá kàn kaámà kɪfɪfɪ
 AGR-S NF catch fish
 3MS HAB

(Audu does catch fish)

(1) (a) Audù yà ø kaámà kifif
 AGR-S SUB catch fish
 3MS

(Let Audu catch fish)

(b) Bintă tà ø dáfà àbinci
 AGR-S SUB cook food
 3FS

(Let Binta cook food)

(c) Dàalibái sù ø koómàa makáfántaá
 students AGR-S SUB return school
 3PL

(Let students return to school)

Hausa also has the subjunctive (imperative) mood but unlike tense and aspect, it is not phonetically realized. The subjunctive mood (SUB) is recognized by the presence of a low tone (˘) on the subject agreement element as shown in (13a1).

The agreement element (AGR) in the Hausa inflection node (INFL) is the subject agreement marker/element (AGR-S). It carries person, gender and number features and is overtly represented by markers as shown in the following table.

(135)

Subject agreement marker (AGR-S)	Features			Feature representation
	Person	Gender	Number	
ní	1st	masculine	singular	1MS
ní	1st	feminine	singular	1FS
nú	1st	-	plural	1PL
ká	2nd	masculine	singular	2MS
kí	2nd	feminine	singular	2FS
kú	2nd	-	plural	2PL
yá	3rd	masculine	singular	3MS
tá	3rd	feminine	singular	3FS
sú	3rd	-	plural	3PL

The various subject agreement markers (AGR-S) in Hausa are shown in the following examples.

(136)

(a) (Ní) ní kà̀n yí kà̀ràatuú
 I AGR-S NF do read
 1M/FS 1M/FS HAB

(I do read)

- (b) (Muú) mú nàa cín àbínčí
 We AGR-S NF eating food
 1PL 1PL CONT
 (We are eating food)
- (c) (Káí) ká kàn sàuràarí làabàaǎí
 You AGR-S NF listen news
 2MS 2MS HAB
 (You do listen to news)
- (d) (Keé) kí ñ káryà kújèeraá
 You AGR-S NF break chair
 2FS 2FS PERF
 (You broke a chair)
- (e) (Kuú) kù ø fitá wàjé
 You AGR-S SUB go out
 2PL 2PL
 (You go out!)
- (f) (Shíí) yá á kaámà kíííí
 He AGR-S NF catch fish
 3MS 3MS PERF
 (He caught a fish)

(g) (Itá) tá nàa wánkè kwaánoónif
 She AGR-S NF wash dishes
 3FS 3FS CONT

(She is washing dishes)

(h) (Sún) sú ñ tàfí mákářántaá
 They AGR-S NF go school
 3PL 3PL PERF

(They went to school)

It is evident from (135) and (136) that the INFL in Hausa is made up of an agreement marker and tense-aspect marker. Both the agreement marker and the tense-aspect marker are functional elements (in the sense of Abney 1987) as shown by the evidence in the next section. This being the case, we suggest, as in Yusuf (1991), a split-INFL for Hausa in line with Pollock's (1989) split-INFL analysis for the universal INFL (See chapter 1 section 1.3.3 .2 for an earlier discussion on split-INFL).

3.2 Functional (agreement) elements in clause structure of Hausa

So far we have identified AGR-S and Tense-Aspect as agreement elements in Hausa clause structure. We shall argue that the 'grade' element of the Hausa verb is also

an agreement element and furthermore, each of these agreement elements is a Functional category in the sense of Abney (1987). Abney distinguishes Functional elements or categories from thematic categories using the syntactic category feature [+F]. Functional categories are defined in chapter one section 1.3 as these elements that possess essential properties but the properties do not define the class of Functional elements. He points out further that Functional elements are closed lexical elements and are generally phonetically and morphologically dependent; generally unstressed; often enclitic and affixes and sometimes even phonologically null. According to Abney, other defining properties of Functional elements include the fact that Functional elements lack 'descriptive content' - i.e. do not have a referent in real world the way verbs and nouns do have.

3.2.1 Subject agreement element (AGR-S)

Subject agreement element or AGR-S in Hausa exhibits the defining properties of Functional elements such as being phonetically and morphologically dependent (it is a bound morpheme which must always align with Tense or Aspect marker) and checking the NP-features of the subject

NP. The ability of AGR-S to enter into agreement relation with the subject NP in [SPEC, AGR-S''] follows from the fact that it contains phi-features (i.e. the features person, gender and number) which it shares with the subject NP. In Hausa, AGR-S is represented by an overt marker which marks agreement relation with a preceding subject NP in [SPEC, AGR-S'']. The various realizations of AGR-S were shown in (136) above.

3.2.2 Tense-Aspect (TNS-ASP)

Tense-Aspect exhibits the defining properties of functional elements. Tense=aspect is phonetically and morphologically dependent. That is to say, tense or aspect is a bound morpheme which must be affixed to an AGR-S marker at PF. Tense-Aspect in Hausa is generally represented by an overt marker, though there are instances of non-overt realization (see 133 above), and relate to the subject NP and the verb. Tense-Aspect has the dual function of (i) combining with AGR-S to assign abstract Nominative Case to the subject NP under spec-head agreement, and (ii) spelling out the aspectual and temporal value of the action denoted by the

verb as shown in (137).

(137)	Áudù	yá	á	kaámà	kíffíí
	subject	AGR-S	NF	V	noun object
	NP		3MS PERF	catch	fish
		┌───┐			
		│			
		└───┘			
		┌───┐			
		│			
		└───┘			
	Nominative Case				

(Audu caught a fish)

In (137) above, AGR-S yá and the Non-future perfective aspect á assign Nominative Case to the subject NP Áudù. The non-future perfective aspect á, alone, spells out the temporal cum aspectual value of the verb as denoting a non-future (past) perfective action. TNS-ASP is always realized as an enclitic attached to AGR-S but may also assume zero realization (i.e. may be phonetically null). The non-future perfective aspect in Hausa is also realized as zero and occurs in clauses containing an element in [SPEC, CP]. This is illustrated in the following example.

(138)	[Áudù] _i	(neé)	[t _i]	yá	∅	kaámà	kíffíí
	SPEC	FOC	SPEC	AGR-S	NF	catch	fish
	CP	AGR-S''		3MS	PERF		

(Audu (it is) (that) caught a fish)

The non-future perfective aspect $\emptyset$ (phonetically realized as null) is contrasted with the phonetically realized non-future perfective $\acute{a}$ in (137). Notice that in (137), the subject NP is in [SPEC, AGR-S''] and not in [SPEC, CP].

The ability of TNS-ASP to enter into agreement relation with verb follows from the fact that it specifies the temporal cum aspectual properties of the verb. These properties are never manifested on the verb itself. Rather, they are inherently contained in, and represented by the TNS-ASP element. TNS-ASP belongs to the syntactic class defined by the feature [$\underline{+F}, \underline{+N}$]. Notice that it is the nominal trait of TNS-ASP which enables tense-aspect to combine with AGR-S to assign abstract nominative case to the subject NP under spec-head agreement relation. [cf Chomsky 1992:8-26].

3.2.3 The 'grade' element (or Object Agreement element (AGR-O)).

A standard analysis of the Hausa verb (cf Newman 1973) posits the verb as comprising two morphological components, viz the verbal base and the grade. The

structure of the verb is given as in (139).

(139)

Notice that from (139), it is clear that the standard analysis does not consider either verbal base or grade to be an independent head. However, in the light of recent insights into the nature and composition of categories as in Abney (1987), the verbal base and the grade are independent heads, each capable of projecting maximally to verbal base phrase (V'') and grade phrase (or AGR-O'') respectively. The verbal base determines the argument structure of the verb and the grade determines the nature of agreement relations in the verbal component. The verbal base carries inherent features in respect of transitivity or unaccusativity, thereby determining the structure of the VP. The verbal base kaam- 'catch' for example, is inherently transitive and will therefore require a following object. The verbal base therefore projects maximally to verbal phrase (V''). The grade exhibits the defining characteristics of Functional elements as

defined in Abney (1987:64-68) and enumerated in part in section 3.2 of the present chapter. In particular, it is phonetically realized as a bound morpheme, an affix that attaches to the verbal base. The grade also lacks a descriptive content - it refers to nothing in real world.

The grade marks agreement relations in the verbal component in a similar fashion with AGR-S. Following ideas in Chomsky (1991, 1992), the grade element may be referred to as AGR-O, an element that marks agreement relations in the verbal component. The main function of the grade (or AGR-O) is to enable the verbal base attain 'full verb' status, and this is achieved under agreement relation. There are seven morphologically defined groupings of grades, giving rise to what Parsons (1960, 1962) referred to as the seven verbal grades (see (13), chapter 1). Five grades (1,2,4,5,6) out of the seven contain four forms each. The remaining two grades (3 and 7) have single form each. Each grade form is an agreement element which enters into agreement relation with a verbal base to form 'full verb'. We shall claim that each grade form is an independent element that enters the lexicon with

unique verbal features or V-features. A verbal base contains morphological or lexical features (L-features) and selects a grade form whose V-features match the L-features of the verbal base.

Our analysis of the grade is essentially morphological, aimed at capturing the real function of the grade in its relation with the verbal base. Consider the four forms (A,B,C,D) of grade 1 as shown in (140). (See Table (214) for distinctive feature composition of each grade form)

(140)	-aa	A-form
	-aa	B-form
	-a	C-form
	-aa	D-form

Recall that in the introductory chapter, section 1.1.2.3, we discussed a defect of a phonological account as in Eulenberg (1972) and Halpern (1991) which assumes that the relationship between grade forms is captured either through a shortening rule or a lengthening rule. In the present study we propose a functional account of the relations between the grade forms, details of which are given in chapter 4. We consider each grade form as consisting of V-features.

Two grade forms may share V-features, but there is always a feature to distinguish them. Forms B and C of grade 1 for example, share the feature [+Transitive] but differ in the minute detail that qualifies the transitivity such as whether the object is a noun or a pronoun. A verbal base that requires a noun object will select the C-form of the grade, while B-form will be selected by a verbal base that requires a pronoun object. Still on grade 1, three forms of the grade, A-form, B-form and D-form, bear phonetic similarity: each is represented by -aa. The distinction between them is that B-form is selected by a verbal base that requires either a zero (phonetically null) object or a pronoun object. D-form is selected by a verbal base that requires an indirect object or dative phrase. A-form is used by intransitive verbal bases that operate grade 1.

The grade element (or AGR-0) belongs to the syntactic class defined by the features [+F, -N]. The verbal

properties enable the grade (or AGR-O) to form 'full verb' with a given verbal base.

3.3 Articulated Structure of the Hausa Verbal Component

Recall that in section 3.2.3 we have established that the verbal base and grade are functional heads, each capable of projecting maximally. Following ideas in Pollock (1989), we propose for Hausa a split verbal component similar to Pollock's split INFL. The split verbal component would comprise two independent elements, namely verbal base and grade, both heads. The projection of the verbal base V to verbal phrase V'' and grade to grade phrase (AGR-O'') is in accordance with the Extended Endocentricity Principle (Radford 1988:547), which is a rigid X-bar theoretic condition on single headedness. The grade element and its maximal projection, the grade phrase are claimed to be the equivalents of Chomsky's AGR-O and AGR-O'' respectively. This follows from the fact that the grade, like AGR-O, marks agreement in the verbal component. I would like to propose therefore, the

following structure for the Hausa verbal component.

(141)

The verbal component is essentially an agreement component with the agreement section of the component (i.e. AGR-O'') dominating the V'' section. The motivation for the structure (141) above follows from the requirement of the Minimalist theory (Chomsky 1992) that the verb (here verbal base) has to be subjected to a checking of its morphological and other properties by a functional element that carries these properties. The checking procedure involves movement of the verb to the checking element. The checking element here is AGR-O, and verb V has to raise to it for the purpose of this checking. Notice that this requirement has independent motivation in

Hausa whose verb comprise a verbal base and grade (or AGR-O) and whose association is purely based on agreement involving sharing of features. The verbal base selects a grade form that carries similar V-features with it. Now, with V incorporated into AGR-O, a full verb, V + AGR-O, is formed. Meanwhile, Case is assigned only under spec-head agreement relation. Thus, the object NP (N'') must raise to [SPEC, AGR-O''] in order to receive Accusative Case from the complex head [V AGR-O] or the full verb. The movement of V to ^{AGR-O} AGR-O and that of object NP to [SPEC, AGR-O''] are illustrated in (142)

The Accusative Case assignment is illustrated in (143).

(143)

The formation of full verb and object movement to [SPEC, AGR-O''] for Accusative Case assignment are illustrated by the transitive verb kaámà 'catch' and its object kiffif 'fish'. The full verb kaámà comprises a verbal base kaam- and AGR-O (grade) -a. The formation of the full verb involves the incorporation of kaam- into AGR-O as shown in (144).

(144)

The object kifif moves to [SPEC, AGR-O'''] to receive Accusative Case under spec-head agreement as shown in (145).

(145)

Further issues on the incorporation of verbal base into $AGR-O$ (V-raising) and object movement to [$SPEC$, $AGR-O''$] for accusative Case assignment are discussed in chapter four.

3.4 Towards an articulated clause structure of Hausa

In section 1.3.3.2 of chapter one, we discussed the articulated structure of the universal clause. Pollock's (1989) original idea of split-infl necessitated a revisitation of the clause structure, leading to a new formulation. Chomsky's (1991) modification to Pollock's ideas and subsequent

refinements (Chomsky 1992) resulted in what is now considered the universal articulated clause structure, illustrated as (45) in chapter one and repeated here as (146) for convenience.

Our aim in this section is to adopt (146) for Hausa, taking into account the idiosyncracies of the language.

3.4.1 Existing Accounts of Hausa Clause Structure

The structure of the simple clause in Hausa within the transformational generative framework is given either as (147a) - a pre-GB model as in Galadanci (1976:80), or (147b) - a GB model as in Tuller (1986:47).

(VC = Verbal complex, PP= preverbal pronoun;
TM = tense marker)

(147a) is inadequate for a number of reasons.

Consider first the following example from Galadanci (1976:80).

'Alí yá kàn cí kiífif'
(Ali often eats fish)

The claim that the VP contains a node called verbal complex (VC) which contains PP, TM and V is quite inappropriate. The subject agreement element or PP in Galadanci's analysis, cannot be a constituent of the VP. The element preverbal pronoun (PP) is not a pronoun as claimed by Galadanci but rather an agreement element which shares person, number and gender features with the subject NP. Notice also that PP cannot be a resumptive pronoun that functions as an agreement marker. The tense marker (TM), even though it specifies

the time of action denoted by the verb, cannot be a constituent of VP. PP (or subject agreement element) and Tense (TNS-ASP) are independent elements which cannot be subsumed under VP. In chapter four we shall show that the feature composition of subject agreement element and TNS-ASP exclude them from being constituents of VP. The ternary branching analysis of the verbal complex (VC) as shown in (147a) is also untenable in modern X-bar analysis of phrase structures especially in the Barriers framework (Chomsky 1986).

Clause structure (147b) is also inadequate considering the fact that it has been superceded by most recent insights into clause structure as in Pollock (1989) in which a split-infl is assumed. Thus, IP is no longer a node in the universal clause structure.

Yusuf (1991:110) extends Pollock's (1989) idea of split-infl to Hausa and argues for an articulated clause structure for Hausa, partially represented in (149).

(149)

In (149), the split-infl analysis is well motivated considering our previous arguments in sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 on the independence of the subject agreement element (AGR-S) and Tense-Aspect in Hausa. However, a major oversight of Yusuf's articulated clause structure for Hausa is its inability to provide a more articulated structure for the verbal component of the clause. Considering our previous position on verbal base and grade (section 3.2.3), the verbal component of the Hausa clause structure cannot be just the VP as in Yusuf's structure (149) above. Following Chomsky (1991, 1992), we claim that the Hausa verbal component is indeed an agreement phrase, a grade phrase (or 'AGR-O'), headed by 'grade', the agreement head in the verbal component. The Hausa verbal component had

been discussed in the previous section (3.3).

3.4.2 A more articulated clause structure of Hausa

A more articulated clause structure for Hausa, incorporating the proposed articulated verbal component (141), is as in (150).

(150)

We claim that the articulated clause structure (150) will account for simple sentences of Hausa such as Audù yá nàa rúbùutà wásifkàa 'Audu is writing a

letter' and Áudù záa yà sàyí ràakúmaá 'Audu will buy a she-camel', graphically represented as (151a) and (151b) respectively.

(151) (a)

Notice that (151 a and b) are d-structures of the respective sentences they represent. V-raising is required in the formation of the full verb in both (151a) and (151b). TNS-ASP must also raise to AGR-S (T-raising) and in the case of (151b), záa must

attach to the left of AGR-S (left adjunction). Details of these issues are discussed in chapter four.

Now consider the following sentence

(152) Áudù yá á tábà kaámà zaákii
 AGR-S NF once catch lion
 3MS PERF did

(Audu once caught a lion)

(152) contains two verbs, tábà 'once did' and kaámà 'catch'. Recall that 'tábà' had been established as a verb in section 1.1.1. of chapter one. Of the two verbs, kaámà takes záakii as an object and assigns Accusative Case to it. tábà performs an adverbial function of modifying the action denoted by kaámà. How is tábà to be accommodated in the proposed articulated clause structure (150)? Before suggesting any concrete proposal in answer to this question, we should recall that in chapter one, we have established that tábà belongs to a closed class of verbs (traditionally referred to as 'auxiliary verbs') which are capable of co-occurring with other verbs. Following ideas in Bamgboṣe (1974:36-41), we shall claim for Hausa a kind of restricted verb serialization involving verbs belonging to this class. We claim further (still following Bamgboṣe) that the restricted serial verb

construction found in Hausa is the 'modifying' type in which the verbs in the closed class modify other verbs. To distinguish the two verbs in the restricted modifying serial verb construction of Hausa, we propose the use of the feature [+MOD] (i.e. plus modification) for the modifying verb in a similar fashion Bamgbose (1974:36) used the feature for Yoruba. Thus, the modifying verb táà in (152) should bear the feature [+MOD].

With regard to structural representation, we propose that táà occupies [SPEC, V''], the specifier position of V'' at d-structure as shown in the following structural representation of the verbal component of (152).

(153)

At PF, the verbal base kaam-_i had incorporated into AGR-O, forming the full verb kaámà. Since tábà actually modifies the full verb kaámà, we claim that it should occupy [SPEC, AGR-O''] to reflect the modification at this level of representation. Notice that tábà can occupy [SPEC, AGR-O''] since at PF, the position is vacant. A PF representation of (153) is (154).

3.5 Summary

Attempt was made in this chapter to evolve an articulated clause structure for Hausa. The chapter revisited the inflection node (INFL), and following

ideas in Pollock (1989), proposed a split-infl. The chapter also made a survey of agreement elements in the clause structure of Hausa, arguing that the 'grade' element of the Hausa verb must also be considered an agreement element, the equivalent of Chomsky's (1991, 1992) AGR-O. A critical review was also made of previous attempts at setting up clause structure for Hausa. Furthermore, we attempted an articulated structure for the verbal component as a necessary prelude to the ultimate proposed articulated clause structure. Finally, we presented our proposal of a more articulated clause structure of Hausa which we assume is capable of accounting for simple declarative sentences of Hausa.

CHAPTER FOUR

AGREEMENT RELATIONS IN THE ARTICULATED CLAUSE STRUCTURE OF HAUSA

4.0 Preliminaries

In the previous chapter, we proposed an articulated clause structure for Hausa which was fashioned out of Chomsky's articulated universal clause structure. We also discussed some relevant functional categories that play crucial roles in establishing canonical clause structure. In this chapter, we intend to establish the nature of agreement relations holding between functional categories and other elements in an articulated clause structure of Hausa.

4.1 Towards defining agreement in syntax

Essentially, two elements stand in an agreement relation if they share common features. A standard agreement pattern is the specifier-head agreement relation in which head and specifier share the features person, number and gender or the phi-features. Consider Chomsky's (1991) partial universal articulated clause structure in (155).

An element in [SPEC, AGR-S''] and the one occupying AGR-S position stand in SPEC-head agreement relation. So also the element in [SPEC, AGR-O''] and the one occupying the AGR-O position. In standard Government-Binding framework, it is assumed that the head of CP (=C) agrees with the head (and perhaps the specifier) of its AGR-S'' complement.

Another standard agreement pattern is the subject-verb agreement relation as in English. Here also phi-features are shared.

Relations are unified to characterize pairs of agreeing constituents. Haegeman (1992:121) points out that a geometrical relation between agreeing pairs of

elements is such that one agreeing element is always higher in the tree than the element it agrees with. That is to say, agreeing constituents stand in c-command relation. Riemsdijk and Williams (1986: 274) discuss subject agreement within classical Government-Binding framework pointing out that "agreement relationship between the agreement node AGR and the subject can be expressed by coindexing:

$$[\text{S } \text{NP}_i [\text{INFL } [+TNS] \text{AGR}_i] \text{VP }] \text{S}$$

Riemsdijk and Williams argue that agreement has basically nominal characteristics since it carries typically nominal features and can be coindexed with NPs. AGR_i , when present, is considered the most prominent part of the 'discontinuous subject', consisting of NP_i and AGR_i . (NP_i is the most prominent part when AGR_i is absent). The subject of the clause is therefore $[\text{AGR}_i \text{S}]$ if there is one, otherwise $[\text{NP}_i \text{S}]$ or $[\text{NP}_i \text{NP}]$. Chomsky (1981:209-216) also discusses 'subject' in a similar fashion. In the Minimalist framework (Chomsky 1991, 1992), the concept of agreement receives a new boost with the proposal that there could

be object agreement in addition to the well known subject agreement. Chomsky (1991:17) points out that 'agreement with an NP is always the reflection of a government relation between the head AGR and the NP, either the SPEC-head relation or the relation of the head to an adjoined element'. Chomsky argues further that 'structural Case is correlated with agreement and reflects a government relation between NP and the appropriate AGR element.' The proposal for subject and object agreement is stated in Chomsky (1991:17) as follows:

- (156) Subject-verb agreement is associated with Nominative Case and is determined by the relation of the specifier to the AGR-S, head of AGR-S'', while verb-object agreement is associated with Accusative Case, and is determined by the relation of the NP to that of AGR-O head of AGR-O'' either in specifier or adjoined to AGR-O.

Agreement relation in the clause is spec-head relation involving sharing of features, especially the phi features. Agreement relation may also be chain-link

or co-indexing relation involving index sharing. This agreement relation is marked temporally in Hausa via a process called Relative Aspect Marking (RAM) (Tuller 1986). In Universal Grammar, Chomsky (1992) points out that CHAIN-link relation is achieved under 'government', an X-bar theoretic concept which defines geometrical relation between agreeing pairs. Complementation is also an aspect of agreement relation. The relationship between a transitive verb and its direct object is one of complementation. Complementation involves sharing of features. In Government-Binding framework, complementation relation is expressed in terms of sisterhood relation in the sense of X-bar theory and it is achieved under government, a geometrical relation between agreeing pairs. In Hausa, complementation relation is marked morphologically by 'grade'. The Hausa verb relates to a following syntactic environment via the form of its grade as outlined in 1.1.1.4. Complementation relation or object agreement relation in Hausa represents a complex morpho-syntactic agreement relation network involving 'unusual' agreement relations in the

verbal component. The nature of agreement relations in the Hausa verbal component appears 'unusual' because the verb inherently stands in agreement relation with all those elements cited in footnote four i.e. noun object, pronoun object, trace, dative phrase and zero object. Notice that the agreement relation (i.e. complementation relation) in the verbal component would have been 'normal' if the verb only agrees with a following object noun complement. In Hausa NPs, specifically the N + N constructions, complementation relation is morphologically marked by a genitive marker.

Chomsky's subject and object agreement may be spelt out variously in languages. Subject agreement and object agreement may be realized overtly or covertly as a parameter. Overt realization of agreement may be in the form of a morphological marking, with a marker which contains relevant agreement features. In Hausa, both subject agreement and object agreement are represented by a morphological marking involving functional agreement elements. It should be pointed out that in morphologically rich agreement languages such as Hausa, in which elements or constituents in the clause stand in agreement

relation with one another, surface inspection alone suffices to indicate agreement pattern. In the language for example, overt agreement marking allows for the determination of whether or not subject agreement or object agreement is properly represented. A major function of agreement relation as discussed in the Minimalist theory (Chomsky 1992) is to allow a statement to be made on convergence or Full Interpretation (FI) of a linguistic expression.

4.2 Functional categories and the nature of agreement relations

4.2.1 Subject NP in [SPEC,AGR-S']

Standard assumptions in the literature on transformational generative grammar as discussed in Chomsky (1991, 1992) regard a subject NP in the specifier position of AGR-S' as being either base-generated or raised to that position from the specifier position of the VP (if VP-internal subject hypothesis (Larson (1988)) is assumed) as represented in (157).

(157) (a)

(b)

(raised subject NP from [SPEC, V''], assuming VP-internal subject hypothesis)

AGR-S, the head of AGR-S'', is a functional element and contains the NP-features of the subject NP. Meanwhile, the subject NP has morphological NP-features which must be checked by AGR-S. The appropriate position for checking the NP features of the subject NP is the specifier position of AGR-S'' which is the checking domain of the functional head AGR-S. This structural

position allows the realization of an agreement relation known as spec-head relation between the NP in SPEC and the head AGR-S. Chomsky (1986b:24) observes that "spec-head agreement is a form of 'feature sharing' similar to θ government in fact sharing of the features person, number, Case, etc (the $\emptyset$ -features of Chomsky 1981 and other work) when AGR is present and sharing of an abstract $\emptyset$ -feature F when AGR is missing." Notice that in the case of Hausa, as shown in (158) below and further discussed in 4.4.2., the subject NP and AGR-S share the features person, number and gender, thereby satisfying the crucial requirement of spec-head agreement.

The morphological properties of the subject NP that are checked by the NP-features of AGR-S are the phi features person, gender and number. The checking process involves essentially sharing of phi features between the subject NP and the functional head AGR-S under a structural configuration which allows c-command relation between NP position and AGR-S position.

The nature of the agreement relation between the subject NP and AGR-S in Hausa is such that there are

different forms of AGR-S, each agreeing with a particular subject NP type. That is to say each form of AGR-S is a bundle of NP features and matches only a subject NP with matching morphological properties. Agreement is established through a correct matching of morphological features. Table (158) below shows co-occurring pairs of subject NP-AGR-S matching. Notice in particular the matching shared features.

(158)	<u>Subject NP type</u>	<u>Form of AGR-S</u>
	Áudù [3MS]	yá [3MS]
	Ládi [3FS]	tá [3FS]
	Mútàné [3PL]	sú [3PL]
	nií [IMS/FS]	ní [IMS/FS]
	muú [IPL]	mú [IPL]
	kaí [2MS]	ká [2MS]
	keé [2FS]	kí [2FS]
	kuú [2PL]	kú [2PL]
	shíí [3MS]	yá [3MS]
	ítá [3FS]	tá [3MS]
	suú [3PL]	sú [3PL]

Yaáròo	fá <u>ríf</u>		yá
N	A		
3MS	3MS	post	3MS
	3MS		

Yaárínyàa	fá <u>raá</u>		tá
N	N	post	
3FS	3FS	3FS	3FS

káramá	ṛ	yaárínyàa		tá
A	pren	N		
3FS	3FS	3FS		3FS

wádánsú	mútàaneé	doógàayeé	sú
DET	N	A	
3PL	3PL	3PL	3PL

We consider in (159) the actual matching relationship between subject NP and AGR-S (shown in (158) in concrete sentences.

(159)

(a)	[Aúdù]	[yá]	á	kaámà	zaákii	
	N		NF			
	NP	AGR-S	PERF	V	NP	
	3MS	3MS		catch	lion	(Audu caught a lion)

- (b) [Laádi] [tá] á káryà koófàa
 N NF
 NP AGR-S PERF V NP
 3FS 3FS break door (Laadi broke a door)
- (c) [Mútàaneé] [sú] nàa taáwaáyèe
 N NF
 NP AGR-S CONT strike
 3PL 3PL (People are striking)
- (d) [Káí] [ká] á íí Aúdu
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S PERF V NP
 2MS 2MS surpass (You surpass Audu)
- (e) [Keé] [kí] nàa ízà wútaá
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S CONT fan fire
 2FS 2FS (You are fanning the fire, i.e., you are worsening issues)
- (f) [Ní] [ní] kàn rúfè gídaá
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S HAB close house
 IMS/FS IMS/
 FS (I do close the house)

(g) [Muú] [mú] ñ gámà áikii
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S PERF finish work
 IPL IPL

(We finished the work)

(h) [Kuú] [kú] ñ gámà áikii
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S PERF finish work
 2PL 2PL

(You have finished the job)

(i) [Shif] [yá] kàn kárántà làabàáruú
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S HAB read news
 3MS 3MS
 (He does read the news)

(j) [ítá] [tá] á sàamú kúdií
 NP NF
 Pron AGR-S PERF get money
 3FS 3FS

(She got money)

(k) [Suú] [sú] nàa bárcif
 NP NF-
 Pron AGR-S CONT sleep
 3PL 3PL

(They are sleeping)

4.2.2 T-raising in Hausa

The subject NP needs Case. Structural Case assignment takes place under spec-head agreement. AGR-S alone (i.e. not in conjunction with TNS/ASP element) is incapable of assigning an abstract Nominative Case to the subject NP. It is suggested in the Minimalist theory that Tense assigns the abstract Nominative Case. But Tense does not enter into spec-head relation with the subject NP. Tense therefore has to raise to AGR-S to form a new complex head [$\begin{matrix} \text{AGR-S} \\ \text{Tense AGR-S} \end{matrix}$] as shown in (160)

This complex head carries associated Case and agreement features. The complex head assigns abstract Nominative features.

Case to the subject NP by virtue of spec-head agreement. Notice that (160) claims a left adjunction of TNS-ASP to AGR-S as shown in (161).

Hausa however differs from the standard position presented above in respect of TNS-ASP adjunction to AGR-S. In the language, TNS-ASP raises to AGR-S but attaches to its right as shown in (162).

Consider the following example showing TNS-ASP raising to the right of AGR-S.

(163)

(a)

(b) Yaáròo kyàkkyáwaá yá nàa kárántà járiídàa
 N Adj AGR-S NF read newspaper
 boy handsome 3MS CONT

(A handsome boy is reading a newspaper)

The non-future continuous aspect marker nàa in (163a) adjoins to the right of AGR-S yá forming the complex AGR-S yá nàa. It is this complex AGR-S that assigns Nominative Case to the subject NP. A leftward attachment of TNS-ASP to AGR-S as in (161) will not yield a proper PF representation which captures the actual

positioning of AGR-S and TNS-ASP relative to one another in the clause structure of Hausa. We illustrate this claim in the following example.

(164)

(a)

(b) *Yaarò kyàkyaáwaá nàa yá kàràntà jàriidàa

In (164a), the non-future continuous aspect marker nàa adjoins to the left of AGR-S yá forming the complex AGR-S nàa yá. nàa yá violates the actual Hausa positioning of AGR-S and TNS-ASP relative to one another, hence the ill-formedness of (164b).

It has also been suggested in the minimalist theory

that in languages like English, AGR may disappear after completing its function. Perhaps this is possible because in English, AGR is abstract.

But in Hausa, AGR is represented by an overt element and it does not delete.²⁶ AGR in the language, therefore survives every generation and derivation of linguistic expressions.

4.2.3 Object NP in [SPEC, AGR-O']

The object NP, like the subject NP, contains L-features which must be checked by a Functional element with NP-features. The checking element is AGR-O, the head of AGR-O', an agreement phrase. The checking domain of AGR-O is the specifier position of AGR-O'. The standard assumption in the Minimalist theory (Chomsky (1991, 1992) is that object NP raises to the specifier position of AGR-O' for the checking of its morphological properties by AGR-O as shown in (165)

26 But see section 4.5 on null complements of Hausa and the issue of AGR-drop.

The structure (166) shows overt raising of the object NP zaákii 'lion' to SPEC, AGR-O'' for the purpose of Accusative Case assignment.

Structure (166) is ill-formed as a PF representation because it contains overt object NP zaákii 'lion' in [SPEC, AGR-O''] position. It is however a well-formed s-structure after V-raising²⁷ to AGR-O had taken place, yielding a complex AGR-O or full verb. The nature of agreement relation between object NP in [SPEC, AGR-O''] and AGR-O is such that they stand in spec-head agreement relation. An NP in [SPEC, AGR-O''] receives Accusative Case under spec-head agreement relation. Notice that here also, AGR-O alone cannot assign Accusative Case to the object NP in [SPEC, AGR-O'']. For Accusative Case to be assigned to the object NP in [SPEC, AGR-O''], verbal stem V has to raise to AGR-O to form a complex head [V AGR-O]
AGR-O
as shown in (167).

27 See section 4.2.4 for the motivation of V-raising which will yield the full verb káshè 'kill'.

4.2.4 V-raising in Hausa

Consider the following full verbs, each of which comprises a verbal base and grade:

(168)	<u>Full verb</u>	<u>Gloss</u>	<u>Verbal base</u>	<u>Grade</u>
	kaámà	'catch'	kaam-	-a
	zàabí	'choose'	zaab-	-i
	koóroó	'drive towards oneself'	koor-	-oo
	dàfú	'well cooked'	daf-	-u
	káshè	'kill'	kash-	-e

The examples in (168) show that the Hausa verb is bi-

morphemic comprising a sequence of a lexical head (lexical V-stem) and a functional head (functional grade or AGR-O). The verb is indeed a complex whose formation involves the lexical V-stem being syntactically adjoined to the functional head as shown in (167) above. The relationship between the lexical head V-stem and the functional head 'grade' or AGR-O is captured via a syntactic movement which we shall refer to as V-raising. Thus, the actual motivation for V-raising in Hausa is to form full verb which is capable of assigning Accusative Case under spec-head agreement relation. We may wish to ask why V-raising is possible in Hausa. A Minimalist's explanation for V-raising in Hausa will attribute it to the requirement that the L-features of the verbal base must be checked by a functional element that carries the V-features of the verbal base and this checking must be conducted under an appropriate structural configuration. Recall that both verbal base and AGR-O are heads but none of them, alone, can assign Accusative Case to the object NP. The verbal base and AGR-O stand in a head-head agreement relation that yields a full verb. The verbal base -

AGR-O relation is an agreement relation since it involves feature specification, with AGR-O specifying the L-features of the verbal base under head-head agreement. When the verbal base incorporates into AGR-O, a complex head or full verb is produced.

(169) [AGR-O V AGR-O]
 AGR-O

We may wish to ask at this point whether AGR-O lowering as in (170) is also permissible as an alternative way of forming the Hausa full verb.

AGR-O lowering might not be possible for the following reasons. First, in the Minimalist framework,

checking theory essentially involves the checking of lexical features of a given lexical element by a functional element that carries similar features. It involves the movement of a lexical element whose features are to be checked to the functional element that checks the features. It turns out here that AGR-0 is the functional element that checks the lexical features of the verbal base V and cannot therefore lower to V.

Secondly, reversing the order of movement as in (170) leads to an ECP violation. Notice that head movement is highly local and the trace of a moved head must therefore be properly governed via antecedent government (cf Chomsky 1986b: 68-69). Antecedent government of t by AGR-0 under m-command relationship fails because the maximal projection V'' that dominates AGR-0 after it has been lowered to V does not dominate its trace t. It has been pointed out in the Minimalist theory that when V-features of AGR-0 have completed their work (i.e. checking the adjoined V-stem), they disappear. This is perhaps true of English where V-features are absolutely abstract. Consider the following

example showing V-movement in the verbal component of English.

The assumption here is that the verb kill can only assign Accusative Case to the object NP the dog under spec-head agreement. The movement of V to incorporate into AGR-O, yielding the complex [kill AGR-O],
AGR-O
is necessary since it involves checking the L-features of kill by a checking functional element AGR-O. AGR-O here is absolutely an abstract element with no overt morphological realization. The movement of the dog to [SPEC, AGR-O''] is covert but essential in order to

satisfy the requirement of Accusative Case assignment under spec-head agreement. Thus, a surface representation of (171) will depict a structure (172) in which the object NP follows the verb and the verb bears no trace of AGR-O.

(172) [kill the dog]
 V NP

In Hausa, V-features are represented by an overt element, the AGR-O (or grade), and do not disappear. Consider the following example showing V-movement in the verbal component of Hausa.

The first assumption is that the verbal ^{stem} kash- 'kill'

must raise, incorporating into AGR-O in order to have its lexical features checked. The checking element, the AGR-O, is the overt element -e. The incorporation of verbal base into AGR-O yields the complex AGR-O káshé (i.e. [^{AGR-O} kash e]) or full verb. This is illustrated as follows.

kash- raising

The second assumption is that the object NP kàréé 'dog' raises to [SPEC, AGR-O''] at s-structure in order to receive Accusative Case under spec-head agreement relation as shown in (175).

Movement of N'' (kàreé) at s-structure

Thus, a surface representation of (173) will depict a structure (176) in which object NP follows the verb and the verb comprises a verbal stem and AGR-O.

- (176) [kásh è kàreé]
 V-st. AGR- N''
 em O

Generally, subject NP and V-stem in Hausa are attracted by strong checking features, necessitating overt raising. The checking features are the NP features

of AGR-S for subject NP and the V-features of AGR-O for V-stem. The complex [$\begin{matrix} \text{AGR-O} \\ \text{V} \\ \text{AGR-O} \end{matrix}$] stands in spec-head relation with an element in the specifier position of AGR-O''. It assigns Accusative Case to the object NP. However, it does not engage the object NP in further agreement relations. That is to say, unlike AGR-S which carries NP features of the subject NP, thereby motivating overt raising of subject NP at PF, neither the verbal base nor AGR-O contains the NP features of the object NP to motivate overt raising of object NP at PF. Notice that the inability of both the verbal base and AGR-O to motivate overt raising of object NP at PF follows from the fact that they are essentially verbal and carry no nominal features.

4.3 The Agreement Relations

4.3.1 Verbal base-Grade (or AGR-O) relation

The Hausa verb is said to be bi-morphemic because it comprises two morphological units - the verbal base and the grade. Each is a head of a maximal projection. The formation of full verb in Hausa involves a union of the verbal base and the grade as discussed in the previous section.²⁸ The union of verbal base and the grade is not random. Verbal bases are not 'free-floating', capable of picking any grade to form full verbs. Traditional accounts of verbal base-grade relation as in Newman (1973) and Eulenberg (1972) made an important observation that the union of verbal base and grade must be rule-governed but did not show how. The present study intends to offer an explanation which captures the relationship between verbal base and grade. Verbal base-grade relation is an agreement

²⁸ See chapter one (1.1.1.3) for a similar discussion on adjective which is said to comprise of bundle of agreement features and chapter two on adjectival modification of nouns which is also said to be agreement-governed.

relation involving sharing of common features as pointed out in section 4.2.3. When the verbal base incorporates into the grade or AGR-O, it does so to satisfy an agreement that holds between them.

An interpretation of the agreement relation between verbal base and AGR-O within the Minimalist framework will be that the verbal base has morphological and other properties which must be checked. The checking is conducted under a structural relation by a functional element that shares morphological properties with the verbal base. The grade or AGR-O is the suitable candidate in this respect. It stands in a head-head agreement relation with the verbal base and shares morphological features with it. One of the morphological properties of the verbal base is 'transitivity'. A verbal base may be transitive or intransitive. Transitivity, as opposed to intransitivity, will be defined as transitivity to either a noun object or a pronoun object or their null realizations (traces and zero objects). Thus, the object is phonetically realized as noun or pronoun. The transitive verbal base uses other grade forms when the object is

phonetically non-realized as it is the case with a trace of a direct noun object and zero object. A transitive verbal base therefore has a few transitive grade forms at its disposal (for detailed representation of the grade forms see (13) chapter one). For instance, in the case of grades 2 and 5 which are transitive grades, a transitive verbal base operating either grade 2 or 5 will utilize grade forms 2A and 5A with a following trace or zero object; 2B and 5B with a following pronoun object, and 2C and 5C with a following noun object. This is illustrated in the following examples.

(177)

(A) Grades 2A, 2B and 2C

i)	Áudù	yá	á	dòokí	kàréé
		3MS	NF	2C	noun object
			PERF	hit	dog

(Audu hit a dog)

ii)	Áudù	yá	á	dòokeé	shí
		3MS	NF	2B	pronoun object
			PERF	hit	it

(Audu hit it)

iii) Áudù yá á dòokaá e
 3MS NF 2A zero object
 PERF hit something
 (Audu hit (something))

iv) Kàréé_i (nèe) Áudù yá ó dòokaá t_i
 dog FOC 3MS NF 2A trace
 PERF hit
 ((It is) dog (that) Audu hit)

(B) Grades 5A, 5B and 5C

i) Áudù yá á zúbáãr dà rúwaá
 3MS NF 5C SOC noun object
 PERF throw water

(Audu threw away water)

ii) Áudù yá á zúbáãr shí
 3MS NF 5B pronoun object
 PERF it

(Audu threw it away)

iii) Áudù yá á zúbáãr e
 3MS NF 5A zero object
 PERF something

(Audu threw (something) away)

(iv) Rúwáá (nèe) Áudù yá ø zúbáár t_i
 FOC 3MS NF 5A trace
 PERF

((It is) water (that) Audu threw away)

In the case of grades 1, 4 and 6 which are represented by both transitive and intransitive verbal bases, grade forms 1A, 4A and 6A are exclusively used by intransitive verbal bases as shown below.

(178)

(a) Áudù yá á jírgàa
 3MS NF 1A
 PERF move aside

(Audu shifted a bit)

(b) Túkúnyaá tá á daárèe
 pot 3FS NF 4A
 PERF crack

(The pot cracked)

(c) Raánaá tá á búlloó
 sun 3FS NF 6A
 PERF appear

(The sun rises)

jírgàa, daárèe and búlloó are intransitive verbs.

(e) Maaǰinaǎ₁ (cèe) Áudù yá ø fyaáccèe t_i
 phlem FOC 3MS NF blow 4B trace
 PERF

((It is) phlem (that) Audu blew out)

(f) Moótàa₁ (ceé) Áudù yá ø kárboó t_i
 car FOC 3MS NF 6B collect
 PERF

(It is) a car (that) Audu collected)

(g) Áudù yá á kírǵàa e
 3MS NF 1B zero object
 PERF count

(Audu counted (something))

(h) Áudù yá á fyaáccèe e
 3MS NF 4B zero object
 PERF blow

(Audu blew (something))

(i) Áudù yá á kárboó e
 3MS NF 6B zero object
 PERF collect

(Audu collected (something))

Grade forms 1C, 4C and 6C are used by transitive verbal bases with a following noun object as shown in (180).

(180)

(a) Audù yá á kírǵà kúdíf
 3MS NF 1C noun object
 PERF count money

(Audu counted money)

(b) Audù yá á fyaácè màajínaá
 3MS NF 4C noun object
 PERF blow out phlem

(Audu blew out phlem)

(c) Audù yá á kárboó móótàa
 3MS NF 6C noun object
 PERF collect car

(Audu collected a car)

The 'transitivity' property of verbal bases operating Grades 1,2,4, 5 and 6 as exemplified in (177), (178), (179) and (180) is summarized in the tables below.

(181)

Grades	Occurring forms of grade			Transitivity to
	A-form	B-form	C-form	
2,5	-aa; -aã	-	-	zero object; traces
2,5	-	-ee; -aã	-	pronoun object
2,5	-	-	-i; -aã	noun object

(182)

Grades	Occurring forms of grade			Transitivity to
	A-form	B-form	C-form	
1,4,6	-	-aa; -ee -oo	-	pronoun object, zero object; trace
1,4,6	-	-	-a; -e, -oo	noun object

There are seven morphological grades of the verb in Hausa, enumerated in (13) chapter one. With the exception of grades 3 and 7 which have only one grade form each, i.e. -a and -u respectively, each of the other grades (1,2,4,5 and 6) contains four grade forms

and the forms are referred to as A, B, C and D forms (see (183) below). Each of the grade forms represents a distinct V-feature, and a verbal base associates with a grade form whose V-features are capable of checking the L-features of the verbal base. A detailed account of the feature composition of grade forms is given in section 4.4.1 of the present chapter.

4.3.2 Head-complement relation

Next we consider another important agreement relation in the verbal component, i.e. the relation between full verb and the syntactic environment²⁹ that follows it immediately. 'Syntactic environment' had been defined in footnote four, chapter one. Six types of syntactic environments are commonly distinguished:

- (i) noun object (ii) pronoun object (iii) zero object
- (iv) trace (v) dative phrase and (vi) clausal complement.

Each of these 'syntactic environments' can follow the verb immediately and must agree with the verb. We refer to each of these 'syntactic environments' as complement

²⁹ Other elements such as the adverbials may follow the verb but they do not fall into these 'syntactic environments' which serve as complements and which follow the verb 'immediately'.

in view of the fact that they behave like true complements. In the Parsonian verbal system (Parsons (1960:23) (1971/72:63)) as shown in (183), four grade forms (A,B,C,D) are isolated for each grade.

(183) <u>Form of grade</u>	<u>Characteristics</u>	<u>Syntactic environment</u>
A	long vowel	zero or null objects and intransitive verbs
B	long vowel	pronoun objects, traces, ³⁰ clausal complements
C	short vowel	noun object
D	long vowel	Dative phrase

³⁰ Parsons (1960: 25-26) points out that "long vowel forms may be exponents of transitivity to an antecedent nominal or pronominal object." By 'antecedent nominal' is meant an NP that has now become antecedent having left its original object position. In the parlance of Principles and Parameters framework we say that the antecedent nominal left behind a coindexed 'trace' of itself. Thus, whereas Parsons makes reference to 'transitivity to an antecedent', we make reference to 'transitivity to a trace'. Hence, the use of trace here.

To consolidate Parson's position in (183), we posit that a transitive verbal base operating say grade 1 will require grade forms 1A, 1B, 1C or 1D as shown in the following examples.

(184) (a) Áudù yá á kaámàa e
 3MS PERF 1A zero object
 catch

(Audu caught)

(b) Áudù yá á kaámàa tá
 3MS PERF 1B pronoun object
 catch

(Audu caught her)

(c) Áudù yá á kaámà àkúyàa
 3MS NF 1C noun object
 PERF catch goat

(Audu caught a goat)

(d) Áudù yá á kaámàa wà Alí àkúyàa
 3MS NF 1D dative
 PERF phrase
 catch for Alí goat
 (Audu caught a goat for Alí)

We would like to observe that the inability of previous efforts as in the Parsonian verbal grade system to capture the actual relationship between full verb and the syntactic environment following it follows from a fundamental aberration in defining the actual phenomena for which they sought a principled account. A basic misconception was the view that the grade element relates directly with the syntactic environment, and in which case, the syntactic environment determines the grade form to occur with the verbal base. This view about verb-syntactic environment relation clearly reverses a normal order by depriving the full verb its right as a head to select its own complement. In actual fact, the grade does not relate with the syntactic environment prior to its association with the verbal base. The grade element, as we have pointed out in the previous section, relates only with the verbal base in order to satisfy an agreement morphology. That is to say, the grade checks the morphological properties of the verbal base, agreeing with it, so as to form a full verb.

- (186) [Áudù] yá á fásà kwálbaá
 NF
 SPEC, 3MS PERF 1C
 AGR-S'' brake bottle
 (Audu broke a bottle)

- (187) [kwálbaá]_i (cèe) Áudù yá ø fásàa t_i
 SPEC FOC 3MS PERF 1B
 CP
 ((It) is) a bottle (that) Audu broke)

The non-future perfective aspect (not the 'relative' type) is represented by -n as in (185a) and -a as in (186). The forms -n and -a are used in clauses containing no elements in their specifier positions and their distribution is as follows:

- (188)
- | AGR | PERF | Aspect | Example | | | | |
|-----|------|--------|-------------------|------|------|-------|--------|
| ná | -a | | (Níí) | ná | á | kaámà | zaákii |
| | | | IM/F | IM/F | NF | catch | lion |
| | | | S | S | PERF | | |
| | | | (I caught a lion) | | | | |

<u>AGR</u>	<u>PERF Aspect</u>	<u>Example</u>			
mú	-ń	(Muú) mú	ń	kaámà	zaákii
			NF		
		IPL IPL	PERF	catch	lion
		(We caught a lion)			
ká	-ń	(Kái) ká	á	kaámà	zaákii
			NF		
		2MS 2MS	PERF	catch	lion
		(You caught a lion)			
kí	-ń	(Keé) kí	ń	kaámà	zaákii
			NF		
		2FS 2FS	PERF	catch	lion
		(You caught a lion)			
kú	-ń	(Kuú) kú	ń	kaámà	zaákii
			NF		
		2PL 2PL	PERF	catch	lion
		(You caught a lion)			
yá	-á	(Shif) yá	á	kaámà	zaákii
			NF		
		3MS 3MS	PERF	catch	lion
		(He caught a lion)			

The forms -ka and -ø (phonetically unrealized) are used in clauses with an element in their specifier positions (i.e. SPEC, CP). They are traditionally referred to as the 'relative forms' of the perfective aspect. Their distribution is as follows:

(189)

<u>AGR</u>	<u>Perfective Aspect</u>	Examples					
ná	-ø	[zaákiil] _i	(neé)	ná	ø	kaámà <u>n</u>	t _i
		SPEC			NF		
		CP lion	FOC	1M/F	PERF	catch	
				S			
		(Lion (it is) I caught)					
mú	-kà	[zaákiil] _i	(neé)	mú	kà	kaámà <u>a</u>	t _i
					NF		
		SPEC	FOC	1PL	PERF		
		CP lion				catch	
		(Lion (it is) we caught)					
ká	-ø	[zaákiil] _i	(neé)	ká	ø	kaámà <u>a</u>	t _i
					NF		
		SPEC	FOC	2MS	PERF		
		CP lion				catch	
		(Lion (it is) you caught)					

<u>AGR</u>	<u>Perfective Aspect</u>	<u>Examples</u>			
ká	-∅	[zaákíi] _i (neé)	ká	∅ NF	kaámàa t _i
		SPEC	FOC	2MS PERF	
		CP lion			catch
		(Lion (it is) you caught)			
kí	-∅	[zaákíi] _i (neé)	kí	kà NF	kaámàa t _i
		SPEC	FOC	2FS PERF	
		CP lion			catch
		(Lion (it is) you caught)			
kú	-kà	[zaákíi] _i (neé)	kú	kà NF	kaámàa t _i
		SPEC	FOC	2PL PERF	
		CP lion			catch
		(Lion (it is) you caught)			
yá	-∅	[zaákíi] _i (neé)	yá	∅ NF	kaámàa t _i
		SPEC	FOC	3MS PERF	
		CP lion			catch
		(Lion (it is) he caught)			

AGR Perfective
Aspect

Examples

tá -∅ [zaákii]_i (neé) tá ∅ kaámàa t_i
NF
SPEC FOC 3FS PERF
CP lion catch
(Lion (it is) she caught)

sú -kà [zaákii] (neé) sú kà kaámàa t_i
NF
SPEC FOC 3PL PERF
CP lion catch
(Lion (it is) they caught)

The non-future continuous aspect is represented by -nàa (190a) and (191a) and by -kee (190b) and (191b) respectively.

(190) (a) Yâaraá sú nàa káñàntà jàñííàa
NF
child- 3PL CONT read newspaper
ren

((The) children are reading a newspaper)

b) [jàříídàa]_i (ceé)³² yáaraá sú kèe kářàntáawáá³³ t_i
 SPEC FOC 3PL NF CONT
 CP

((It is) a newspaper (that) (the) children are reading.

(191) (a) Audù yá nàa fásà kwálbaá
 3MS NF break bottle
 PERF

(Audu is breaking a bottle)

32 There is tonal polarity here. That is to say, the tone of the focus marker (FOC) is always the opposite of the tone of the syllable preceding the focus marker (Cf Parsons 1960: 13-14).

33 Notice that in this example, the NP direct object had moved into [SPEC,CP] and the verb takes an additional -waa suffix. In traditional terms (cf. Kraft and Kirk-Greene (1973:98)) a large number of transitive verbs are said to employ the -waa ending in the continuative aspect, thereby rendering them into 'verbal nouns'. Newman and Newman (1977:x-xi) point out that verbs are normally replaced by verbal nouns (which corresponds to present participle in English) and that regular verbal nouns are derived from verbs in a systematic way, by adding -waa or by lengthening the final vowel. In addition to these facts, the present study further draws attention to the fact that the addition of -waa suffix or additional length to a transitive verb with the non-future continuative aspect occurs only when an object NP moves into [SPEC,CP] as in (i) or when there is a following zero object as in (ii).

(i) [jàříídàa]_i (ceé) yáaraá sú kèe kářàntáawáá t_i
 SPEC FOC children 3PL NF reading
 CP newspaper CONT

((It is) a newspaper (that) (the) children are reading)

(ii) Yáaraá sú nàa kářàntáawáá ø
 children 3PL NF reading zero object
 CONT

((The) children are reading (something))

(b) [^{Kwáalbaá}_i (cee) Audù yá kèe fásàawaá t_i
 SPEC CP FOC 3MS NF CONT breaking

((It is) is a bottle (that) Audu is breaking)

The form -naa of the non-future continuous aspect is used in non-movement clauses and its distribution is as follows:

(192)

<u>AGR</u>	<u>Continuous Aspect</u>	<u>Examples</u>				
ní	-naa	(ní)	ní	Nàa	káṛàntà	jàṛiídàa
		LM/F	IM/F	NF	read	newspaper
		S	S	CONT		

(I am reading a newspaper)

Notice that movement from the subject position to [SPEC,CP] does not motivate verbal noun formation (or the addition of -waa to the verb) but only triggers 'relative' aspect marking (i.e. due to the presence of an element in [SPEC,CP] as shown in (iii)).

(iii) [^{yaaraá}_i (nèe) t_i sú kèe káṛàntà jàṛiídàa
 SPEC, CP FOC 3PL NF CONT read newspaper

((It is) children (that) are reading the newspaper)
 Notice also the falling tone (^) of káṛàntà[^]awaá. With trisyllabic and other polysyllabic verbs, the syllable adjacent to the suffix -waa carries a falling tone.

<u>AGR</u>	<u>Continuous Aspect</u>	<u>Examples</u>				
<i>ní</i>	-nàa	(Níí)	<i>ní</i>	<i>nàa</i>	<i>káàrantà</i>	<i>jààrífàa</i>
		1M/F	1M/F	NF	read	newspaper
		S	S	CONT		
		(We are reading a newspaper)				
<i>ká</i>	-nàa	(Káí)	<i>ká</i>	<i>nàa</i>	<i>káàrantà</i>	<i>jà rííídàa</i>
		2MS	2MS	NF	read	newspaper
				PERF		
		(You are reading a newspaper)				
<i>kí</i>	-nàa	(Kéé)	<i>kí</i>	<i>nàa</i>	<i>káàrantà</i>	<i>jààrífàa</i>
		2FS	2FS	NF		
				CONT		
		(You are reading a newspaper)				
<i>kú</i>	-nàa	(Kuú)	<i>kú</i>	<i>nàa</i>	<i>káàrantà</i>	<i>jààrífàa</i>
		2PL	2PL	NF		
				CONT		
		(You are reading a newspaper)				
<i>tá</i>	-nàa	(ítá)	<i>tá</i>	<i>nàa</i>	<i>káàrantà</i>	<i>jààrífàa</i>
				NF		
		3FS	3FS	CONT		
		(She is reading a newspaper)				

AGR Continuous Aspect

Examples

sú -nàa (Suú) sú nàa kárántà járífàa
NF
3PL 3PL CONT

(They are reading a newspaper)

The form -kee of the continuous aspect is used in clauses containing an element in [SPEC, CP]. This form (-kee) is traditionally referred to as the 'relative' form of the continuous aspect. Its distribution is as in (193).

(193)

AGR Continuous Aspect

Examples

ní -kèe [jàrífàa]_i (ceé) ní kèe kárántáawáa t_i
SPEC FOC 1M/F_{NF} CONT
CP S

(Newspaper (it is) I am reading)

mú -kèe [jàrífàa]_i (ceé) mú kèe kárántáawáa t_i
SPEC FOC 1PL_{NF} CONT
CP

(Newspaper (it is) we are reading)

ká -kèe [jàrífàa]_i ceé ká kèe kárántáawáa t_i
SPEC FOC 2MS_{NF} CONT
CP

(Newspaper (it is) you are reading)

<u>AGR</u>	<u>Continuous Aspect</u>	<u>Examples</u>
kí	-kèe	[jàrĩfɔ̀dàa _i] (ceé) kí kèe káàràntáawá t _i NF SPEC FOC 2FS CONT CP (Newspaper (it is) you are reading)
kú	-kèe	[jàrĩfɔ̀dàa _i] (ceé) kú kèe káàràntáawá t _i NF SPEC FOC 2PL CONT CP (Newspaper (it is) you are reading)
yá	-kèe	[jàrĩfɔ̀dàa _i] (ceé) yá kèe káàràntáawá t _i NF SPEC FOC 3MS CONT CP (Newspaper (it is) he is reading)
tá	-kèe	[jàrĩfɔ̀dàa _i] (ceé) tá kèe káàràntáawá t _i NF SPEC FOC 3FS CONT CP (Newspaper (it is) she is reading)
sú	-kèe	[jàrĩfɔ̀dàa _i] (ceé) sú kèe káàràntáawá t _i NF SPEC FOC 3PL CONT CP (Newspaper (it is) they are reading)

A basic assumption about 'relative' aspect marking is that 'it is dependent at least in part, on movement'. An element may move either from the subject or object position to [SPEC, CP], triggering relative aspect marking as shown in (194).

(194)

(a) Movement from subject position

[	Audù _i	(neé)	[	t _i	yá	∅	kaámà	zaákii
SPEC		FOC	SPEC		3MS	NF	catch	lion
CP			AGR-S					

(Audu (it is) (that) caught a lion)

(b) Movement from object position

[	Zaákii _i	(neé)	Audù	yá	∅	kaámàa	t _i
SPEC		FOC		3MS	NF	catch	
CP	lion						

(Lion (it is) (that) Audu caught)

Tuller (1986: 133) observes that "specifically, relative aspect marking ... represents a test for the presence of an s-structure operator or its trace in the specifier position of a clause. If an operator is in such a position, the INFL it governs must appear in the relative

form. If the trace of an operator is in such position, the INFL it governs may optionally and marginally appear in the relative form." This observation is captured by example (195) which involves wh-movement from the object position of an embedded clause to the specifier position of the matrix clause.

(195) [mèe_i] (neé) 'yánsàndáa sú kà cée
 SPEC FOC police 3PL NF say
 CP what PERF

[[CP SPEC t'_i] yâaraá sú n̄ / sú ka sàyaá t'_i]
 children 3PL NF 3PL NF buy^{2A}
 PERF PERF

(What (is it) (that) the police said the children bought?)

The specifier position of the embedded clause contains the trace (t'_i) of mèe (what). Relative aspect marking is optional in the embedded clause, hence the -n/-ka option for the perfective aspect. The specifier position of the matrix clause is occupied by mèe, hence triggering 'relative aspect marking' (represented by the relative perfective aspect ka) in the matrix clause.

Some contexts have been identified where the relative form of the perfective or the continuous aspect may appear (cf Kraft and Kirk-Greene 1973:104-111). These include relative clauses, wh-interrogative and focus-fronting constructions. Since relative aspect marking is as a result of movement, the three contexts are products of movement processes, namely relativization, wh-interrogation and focus-fronting respectively. These are illustrated in (196)

(196)

Relativization

(a) daálibif [wándà_i t_i yá ø shigá soójà]
 student RC who 3MS NF PERF enter army
 (Student who joined the army)

(b) daálibif [wándà_i mákárántá tá ø kòoraá t_i]
 student RC who school 3FS NF PERF expel
 (Student whom the school expelled)

Wh-interrogation

(a) [SPEC wàa_i] Áudù yá ø màaràa t_i
 CP who 3MS NF PERF slap

(Who did Audu slap?)

(b) [SPEC wàa_i] t_i yá ø màarí Ládí
 CP who 3MS NF PERF slap

(Who slapped Ladi?)

(c) [Mèe]_i Áudù yá kèe káṙànfáawá t_i
 SPEC CP what 3MS NF CONT reading

(What is Audu reading?)

(d) [wàa]_i t_i yá kèe káṙànfá Ashàfáá
 SPEC CP who 3MS NF CONT read Ashafaa

(Who is reading Ashafaa?)

Focus-fronting

(a) [^{SPEC}soójoójif_i] (nèe) t_i sú kà káryà gádaa
 CP FOC 3PL NF PERF break bridge
 soldiers

((It is) (the) soldiers (who) broke the bridge)

(b) [^{SPEC}gádaa_i] (ceé) soójoójif sú kà káryàa t_i
 CP FOC soldiers 3PL NF break
 bridge PERF

(It is) a bridge (that) soldiers broke)

(c) [^{SPEC}gádaa_i] (ceé) soójoójif sú kèe káryàawaá t_i
 CP FOC soldiers 3PL NF breaking
 bridge CONT

(Bridge (it is) (that) soldiers are breaking)

A generalized relative aspect marking has been proposed in Tuller (1986) and it is said to be triggered not only by operators in [SPEC, CP], but also by intermediate traces in specifier positions that are linked to such an operator (cf. 33).

The account of the relative aspect marking given above derives its motivation from the fact that an

operator or its trace in the specifier position of a clause triggers relative aspect marking. The account assumes also that the presence of an operator or its trace in the specifier position is due to movement. This account of relative aspect marking misses the important fact that relative aspect marking is a consequence of some agreement relation holding within the clause. Following ideas in Chomsky (1986b) the agreement relation in Hausa that triggers relative aspect marking may be referred to as 'chain-coindexing' relation. Chain-coindexing relation is a relation obtaining between a head and its trace in a chain. A chain is a product of movement and the antecedent X (head) and its trace t (foot) in the chain (X...t) maintain a relation. Chomsky (1986b:68-80) points out that chain coindexing refers to a relation between antecedent and its trace in which properties of the raised antecedent including index 'percolates' to the antecedent. Chain-coindexing is achieved under government. Thus, a proper chain is one that satisfies the chain coindexing relation. An idiosyncrasy of Hausa is that proper chain formation, apart from satisfying coindexing, must also be marked by a

'relative' aspect. That is to say, in Hausa, even though a well motivated movement into [SPEC, CP] may satisfy chain coindexing thereby producing proper chain in the clause, that notwithstanding, the resultant structure remains ill-formed if 'relative' aspect marking is not effected as shown in (197).

(197)

(a) * [Audù_i] (neé) t_i yá nà kárántà járiídàa
 SPEC CP FOC 3MS NF read newspaper
 CONT

(It is Audu who is reading the newspaper)

(b) * [járiídàa $_i$] (ceé) Audù yá á kárántaá t_i
 SPEC CP news-paper FOC 3MS NF PERF read

(It is a newspaper that Audu read)

The chains ($\text{Audù} \dots t$) and ($\text{járiídàa} \dots t$) in (197a) and (197b) respectively are proper chains that satisfy chain coindexing. However, the resultant structures

Notice that this broad outlook of the 'relative' aspect marking as signifying 'aspectual agreement' in clauses containing proper chains is missing in the earlier account of the phenomenon given above. The phenomenon of relative aspect marking is strictly as a result of movement to [SPEC, CP]. A movement to [SPEC, AGR-S''] for example, does not trigger relative aspect marking as shown in (199).

- (199) [mángxwàrò_i] yá á nùuná t_i
 SPEC mango 3MS NF rife
 AGR-S'' ↑ PERF
- (Mango has ripen)

The object movement in (199) is not focus-fronting. The verb nùuná is unaccusative. Its passive morphology makes it incapable of assigning Accusative Case to its direct object mángxwàrò. Mángxwàrò therefore had to move to [SPEC, AGR-S''] to receive Nominative Case under spec-head agreement. Notice however that a vacuous movement of mángxwàrò from [SPEC, AGR-S''] to [SPEC, CP] in (200) creates a chain (mángxwàrò....t) which will necessitate relative aspect marking (∅ NF PERF) under chain-coindexing relation.

(200) [SPEC mǎngwàrò₁] (neé) [SPEC t₁] yá ∅ nùuná
 CP mango FOC AGR-S' 3MS NF ripe

(It is mango (that) has ripen)

4.4 Further Aspects of Agreement Relations

4.4.1 Feature Composition of grade forms

In chapter three I argued that the grade element of the Hausa verb is the overt realization of the equivalent of Chomsky's abstract AGR-0, a functional element that marks object agreement in the verbal component. I also pointed out in section 3.2.3 that the grade (or AGR-0) is a composite of matching verbal features that check the morphological features of the verbal base. In this section, I will examine closely the feature composition of the grade element, showing how the features help in accounting for the phenomena I refer to as 'grade form substitution' and other aspects of null elements in Hausa. 'Grade form substitution'³⁵

³⁵ The 'grade form substitution' phenomena advocated in the present study differs from the familiar "grade borrowing" (Newman (1973:302-303), Parsons

is a strategy employed by a transitive verbal base to substitute a grade form meant for a pronoun object for one meant for a zero object. It is necessary that the two substituting grade forms are forms of one grade. Grade form substitution helps to clear a vague situation such as (201) created by the presence of a null element e following a transitive verb directly.

(201) Áudù yá á àuraá e
 3MS NF 2A zero object
 PERF marry

(Audu married (someone))

(1971/72:75-79)) in which a given verbal base, while operating a particular grade, for example grade 2 (i), may borrow and operate the predivative (D-form) of another grade say grade 5 as in (ii).

i) Áudu yá á kàrbí kúdíf
 2C
 collect money

(Audu collected money)

ii) Áudù yá á kàrbáā [wà Alí] kúdíf
 5D dative
 phrase

(Audu collected money for Alí)

This is because operating the D-form of grade 2 (i.e. -aa LH) will yield an ill-formed structure as shown in (iii).

iii) *Áudù yá á kàrbáā [wà Alí] kúdíf
 2D dative
 phrase

A grade form substitution (2B for 2A) as in (202) allows a pronoun in place of a gap or zero object and this marks the sentence less vague.

(202) Audù yá á àureé tà
 3MS NF 2B pronoun object
 PERF marry her
 (Audu married her)

A discussion on the application of the phenomena of 'grade form substitution' is presented in chapter five.

The grade is made up of a variety of features: phonological, and syntactic and perhaps semantic.³⁶ The phonological and syntactic features are directly relevant here.³⁷ Syntactic features of the grade include transitivity feature [+ Transitive], length feature [+ Long],

³⁶ Compare Newman (1973:300-304).

³⁷ The phonological feature is the feature [Tone]. Each grade form has a distinct tone pattern for disyllabic and polysyllabic verbs, with basic tone pattern indicated for disyllabic verbs. Grades 1 and 4 share same tone pattern (HL) but are not phonetically similar. Grades 2,3 and 7 share LH tone pattern and grades 5 and 6 share HH tone pattern. They are also dissimilar phonetically.

<u>Grades</u>	<u>Tone Pattern</u>
1,4	HL
2,3	LH
5,6	HH

Unaccusativity feature [+ Unaccusative], Case feature [$\pm$ Case], NP feature [$\pm$ Pronominal], the feature [+Dative] and the feature [+Sociative].

4.4.1.1 The feature [+ Transitive]

Two types of objects are distinguished in Hausa: phonetically realized objects (nouns and pronouns) and null objects. A null object can be a zero object or a trace. The objects are illustrated as follows:

(203)

(a) Audù yá á kaámà kiffif
 3MS NF
 PERF catch fish
 NP object

(Audu caught it)

(b) Audù yá á kaámà shí
 3MS NF
 3MS PERF catch it
 pronoun object

(Audu caught it)

(c) Audù yá á kaámà e
 3MS NF
 3MS PERF catch zero or dummy object

(Audu caught (something))

A further picture of this representation which contains the actual phonetic shape of the grade forms was given in section 1.1.1.4 of chapter one.

(d) Kiffif₁ (nee) Audù yá [∅] kaámàa t₁
 fish FOC 3MS NF PERF catch trace

((It is) fish (that) Audu caught)

The feature [+ Transitive] indicates that the verb takes an object or complement. A transitive verbal base that takes a direct noun object requires a grade form with the following features:

(204)

+ HL/+HH/+LH
+ Long
+ Case
+ Transitive
- Pronominal
+ Sociative

Each of the following grade forms C contains these features as shown in (205) and therefore can take a direct noun object.

(205) Grade	Grade form (C)	Feature matrix					
1	-a	<table border="1"> <tr><td>+HL</td></tr> <tr><td>-Long</td></tr> <tr><td>+Case</td></tr> <tr><td>+Transitive</td></tr> <tr><td>-Pronominal</td></tr> </table>	+HL	-Long	+Case	+Transitive	-Pronominal
+HL							
-Long							
+Case							
+Transitive							
-Pronominal							

38 The feature [+Sociative] is only required by verbal bases operating grade 5.

<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form (C)</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
2	-i	[+LH -Long +Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
4	-e	[+HL -Long +Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
5	-aĩ	[+HH +Long +Case +Transitive -Pronominal +Sociative]
6	-oo	[+HH +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]

A transitive base that takes a pronoun object or null object requires a grade form with the following features.

(206)	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
1	(a)	-aa (B-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +LH +Long +Case +Transitive +Pronominal]
	(b)	-aa (B-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +LH +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
2	(a)	-aa (A-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +LH +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
	(b)	-ee (B-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +LH +Long +Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
4	(a)	-ee (B-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +HL +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
	(b)	-ee (B-form)	[<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +HL +Long +Case +Transitive +Pronominal]

<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
5	(a) -ař (A-form)	[+HH +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
	(b) -ař (B-form)	[-HH +Long +Case +Transitive +Pronominal]
6	(a) -oo (B-form)	[+HH +Long -Case +Transitive -Pronominal]
	(b) -oo (B-form)	[+HH +Long +Case +Transitive +Pronominal]

An intransitive base requires the feature [-Transitive] and a grade form with the following features:

(207) <u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
1	-aa (A-form)	[+HL +Long -Case -Transitive]

<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
4	-ee (A-form)	[+HL +Long -Case -Transitive]
6	-oo (A-form)	[+HH +Long -Case -Transitive]

Notice that A-forms of grade 1 (-aa), grade 4 (-ee) and grade 6 (-oo) are the only grade forms available for intransitive verbal bases.

4.4.1.2 The feature [+ Long]

Length feature is realized as short or long, i.e. [+ Long], meaning that the grade element, being essentially a vowel, is realized as short vowel [-Long] or long vowel [+Long]. Grade 5 which is realized as -aĩ is considered long i.e. [+Long].³⁹ The feature [-Long] indicates having a following noun object. However, grades 5

³⁹ Following arguments in Parsons (1971/72:75-76; 88), -aĩ or -VC equal -VV. Newman (1973:313) also argues that "one can certainly say that whatever other complexities there might be, all of the pre-pronoun vowels are long, i.e. the rule of final vowel lengthening before personal pronoun object stands intact as a well verified, actively productive rule

and 6 verbs, despite having the feature [+Long] i.e. long grade forms, are still followed by noun object.⁴⁰ Grade 3 and 7 verbs are Unaccusative but must be [-Long] to indicate that at the d-structure level of representation, they have a following noun object. The noun object must however move to [SPEC,AGR-S'] at s-structure to receive Case.

4.4.1.3 The feature [$\pm$ Case]

Intransitive bases require the feature [-Case]. Transitive bases that are followed immediately by null objects also require the feature [-Case]. The feature [+Case] indicates that there is a following direct object (noun or pronoun) to receive an Accusative Case. The feature [+Transitive] alone is not enough to distinguish overt object noun and pronoun (which receive Case) from

in Hausa". Now since -aĩ is found with a following pronoun, it must be long.

⁴⁰ Our present knowledge of the grade system does not allow us deduce any reason for this deviation. As at now, we shall view the lengthening in the C-forms of grades 5 and 6 as an exception to the standard pattern of shortening before a following noun object.

null object (zero and trace). The feature [+Case] must also be considered.

4.4.1.4 The feature [+Pronominal]

The feature [+Pronominal] further distinguishes types of objects. The feature [+Pronominal] represents direct object pronoun. The feature [-Pronominal] indicates direct noun object, zero object or trace. Grades 1,4 and 6 are operated by both transitive and intransitive bases. The A-forms of grades 1,4, and 6 are used exclusively by intransitive bases; B-forms are used by transitive bases with a following pronoun or null object. D-forms are used by transitive bases with a following dative phrase. This information is illustrated as follows.

(208)

Grades	Occurring forms of grade				Elements that follow full verb
	A-form	B-form	C-form	D-form	
a 1,4,6	-aa/-ee -oo	-	-	-	nothing, being intransitive
b 1,4,6	-	-aa/-ee -oo	-	-	pronoun object, zero object, trace
c 1,4,6	-	-	-a/-e -oo	-	noun object
d 1,4,6	-	-	-	-aa/-ee -oo	dative phrase

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Grades 2 and 5 are used exclusively by transitive verbal bases. This being the case, the A-forms of these grades are used for zero objects and traces; B-forms for pronoun objects; C-forms for noun and D-forms for dative phrases. This information is represented in the following table.

(209)

Grades	Occurring forms of grade				Elements that follow full verb
	A-form	B-form	C-form	D-form	
a 2,5	-aa; -aã	-	-	-	zero objects; traces
b 2,5	-	-ee; -aã	-	-	pronoun objects
c 2,5	-	-	-i; -aã ⁴¹	-	noun objects
d 2,5	-	-	-	-aa; aã ⁴²	dative phrase

41 With grade 5 C-form -aã, the feature [+Sociative] represented by the Sociative particle da is required between the grade form -aã and the noun object. See section 4.4.1.7 for further discussion.

42 Parsons (1971/72) points out that the suggested D-form -aa LH for grade 2, if operated by a verbal base, produces unacceptable structures such as the following.

i) a. ?Alí yá á dàukaá [wà Muúsaá] kúdíí
 3MS NF 2D dative money
 phrase

(Ali took for Musa money)

4.4.1.5 The feature [+Unaccusative]

The unaccusative verbal base stands distinct. It differs from that verbal base which assigns Accusative (or Objective) Case to its direct noun or pronoun object, and from those verbal bases which though transitive, do not assign Accusative Case to their objects or complements, the objects/complements being null (i.e. zero object or trace). The passive morphology of the unaccusative verbal base makes it incapable of assigning Accusative Case. An unaccusative verbal base requires a grade form with the following features.

b. ?Alí yá á fíẓgaá [wà Laádi] àdiíkòò
 3MS NF 2D dative head-tie
 PERF grab

(Ali grabbed for Ladi a head-tie)

He argues that grade 2 must 'borrow' D-forms from grades 1, 4, and 5, the 'lending' grades. (i)a and b become well-formed after 'borrowing' 5D and 4D forms respectively as in (ii).

ii) a Alí yá á dáukáṛ [wà Muúsaá] kúdíí
 5D dative
 phrase

b Alí yá á fíẓgèè [wà Laádi] àdiíkòò
 4D dative
 phrase

(210)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{LH} \\ -\text{Long} \\ +\text{Unaccusative} \end{array} \right]$$

The grade forms -e (for grade 3) and -u (for grade 7) are used exclusively for the unaccusatives. No other grade form carries the feature [+Unaccusative].

4.4.1.6 The Feature [+Dative]

Parsons (1971/72:63) defines the dative phrase as "a noun, pronoun or nominal group preceded by, or in construction with, the particle wà/mà/má. This particle can only follow a finite verb or a 'nomino-verbal' or 'weak' verbal noun." The NP that occurs with the dative is referred to as indirect object and the grade form employed for a following dative phrase is called pre-dative or D-form. Parsons (1971/72:76) points out that every grade has a D-form but grades 2,3 and 7 'borrow' their D-forms from the 'lending' grades 1,4, and 5 because native speakers, most often, prefer 1D, 4D and 5D forms instead of 2D, 3D and 7D forms. We shall propose in the present study the feature [+Dative] to indicate a following dative phrase. Notice that in

Hausa, the indirect object is licenced by the dative particle wa/ma. The feature [+Dative] is therefore represented by wà/mà/má. An indirect object is licenced by wà or mà if it is a noun or anaphor. It is licenced by má alone if it is a pronoun (cf Parsons (1971/72: 66)). Since the actual D-forms of grades 2,3 and 7 are seldom used by native speakers of Hausa, we shall mark them ** in (214) to indicate rare occurrence. The three forms are hypothetical D-forms which are seldom used. Parsons (1971/72: 78) states that "in point of fact, in the whole of Hausa lexicon, I know of only two grade 7 verbs that are used with a dative, tàarú (gather) and àukú (happen)." Thus, grades 2,3, and 7 must 'borrow' their D-forms from the 'lending' grades 1,4, and 5.

The present study goes further to determine the categorial status of the introducer wa. We must point out that referring to wa as an 'introducer' does not indicate the syntactic category that wa belongs to.

We are tempted to assume that wa may be a verb, taking into account the fact that it exhibits a mutational behaviour, typically associated with Hausa regular verbs. That is to say, the w- stem takes a short vowel a if the indirect object following it is a noun or an anaphor (211a and b) and long vowel aa if it is followed by the trace of the indirect object (211c).

(211) (a) Áuduù yá á kaámàa [wà Alí]⁴³ kiífií
 3MS NF catch for Ali fish
 PERF

(Audu caught fish for Ali)

(b) Áudu yá á kaámàa [wà kansà] kiífií
 3MS NF catch for himself fish
 PERF

(Audu caught fish for himself)

⁴³ See Munkaila (1990) for a discussion on the positioning of the Hausa indirect object between verb and its direct object and on how Case is assigned to the direct object.

(c) Alí (nee) Áudù yá ó kaámàa [wàa t₁] kiffií
 FOC 3MS NF PERF catch for fish

(It is Ali (that) Audu caught fish for)

Notice that w- is a quasi verb since its ability to assign objective (or Accusative) Case is limited to indirect objects only.

4.4.1.7 The Feature [+Sociative]

We have shown that the C-form of grade 5 -aĩ is long and may take a direct noun object. However, it will be explained below that, Hausa requires an obligatory element dà between -aĩ and the direct object:

-aĩ dà Noun object
 5C

Parsons (1971/72: 60-61) refers to dà as 'sociative' particle. Neither Parsons (1971/72) nor

Newman (1973) accounted for the presence of dà in causative constructions. The present study offers the following explanation. Grade 5 is essentially a causative grade, meaning that verbal bases that operate it have causative meaning. Following ideas in Grimshaw (1990), the argument structure of a Hausa causative verb requires essentially a causative agent which is an external argument to the verb. The experiencer of the action denoted by the verb when present cannot follow the verb directly. This is because a causative verb in Hausa does not assign Accusative Case to the experiencer of its action. Rather, a Sociative particle da (placed between the verb and the experiencer of its action) is required to mark the causative relationship. The sociative particle da also licences the experiencer NP, assigning to it perhaps a 'Sociative Case'. The experiencer NP (noun, anaphor, subject pronoun) requires the licenser dà in causative constructions as shown in the following examples:

(212)

(a) Audù yá á sáyá̄r [dà doókii]
 3MS NF 5C soc. noun object
 PERF sell horse
 'Audu caused the sale of a horse'
 (Audu sold a horse)

(b) Audù yá á sáyá̄r [dà kânsà]⁴⁴
 3MS NF 5C soc. anaphor object
 PERF
 'Audu caused the sale (of something) himself'
 (Audu sold out something himself)

(c) Audù yáa á sáyá̄r [dà shíí]⁴⁵
 3MS NF 5C soc. subject pronoun
 PERF sell he/it
 'Audu caused the sale of something'
 (Audu sold it)

⁴⁴ kânsà is ambiguous. It can also be interpreted as 'his head'. With this interpretation, the sentence will translate as 'Audu sold his own head'.

⁴⁵ A rudimentary morphological Case marking is found in the pronominal system of Hausa. Here, distinction between subject and object is marked morphologically as shown in (i). Notice that the object pronouns resemble the forms of AGR-S in (158), chapter four.

We suggest that dà and the experiencer NP constitute a 'sociative phrase' [dà NP]. A dative phrase may precede the sociative phrase as in the following example.

i) Subject pronoun

ní 1M/FS
muú 1PL
káí 2MS
keé 2FS
kuú 2PL
shíí 3MS
ítá 3FS
suú 3PL

Object pronoun

ní 1M/FS
mú 1PL
ká 2MS
kí 2FS
kú 2PL
shí 3MS
tá 3FS
sú 3PL

With the causative verb, the experiencer of the action of the verb may be an object pronoun, and in which case, the sociative particle dà is not required to license the object pronoun as shown in the following examples

ii) Audù yá á sáyáã shí
3MS NF 5B pronoun object
PERF sell it
(Audu sold it)

But in most Hausa dialects, the subject pronoun is preferred in place of object pronoun. This

(213)

Audu yá á sáyá̄r̄ [wà Alí] [dà doókii]
 3MS NF 5D dative sociative
 PERF phrase phrase
 'Audu caused the sale of a horse to Ali'
 (Audu sold a horse to Ali)

Notice that the causative verb sáyá̄r̄ now assumes a D-form, indicating that it is followed directly by a dative phrase.

Thus far I have discussed the various features that make up the grade elements of the verb. The table (214) below gives a vivid representation of the grade forms and their inherent phonological and syntactic features. Notice that the table differs from its counterpart (13) in chapter one. Thus, whereas the table (214) displays the essential feature composition of each grade form, the table (13) is not

being the case, the subject pronoun appears only with the sociative particle dà to license it as in (212c) above. The causative structure (ii) (with object pronoun) is only common in Gúddiri, one of the dialects of Hausa.

so vivid in this respect. Table (214) also differs from (13) in respect of the grade form status of grades 3 and 7 -a and -u forms which were said to be A-forms in (13). Here the grade forms -a and -u are said to be C-forms as argued in section 1.1.2 of chapter one.

(214) Table showing feature composition of grade forms

GRADE	A-FORM	B-FORM	C-FORM	D-FORM
	aa	aa	a	aa
Grade 1	[+HL(H) +Long -Case -Trans]	[+HL(H) +Long +Case +Trans +Pron]	[+HL(L) -Long +Case +Trans -Fron]	[+HL(L) -Long -Case +Trans +Dative]
	aa	ee	i	aa**
Grade 2	[+LH(L) +Long -Case +Trans -Pron]	[+(L)LH +Long +Case +Trans +Pron]	[+(L)LH -Long +Case +Trans -Pron]	[+LH(L) +Long -Case +Trans +Dative]
			a	a**
Grade 3	-	-	[+LH(L) -Long -Case +Unacc -Pron]	[+LH(L) -Long -Case +Unacc +Dative]
	ee	ee	e	ee
Grade 4	[+HL(H) +Long -Case -Trans]	[+HL(H) +Long +Case +Trans +Pron]	[+HL(H) -Long +Case +Trans -Pron]	[+HL(H) +Long -Case +Trans +Dative]
	aĩ	aĩ	aĩ	aĩ
Grade 5	[+(H)HH +Long -Case -Trans -Pron]	[+(H)HH +Long +Case +Trans +Pron]	[+(H)HH +Long +Case +Trans -Pron +Sociative]	[+(H)HH +Long -Case +Trans +Dative]
	oo	oo	oo	oo
Grade 6	[+(H)HH +Long -Case -Trans]	[+(H)HH +Long +Case +Trans +Pron]	[+(H)HH +Long +Case +Trans -Pron]	[+(H)HH +Long -Case +Trans +Dative]
	-	-	u	u**
Grade 7			[+(L)LH -Long -Case +Unacc -Pron]	[+(L)LH -Long -Case +Unacc +Dative]

4.5 Null complements of Hausa

The Hausa verb is essentially an agreement complex, comprising 'agreeing' components, namely, the verbal base and the grade.⁴⁶ The verbal base contains morphological features which must be checked by a checking element, the grade, which in itself contains inherent matching verbal features. Thus, a perfectly formed verb, a full verb, is complete with its sub-categorization requirements.

The relationship between a Hausa verb and any of the syntactic environments (noun object, pronoun object, zero object, trace, dative phrase, clausal complement) is strictly subcategorizational, with the verb absolutely 'agreeing' with each of the said syntactic environments. This being the case, the agreement pattern in the verbal component will be quite 'unusual' since not only the standard verb-object agreement relation will then be found. The nature of agreement between full verb and the element following it is one of 'licencing'. The feature

⁴⁶ The claim that the verb contains these two morphological parts have been made earlier especially in 4.2.3.

composition of the verb which is represented in the grade, licences a following element. For example, a full verb such as kaámà 'catch', whose grade component -à carries the features [+HL, -Long, +Transitive, +Case, -Pronominal] will require a direct noun object as shown in (215).

(215) Áudù yá á [kaámà] kífif
 3MS NF V 1C N object
 PERF

[+HL
 -Long
 +Case
 +Transitive
 -Pronominal]

(Audu caught a fish)

Similarly, the full verb 'kaámàa 'catch', whose grade component carries the features [+HL, +Long, +Case, +Transitive, +Pronominal] requires either a null complement (zero object or trace) or object pronoun as shown in (216).

(216)

(a) Áudù yá á [kaámàa] shí
 3MS NF V 1B pronoun object
 PERF

[+HL
 +Long
 +Case
 +Transitive
 +Pronominal]

(Audu caught it/him)

b) Audù yá á [kaámàa] e
 3MS NF V 1B zero object
 PERF

[+HL
 +Long
 -Case
 +Transitive
 -Pronominal]

(Audu caught something)

c) Kiffif_i (nèe) Audù yá ø [kaámàa] t_i
 FOC 3MS NF V 1B trace
 PERF

[+HL
 +Long
 -Case
 +Transitive
 -Pronominal]

(Fish (it is) (that) Audu caught)

All grades have forms that cater for null complements. However, grades 3 and 7 have only one grade form, the C-form, which carries the feature [+Unaccusative]. Grades 1, 4 and 6, which cater for both transitive and intransitive verbal bases, have one grade form each for both pronoun object and null complements (zero object and

trace). It is the grade form B. In this case, the feature [+Pronominal] distinguishes trace and zero object [-Pronominal] from object pronoun [+Pronominal].

Grades 2 and 5, which cater exclusively for transitive verbal bases, assign the grade form A for null complements (zero object and trace) and grade form B for pronoun object. In the case of grade 2, the A-form of the grade is -aa and the B-form is -ee. A-form and B-form of grade 2 are distinguished by the features [+Case] and [+Pronominal] as can be seen from their feature matrices in (217).

(217)	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
	2	A (-aa)	$\begin{bmatrix} +HL \\ +Long \\ -Case \\ +Transitive \\ -Pronominal \end{bmatrix}$
	2	B (-ee)	$\begin{bmatrix} +HL \\ +Long \\ +Case \\ +Transitive \\ +Pronominal \end{bmatrix}$

In the case of grade 5, the A and B forms of the grade which cater for null complements and pronoun objects

respectively, are phonetically similar. That is to say, each is realized as -aĩ. They are distinguished however by the features [Case] and [Pronominal] as shown in the following paradigm.

(218)	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Grade form</u>	<u>Feature matrix</u>
	5	A (-aĩ)	$\left[\begin{array}{l} +HH \\ +Long \\ -Case \\ +Transitive \\ -Pronominal \end{array} \right]$
	5	B (-aĩ)	$\left[\begin{array}{l} +HH \\ +Long \\ +Case \\ +Transitive \\ +Pronominal \end{array} \right]$

The grade (or AGR-O) in Hausa provides a way of determining agreement in the verbal component of the clause in a similar fashion AGR-S provides mechanism for determining agreement in the subject component of the clause structure.

4.5.1 Null subject-null object Hypothesis Hausa: A Review

Tuller (1986) points out that Hausa allows null subjects and null objects and argues that the null subject-null object hypothesis for Hausa has direct

relevance to subadjacency. The phenomenon of null subject and null object is represented by the following examples;

(219)

(a) [e] yá á kaámà kifíif
 null subject 3MS PERF catch fish

((Someone) caught a fish)

(b) Audù yá á kaámàa [e]
 3MS PERF catch null object (zero object)

(Audu caught something)

(c) Kifíif₁ (nèe) Audù yá ø kaámàa [t_i]
 fish FOC 3MS PERF catch null object (trace)

(Fish (it is) (that) Audu caught)

Tuller (1986: 319-403) makes the following observations about null subjects and null objects in Hausa.

- (220) (a) There should be a phi-feature identification of null subjects and null objects.
- (b) Null subjects and null objects are pros.
- (c) Subject and object pro require a pro-identifier and pro-licencer and the identifier is not necessarily the licencer.
- (d) Null objects cannot be PRO, NP trace or variable.

(e) In Hausa, pro licencing heads are INFL, V and N.

Tuller links the phenomenon of null subject and null object with the subjacency condition through resumptive strategies which are meant to circumvent subjacency violations in relativization structures. She further points out that Hausa, like other languages, employ two resumptive strategies to circumvent subjacency violation. The strategies are (i) the use of gap and (ii) the use of resumptive pronouns. The use of resumptive pronoun is optional and gap can always be used instead. Tuller therefore assumed that the fact that Hausa allows null subjects and null objects facilitates for subjacency violation in relativization structures which otherwise would have obeyed subjacency. She points out further that the gap strategy which is essentially the manipulation of the null subject and null object facts of Hausa, is not available to focus-fronting and wh-interrogation. Thus, structures involving wh-interrogation or focus-fronting out of subjacency islands or complex clauses, must always obey subjacency.

Some of the observation made by Tuller on facts of null subject and null object in Hausa are not quite

correct. For example, null objects are not licensed solely by phi-features in the strict sense of the features gender, number and person. Rather, they are licensed by some form of agreement relation obtaining between verb and null object (see section 4.3.2). We can also contest Tuller's claim that null objects cannot be NP traces or variables. I assume that in Hausa NP traces are null objects because they share similar characteristics with the other null object, the zero object, such as being licensed by same grade form. Notice that 'verb-syntactic environment' relationship is governed by agreement and same agreement features allow for verb-syntactic environment relation whether the syntactic environment is realized as zero object, trace or variable as illustrated by the following examples.

(221)

(a)	[	Kiffif] _i	(nèe)	Audù	yá	∅	kaámàa	t _i
	SPEC,		FOC		3MS	NF	1B	trace
	CP	fish				PERF		
							[	
							+HL	
							+Long	
							+Trans.	
							-Case	
							-Pronom.]	

((It is) fish (that) Audu caught)

(b) Audù	yá	á	kaámàa	e
	3MS	NF	1B	zero object
		PERF	[	
			+HL	
			+Long	
			+Trans	
			-Case	
			-Pronom	
			]	

(Audu caught (something))

In the examples above, the verb enters into agreement relation with a trace and zero object in the same manner indicated by the use of same grade form (i.e. 1B) to mark agreement relation with both.

In chapter five of the present study, a morpho-syntactic approach to the null subject and null object object issue of Hausa is advocated. I claimed there that null subjects and null objects are products of agreement relations. That is to say, null subjects and null objects are licenced by agreement relations.

4.5.1.1 Null Subject

Tuller (1986) rightly points out that there should be phi-feature identification of null subject. In the Minimalist framework, it is assumed that the subject NP has morphological features (phi-features) which are

share with a checking element under a government relationship. The subject element is in the specifier position of AGR-S'' as shown in (222).

Spec-head agreement relation obtains between an element in the specifier position and AGR-S head as previously mentioned in 4.2.1. The element in SPEC, AGR-S'' (i.e. the subject NP) may appear null as shown in (223).

(223)

(a) [SPEC, NP_e] yá á kaámà zaákii
 AGR-S AGR-S NF 1C lion
 AGR-S'' 3MS PERF catch

((Someone) caught a lion)

b) [SPEC, NP_e] kí nàa káǎ̀ántaá tá
 AGR-S'' AGR-S NF 1B it
 2FS CONT read

((You) are reading it)

Null subject is permissible because the position it occupies is properly identified by AGR-S ya. That is to say, ya carries all the phi-features (person, gender and number) of the subject element. In Hausa, AGR-S is overtly represented by a marker which contains strong NP features and this explains why subject can appear in the language.

4.5.1.2 Null Object

Agreement relation in the verbal component is complex. The verb enters into agreement relation with every null element that follows it directly. One of the elements that follow the verb directly is the zero object, a null object. The null object is a product of agreement: the verb inherently agrees with the null object. The ability of the verb to agree with a null

object is an inherent property which is overtly manifested by a 'long form' assumed by the grade (or AGR-O). The inherent agreement relation between the verb and the null object does not require Accusative Case assignment. Consider the following examples:

(224)

(a)	Yáaraá	sú	ń	kàllaá	e
		AGR-S	NF	AGR-O	zero object
	children	3PL	FERF	look 2B	

((The) children looked (at something))

(b)	Audù	yá	á	kaámàa	e
		AGR-S	NF	AGR-O	zero object
		3MS	PERF	1B	
				catch	

(Audu caught (something))

The verbal bases kall- 'look' and kaam- 'catch' are transitive verbal bases. The two operate the grade forms 2B and 1B respectively to accommodate a zero object. Thus, null subjects and null objects are independently motivated in the grammar; they have language internal motivation. For instance, null subjects and null objects can be manipulated in 'subjacency islands' or

complex clauses to serve as strategies for circumventing subjacency violation even though that might not be their principal function.

4.5.2 Phonetically non-realized agreement markers

An important aspect of agreement relation in the Hausa clause structure is the realization that subject agreement element, AGR-S (and perhaps object agreement element, AGR-O too) can be null or phonetically unrealized as shown in (225b).

(225)

(a)	Áudù	[yá]	nàa	kaámà	kiffif
			NF		
	AGR-S		CONT	catch	fish
	3MS				

(Áudu is catching a fish)

(b)	Áudù	[ø]	nàa	kaámà	kiffif
			NF		
	null	AGR-S	CONT	catch	fish
		3MS			

(Áudu is catching a fish)

Notice the presence of AGR-S yá (3MS) in (225a).
This phenomenon of having a null subject agreement

element as in (225b) is commonly referred to in the literature as 'agreement drop'. We would like to point out at the outset that 'agreement drop' is not an automatic phenomenon applicable to every subject agreement element as can be seen from the following examples.

(226) (a) $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ [yá] á kaámà kifíif
 AGR-S NF
 3MS PERF

(Audu caught a fish)

(b) * $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ [ø] á kaámà kifíif
 null AGR-S NF
 3MS PERF

(227) (a) $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ [zaá] [yà] kaámà kifíif
 FUT AGR-S
 3MS

(Audu will catch a fish)

(b) * $\text{\AA}ud\grave{u}$ [zaá] [ø] kaámà kifíif
 FUT null AGR-S
 3MS

We claim that 'agreement drop' renders (226b) and (227b) ill-formed. Previous accounts of 'agreement drop' as in

Tuller (1990), were unable to give plausible explanations regarding motivation, nature and limitations of 'agreement drop' in Hausa. We shall examine in some detail in the following sections, the phenomenon of subject agreement drop. The present study will also, on analogy with subject agreement drop, attempt to account for a possible 'object agreement drop'.

4.5.2.1 Subject agreement drop or null AGR-S

Consider the following sentences.

(228)

(a) Laádi tá nàa káǎràntà jàǎííǎà
 AGR-S NF read newspaper
 3FS CONT

(Ladi is reading a newspaper)

(b) Laádi ø nàa káǎràntà jàǎííǎà
 null AGR-S NF read newspaper
 3FS CONT

(Ladi is reading a newspaper)

(229)

(a) Áudù (neé) yá kèe fásà duútsèe
 FOC AGR-S NF crush stone
 3MS CONT

(Audu (it is) (who) is crushing stones)

(b) Áudù (neé) ø kèe fásà duútsèe
 FOC null NF crush stone
 AGR-S CONT
 3MS

(Audu (it is) (who) is crushing stones)

(230)

(a) Áudù yá kán tàfí goónáá
 AGR-S NF go farm
 3MS HAB

(Audu does go to the farm)

(b) Áudù ø kán tàfí goónáá
 AGR-S NF go farm
 3MS HAB

(Audu does go to the farm)

AGR-S or subject agreement element, is phonetically

unrealized in (228b), (229b) and (230b) as indicated by $\emptyset$ which represents null AGR-S. Null realization of AGR-S is possible with non-future continuous aspect as in (228b), and (229b) and with non-future habitual aspect as in (230b).

Impossible cases of null realization of AGR-S (or AGR-S drop)

There are also instances in which null realization of AGR-S is not possible. We can identify three such instances.

- (2.31) i) left adjunction of future tense zaá to AGR-S
 ii) presence of non-phonetically realized tense-aspect.
 iii) presence of an enclitic (bound morpheme) tense-aspect which must attach to AGR-S at PF.

Left adjunction of zaá to AGR-S and null realization of AGR-S

We consider first the following partial articulated Hausa clause structure.

Recall that we have argued in section 4.2.2 that Nominative Case assignment is done under spec-head relation and this forces us to assume that TNS-ASP, which assigns Nominative Case, incorporates into AGR-S to allow Nominative Case assignment under spec-head agreement relation as shown in (232) above. The incorporation of TNS-ASP into AGR-S involves right adjunction of TNS-ASP to AGR-S except for the future tense zaá which involves left adjunction as shown in (233).

The implication of the left adjunction of zaá to AGR-S is that the sequence zaá-AGR-S does not conform with the natural (or basic) sequence AGR-S -TNS-ASP found with all other tense aspects of Hausa, and at PF, zaá-AGR-S, being a marked sequence, does not permit null realization of AGR-S as shown by the ill-formedness of the following example.

(234) *Audu [zaá ø] kaámà kiífíí
 TNS- null
 ASP AGR-S

A left adjunction of TNS-ASP to AGR-S as in (233) above, violates the natural sequence AGR-S - TNS-ASP which allows null realization of AGR-S under identity with an adjacent subject NP. Notice that it is this natural sequence that enables AGR-S drop under strict adjacency to the subject NP with which it shares phi features (gender, number and person)

Phonetically non-realized Tense-Aspect
 and null realization of AGR-S

We have pointed out in chapter three that the non-future perfective aspect can be phonetically non-realized as

shown in the following example.

(235)

(a) Audù yá ø káryà koófàa
 AGR-S null break door
 3MS NF PERF

((It is) Audu (who) broke the door)

(B) Mákářántaá₁ (cèe) Audù yá ø tàfi t₁
 FOC AGR-S null go
 3MS NF PERF

((It is) school (that) Audu went (to))

Null realization of AGR-S with the non-future perfective aspect is not possible because it will render the complex AGR-S (which contains AGR-S and TNS-ASP) a complete null head, i.e.

[ø ø]
 AGR-S AGR-S ASP

A null head (Null AGR-S) as in (236) cannot assign Nominative Case to the subject NF Audù and cannot also check the nominal features of Audù (i.e. the features person, gender and number).

(236)

(a) *Audù [AGR-S $\emptyset$ AGR-S $\emptyset$ null] káryà koófàa
NP PERF

(b) *Mákárántaá_i (cèe) Audù [AGR-S $\emptyset$ AGR-S $\emptyset$ null] táfí t_i
FOC NF PERF

Bound⁴⁷ Tense-Aspect and null realization of AGR-S

Some tense-aspect markers in Hausa are realized as bound morphemes (enclitics) comprising a single segment. These are -á (non-future perfective) and -à (future). Their occurrence with AGR-S is illustrated in (237).

(237)

(a) Audù yá á kaámà zaákii
AGR-S NF catch lion
3MS PERF

(Audu caught a lion)

(b) Audù yá à kaámà zaákii
AGR-S FUT catch lion
3MS

(Audu will catch a lion)

⁴⁷ Tense and aspect markers in Hausa are realized either as free morphemes or bound morphemes (comprising only a single segment, consonant or vowel, or phonetically unrealized ($\emptyset$)) as shown in (133) chapter three. The single segment tense-aspect must attach to AGR-S at PF.

We shall propose a phonetic argument for the impossibility of null realization of AGR-S with the non-future perfective aspect -á and the future tense -à. The tense-aspect markers -á and -à are enclitics which must attach to AGR-S at PF. Null realization of AGR-S will not allow the realization of convergent PF structures since the tense-aspect enclitics will not be attached to their hosts as shown by the non-convergence of (238a and b).

(238) (a) *Áudù ∅ á⁴⁸ kaámà zaákii
 null NF
 AGR-S PERF

(b) *Áudù ∅ à kaámà zaákii
 null FUT
 AGR-S

Possible cases of null realization of AGR-S (or AGR-S drop)

AGR-S drop is possible with the non-future continuous aspect nàa, and kèe and the non-future habitual aspect kàn as shown in (239), (240) and (241) respectively.

48 (238) is possible only in child's language. Children between the ages of 1 and 2 very often utter sentences such as Áudù ∅ á kaámà zaákii instead of Áudù yá á kaámà zaákii.

(239)

(a)	Audù	yá	nàa	kárántà	jàrífàà
	AGR-S		NF	read	newspaper
	3MS		CONT		

(Audu is reading a newspaper)

(b)	Audù	∅	nàa	kárántà	jàrífàà
	AGR-S	null	NF	read	newspaper
	3MS		CONT		

(Audu is reading a newspaper)

(240)

(a)	Audù	yá	kèe	kárántà	jàrífàà
	AGR-S		NF	read	newspaper
	3MS		CONT		

(Audu (it is) (who) is reading a newspaper)

(b)	Audù	∅	kèe	kárántà	jàrífàà
	AGR-S	null	NF	read	newspaper
	3MS		CONT		

(Audu (it is) (who) is reading a newspaper)

(241)

(a)	Audù	yá	kàn	kárántà	jàrífàà
	AGR-S		NF	read	newspaper
	3MS		HAB		

(Audu does read newspaper)

(b) Audù ø kàn káṙàntà jàṙiídàa
 null NF read newspaper
 AGR-S HAB

(Audu does read newspaper)

I will argue that the possibility of AGR-S drop or having null AGR-S in (239b), (240b) and (241b) can be explained by a phonetic argument as well as a structural syntactic one. The phonetic argument goes as follows. The tense-aspect markers nàa, kèe and kàn are free morphemes which can stand on their own. They are distinguished from bound morpheme tense-aspect markers which comprise only a single segment (consonant or vowel) and which must attach to AGR-S at PF.

There are two aspects of the structural argument. In the first place, nàa, kèe and kàn, unlike the future tense morpheme zaá, occur in the unmarked structural sequence AGR-S - TNS-ASP which allows AGR-S drop at PF. Secondly, recall that we have argued in section 4.3.3 that tense-aspect marker kèe indicates presence of an element in [SPEC,CP].

Now consider example (242) in which the subject NP has moved to [SPEC,CP] (focus-fronting) and the clausal aspect is the non-future continuous aspect kèe.

(242)

Áudù (neé)	yá	kèe	kárántà	jářifidáa
FOC	AGR-S	NF	read	newspaper
	3MS	CONT		

(Audu (it is) (who is reading a newspaper))

Here we may argue that AGR-S drop is possible (thus producing (243) because the subject NP Áudù to which AGR-S is so much related, is not in [SPEC,AGR-S''] but

in [SPEC,CP]. Thus, spec-head agreement no longer holds directly between subject NP Audù and AGR-S yá, and therefore AGR-S can drop easily.

(243) Audù [$\emptyset$ kèe] kárántà jáííídàa
 AGR-S null NF read newspaper
 AGR-S CONT
 3MS

(Audu (it is) (who) is reading a newspaper

The non-future habitual aspect (HAB) is also used in structures containing an element in SPEC,CP but it does not have a form different from kàn. Consider the structure (244) containing a subject NP Audù in [SPEC,CP] and a non-future habitual aspect kàn.

(244)

Audù (neé) yá kàn ká̃ràntà jà̃rífàà
 FOC AGR-S NF read newspaper
 3MS HAB

(Audu (it is) (who) does read the newspaper)

Here also in (244) AGR-S drop is possible for the same reasons that led to its drop in (243). Dropping AGR-S in (244) will produce the structure (245).

(245) Audù [ø kàn] ká̃ràntà jà̃rífàà
 AGR-S null NF read newspaper
 AGR-S HAB

(Audu does read the newspaper)

So far we considered only one case in which the

subject NP in [SPEC,AGR-S'''] moved into [SPEC,CP] triggering aspect marking. We argued there that AGR-S drop is possible because SPEC-head relation between subject NP in [SPEC,AGR-S'''] and AGR-S is weakened with the movement of subject NP to [SPEC,CP]. Let us consider a movement from the object position to [SPEC,CP] as in (246) which will also trigger aspect marking.

(246)

(b) Jàrífàà_i (ceé) Áudù [yá kèe] kárántáawáá t_i
 FOC AGR-S AGR-S NF reading
 3MS CONT

(Newspaper (it is) (that) Audu is reading)

Here also, AGR-S yá can drop, yielding the structure (247).

(247) Jàrífàà_i (ceé) Áudù [ø kèe] kárántáawáá t_i
 FOC AGR-S null NF reading
 AGR-S CONT
 3MS

(Newspaper (it is) (that) Audu is reading)

4.5.2.2 Object agreement drop or null AGR-O

AGR-O, as an integral overt component of the Hausa regular verb, does not seem to have a null realization as shown by the (b) options of the following paired examples.

(248) (a) Áudù [yá á] [sáy í] móótàn
 NF
 AGR-S PERF verbal AGR-O car
 3MS base

(Audu bought a car)

(b) *Áudù [yá á] [sàý ø] moótàn
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-S
 3MS PERF base

(249)

(a) Áudù [yá á] [sàý eé] tà
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-S pronoun object
 3MS PERF base it/her

(Audu bought it/her)

(b) *Áudù [yá á] [sàý ø] tà
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O it/her
 3MS PERF base

(250)

(a) Áudù [yá á] [sàý aá] e
 NF verbal AGR-O zero object
 AGR-S PERF base

(Audu bought something)

(b) *Áudù [yá á] [sàý ø] e
 NF verbal AGR-O zero object
 AGR-S PERF base

(251)

(a) Moótàa_i (ceé) Áudù [yá ø] [sàý aá] t_i
 car FOC AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O
 3MS PERF base

(Car (it is) (that) Audu bought)

(b) *Moótaa_i (ceé) Áudù [yá ø] [sày ø] t_i
 car~ FOC AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O
 3MS PERF base

In the (b) options of (248), (249), (250) and (251), the verbal base say- 'buy' constitutes an incomplete verb without the AGR-O (grade) component of the verb, hence the ill-formedness of all the (b) options. However, AGR-O seems to be realized as null with some verbs such as háu (ascend/mount), kái (deliver) and bíyaa (pay). We assume a null realization of AGR-O with these verbs because one cannot point out precisely what is representing overt AGR-O in these verbs. Consider the following examples in which háu seems to occur without overt AGR-O.

(252)

(a) Áudù [yá á] [háu ø] doókii
 AGR-O NF verbal AGR-O noun object
 3MS PERF base horse

(Audu mounted a horse)

(b) Áudù [yá á] [háu ø] shí
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O pronoun object
 3MS PERF base it/him

(Audu mounted it/him)

(c) Áudù [yá á] [háu ø] e
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O zero object
 3MS PERF base
 (Áudu mounted something)

(d) Doókii_i (neé) Áudù [yá ø] [háu ø] t_i
 horse FOC AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O trace
 3MS PERF base
 (Horse (it is) (that) Áudu mounted)

A descriptive generalization will be that the null realization of AGR-O, associated with verbs such as háu, kái and bíyaá might be an indicator of irregularity which marks every verb without overt AGR-O as irregular verb. Regular verbs on the other hand, are distinguished by having overtly realized AGR-O. For example, the regular transitive verbal base kaam- 'catch' is realized as kaámà or kaámaà; that is to say with overt AGR-O -à or -àa, depending on whether the verb is followed directly by a noun object (in which case it requires AGR-O -à) or by either zero object, pronoun object, trace of an NP object or dative phrase (in which case it requires AGR-O -àa). This is

illustrated by the following examples.

(253)

(a) Audù [yá á] [kaám à] kifif
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O noun object
 3MS PERF base fish
 (Audu caught a fish)

(b) Audù [yá á] [kaám àa] shí
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O pronoun object
 3MS PERF base it/him
 (Audu caught it/him)

(c) Audù [yá á] [kaám àa] e
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O zero object
 3MS PERF base
 (Audu caught something)

(d) Kiffif_i (nèe) Audù [yá ó] [kaám àa] t_i
 fish FOC AGR-S NF verbal AGR-O
 3MS PERF base
 (Fish (it is) (that) Audu caught)

(e) Audù [yá á] [kaám àa] [wà Alf] kifif
 AGR-S NF verbal AGR-S dative noun
 3MS PERF base phrase object fish
 fish
 (Audu caught a fish for Ali)

Irregular verbs on the other hand, generally do not require overt AGR-O in the determination of their agreement features. Agreement features of irregular verbs seem to be 'freely' determined, indicating that an irregular verb makes no formal distinction (marked morphologically by AGR-O) between agreement with a following noun object on one hand, and agreement with all other elements (i.e. pronoun object, zero object, trace of moved NP and dative phrase) that follow the verb on the other hand.

4.5 Summary

In this chapter we discussed the nature and form of agreement relations obtaining in the articulated clause structure of Hausa, starting with an attempt at defining the notion of 'agreement' in syntax. The chapter discusses the role played by functional categories in the determination of agreement relations and in particular the nature of T-raising and V-raising in Hausa. The chapter identifies major agreement relations in the articulated clause structure of Hausa. They include verbal base-grade (or AGR-O) relation, head-complement

relation and chain-coindexing relation. The chapter also draws attention to the complex agreement relations obtaining in the verbal component of the articulated clause structure and specifies in vivid details the feature composition of grade forms. The grade (or AGR-O) is a functional element that controls agreement relations in the verbal component of the articulated clause structure. The chapter further discusses the important issue of null subject - null object hypothesis in Hausa, arguing for a morphosyntactic explanation of null subject and null object in Hausa. In particular, the chapter discusses possible cases of null realization of AGR-S (or AGR-S drop) and cases in which it is impossible to occur. The chapter also attempted an explanation of the phenomenon of null realization of AGR-O (or AGR-O)drop). On the whole, the chapter favours an agreement-oriented approach to the issue of determination of agreement relations in the articulated clause structure of Hausa. The approach of the chapter is motivated and supported by the rich morphology of Hausa.

CHAPTER FIVE

ASPECTS OF MOVEMENT AND THE AGREEMENT ISSUE IN HAUSA CLAUSE STRUCTURE

5.0 Preliminaries

One of the goals of the present study is to show how agreement relations in the clause affect movement facts. In the introductory chapter (chapter one), we have shown the inadequacy of those movement facts of Hausa which do not take into cognizance the various agreement relations obtaining in the clause. In the present chapter, we shall propose an alternative agreement-oriented approach to movement in the clause structure of Hausa. The new approach to movement takes into account agreement relations in the clause which are assumed to play crucial roles in every analysis of the clause. In particular, the present study argues that the basic assumptions of the two conditions on movement, namely the subjacency condition and the Empty Category Principle (ECP) as in standard Government-Binding framework are insufficient in respect of movement in Hausa. Alternatively, distance of movement (subjacency) and proper government of traces (ECP) are also accounted

for by appropriate agreement relations obtaining in the clause.

5.1 Movement Theory in Universal Grammar: An Overview

Standard approach to movement theory in Universal Grammar (UG) as in Chomsky (1981, 1986) posits a major transformational operation, the rule Move Alpha ($\text{Move } \alpha$). $\text{Move } \alpha$ is the only single movement rule in the grammar that has subsumed all other specific transformations of the previous models of transformational grammar. The rule $\text{Move } \alpha$ has the effect of 'moving anything anywhere'.

The basic assumption of movement theory is that any part of the sentence could be moved anywhere. However, operation $\text{Move } -\alpha$ is not without a parameter. Languages vary in respect of (i) nature of alpha, (ii) type of position alpha may move to, and (iii) the nodes which bound movement.

The standard approach to movement also assumes

levels of representation as pointed out in section 1.3.2.

Chomsky (1982:55) observes that the following properties hold between a moved element and its trace after Move α has applied.

(254)

- (a) The trace is properly governed, i.e. it is subject to the Empty Category Principle (ECP).
- (b) The antecedent of the trace is not in a theta position.
- (c) The antecedent-trace relation satisfies the subjacency condition.

Chomsky (1986b:4) identifies two types of movement.

(255)

- (a) Substitution: includes NP movement, head movement, clitic movement, adjunct movement. This type of movement is highly local.

- (b) Adjunction: principally the A'-movement of arguments and is subject to weaker locality condition.

Hoekstra (1991) identifies two tasks of movement theory: (i) to provide a principled theory of the strong locality which is imposed on most instances of movement, (ii) to provide a principled basis for the escape from strict locality which is available for A'-movement of arguments. In addition, movement theory must account for 'residual locality effects' such as the subjacency condition, the ECP, etc, which are found in A'-movement of arguments (or wh-argument movement).

5.2 Aspects of movement

The present study discusses three important aspects of movement theory: distance of movement: How far can a moved element go? In the Principles and Parameters framework, distance of movement is handled by the bounding theory (subjacency) module. In Chomsky (1981), bounding theory entails that movement across more than one bounding node leads to subjacency violation resulting in ill-formed structures. In Chomsky (1986), every maximal projection or phrasal category is a barrier to movement and crossing a barrier leads to subjacency

violation. The present study will argue that contrary to standard position, distance of movement must be an agreement issue in Hausa. Proper government of traces: The trace of a moved element must be properly governed in the sense of Chomsky (1981) and refinements in Chomsky (1986). In Principles and Parameters framework, proper government of traces is handled by the Empty Category Principle (ECP) module. The present study will argue that proper government of traces in Hausa is also accounted for by an agreement relation. Resumptive strategy: The standard position in the Principles and Parameters framework is that subjacency and ECP violations can be circumvented using appropriate resumptive strategies such as the resumptive pronoun strategy (Chomsky (1981) or the adjunction method (Chomsky 1986). The present study will argue that in Hausa, resumptive strategy reduces to issue of agreement relation. Overall, in the present chapter (sections 5.3 and 5.4), we shall argue, among other things, that an idiosyncrasy of Hausa embodied in the null subject-null object hypothesis renders both standard accounts of the subjacency condition and the ECP insufficient. The resumptive pronoun strategy is also reduced to what

we shall refer to as 'grade form substitution' in the present study.

5.3 Agreement-oriented approach to movement: An Outline

In this section, I will examine the basic assumptions and operation of the proposed agreement-oriented approach to movement issue in Hausa.

5.3.1 Basic Assumptions

The agreement-oriented approach to movement issue in Hausa, proposed in the present study, is based on the following assumptions.

- (256) (a) Elements in the clause structure stand in various forms of agreement relations.⁴⁹
- (b) Movement in the clause causes redefining of relations; it may also bring about new relations. For example, verb-object agreement relation between a full verb and a noun object is redefined as one between full verb and trace as a result of movement. A new temporal-cum-aspectual relationship is also created when [SPEC, CP] contains an element. Notice that the element in [SPEC, CP] gets to that position

49 The various forms of agreement relations obtaining in the clause structure of Hausa have been discussed in chapter four.

via a movement operation.

(c) Agreement relations amongst elements must be maintained at all levels of representation. That is to say, 'free elements', must not occur at any level of representation.

(d) A clause structure fails to converge when one or more agreement relations are not observed.

5.3.2 Outline

An agreement-oriented approach to movement assumes that at every level of representation, all agreement relations between elements must be fully represented, the basic agreement relations being the following.

- (257) (a) Subject agreement relation
 (b) Object agreement relation
 (c) Verbal base - grade agreement relation

(257b and c) are agreement relations in the verbal component of the clause. (257a) is the agreement relation obtaining in the subject area of the clause. Consider the d-structure (258) which exhibits all the basic agreement relations enumerated in (257).

(258)	Áudù	yá	á	kaám	a	zaákii
	subject	AGR-S	NF	verbal	AGR-O	noun object
	NP	3MS	PERF	base	1C	
	3MS			catch		lion

'(Audu had caught a lion)

In (258), subject agreement relation obtains between Áudù (subject NP) and the subject agreement element (AGR-S) yá. The nature of the agreement relation is such that they share the phi-features person, gender and number: each represents 3rd person, masculine, singular. (The details of this agreement relation is given in chapter 4). Verbal base - grade agreement relation between verbal base kaám- and object agreement element (AGR-O) -à is satisfied in consonance with the discussion of same in chapter 4. So also the object agreement relation between the full verb kaámà and the noun object zaákii. The noun object zaákii receives Accusative Case under spec-head agreement relation. Details of this kind of agreement relation had also been given in chapter 4. Temporal-cum-Aspectual agreement also holds in (258) because the non-future perfective aspect -á is one of the two aspects (the other being the non-future continuative aspect -nàa) allowed in d-

structures or structures where no movement had taken place. Thus, (258) is a convergent d-structure which satisfies the basic assumptions of an agreement-oriented account of clause structures enumerated in (256).

Movement of elements in d-structure leads to re-defining of relations as well as positing new ones in the resultant s-structure. New relations are usually (i) the chain-coindexing agreement relations between an antecedent (moved element) and its trace, (ii) the aspectual agreement relation which specifically involves change in aspect due to the presence of an element in [SPEC,CP] as a result of an A'-movement into that position. (iii) changes in object agreement relation between the full verb and the trace of an antecedent. That is to say, full verb relates to NP object differently from the trace of the NP object. Consider as s-structure representation (259) of the sentence Záki Audù yá kaámàa (lion (it is) that Audu had caught).

(259)

[	zaákii _i]	Audù	yá	∅	kaám	-àa	t _i
SPEC		subject	AGR-S	NF	verbal	AGR-O	trace
CP	lion	NP	[3MS]	PERF	base	1A	
		[3MS]			catch		

(Lion (it is) (that) Audu had caught)

In the verbal component of (259) above, verbal base-grade agreement relation between the verbal and kaám- and the object agreement element (AGR-O) -àa is satisfied and so also object agreement relation between full verb kaámàa and the trace t of the antecedent zaákii. Object agreement relation which involves Accusative Case assignment to object noun is captured morphologically by AGR-O. Here, AGR-O -àa indicates that what is in the object position is actually the trace t of the antecedent object zaákii. A new temporal-cum-aspectual agreement relation is marked by the non-future perfective 'relative' aspect marker ∅, indicating movement into [SPEC,CP]. Subject agreement relation between the subject NP Audù and the subject agreement element (AGR-S) yá is also observed. It involves sharing of phi-features person, number and gender, between the subject

NP and the subject agreement element (AGR-S). Thus, (259) is a convergent s-structure which satisfies the basic assumptions of the proposed agreement-oriented account of movement enumerated in (256). Agreement relations in Hausa are morphologically marked and the morphemes (functional elements) that server as agreement markers (e.g. AGR-S, AGR-O, tense, aspect) contain relevant properties that allow agreement relations between elements either in the form of feature identification or feature sharing. Agreeing elements also stand in configurations that represent agreement relations. These configurations are defined in X-bar theoretic terms as pointed out in chapter 4.

5.4 Agreement-oriented approach to movement facts of Hausa

5.4.1 Subjacency operation in Hausa

In chapter one I presented Tuller's (1986) account of the operation of the subjacency condition in Hausa, including Tuller's major conclusions, pointing out that

the conclusions could not be quite correct since agreement relations in the clause were not considered. In this section, I will show the superiority of an agreement-oriented approach in capturing movement facts of Hausa as opposed to Tuller's approach to the same issue. In effect, the present study argues that standard subjacency account as in Tuller (1986) is inadequate in determining movement facts of Hausa. It will be shown below that Tuller's null subject - null object hypothesis, relative aspect marking and surface resumptive strategy which are said to have direct relevance to subjacency operation, are indeed agreement issues.

Relativization out of subjacency islands
and the null subject-null object hypothesis

Movement out of subjacency islands is generally excluded. Tuller (1986:83) argues that relativization out of a subjacency island is possible: "since Hausa allows both null subject and null object, we should expect that both subjects and objects should be available for relativization out of subjacency

islands." That is to say, when an object or a subject NP moves out of a subjacency island via relativization, the impact is not felt since Hausa independently allows null subjects and objects. Tuller gives example (260) to illustrate the possibility of relativization out of an embedded question clause which is a subjacency island.

(260) (a) líttáafi-n da_i [káǎ sán
S

book-the which 2MS know
NF PERF

[_{S'} waa_i [_S t_i yáǎ rúbùutaá t_i]]]
who

who 3MS write
NF PERF

(The book which you know who wrote (it))

(b) Mùtúmi-n dà_i [_S káǎ sán

man-the who 2MS know
NF PERF

[_{S'} meè_j [_S t_i yáǎ rúbùutaá t_j]]]

what 3MS write
NF PERF

(The man who you know what he wrote)

Tuller excludes sentences involving wh-interrogation out of subjacency islands as shown in (261) because according to her, the use of the gap strategy or null subject-null object hypothesis is exclusive to relativization.

(261) (a) *wàné líttaáfii_j káø sán

which book 2MS know
NF PERF

[_{S'} wai_i [_S t_i yáø ãúbùutaá t_j]]

who 3MS write
NF PERF

(Which book do you know who wrote)

(b) *wàné mùtum_j káø sán

which man 2MS know
NF PERF

[_{S'} meè_i [_S t_j yáø ãúbùutaá t_i]]

what 3MS write
NF PERF

(Which man do you know what he wrote)

The exclusion of (261) by Tuller might not be quite correct. I assume that Tuller's account fails to capture the real motivation of the gap strategy which is governed by agreement factors that allow null subjects and null objects in the language. We would like to propose that a descriptive generalization should have been that any movement out of subject or object position of a subjacency island must not lead to subjacency violation since Hausa independently allows null subject and null object. This observation should be correct in view of the fact that native speakers judgement declares (261a and b) quite acceptable sentences. Thus, we conclude that since the null subject and null object hypothesis, which is essentially an agreement phenomena (see 4.4.2.1), had rendered standard subjacency account incapable of excluding sentences (260) and (261), then the superior agreement-oriented account of movement facts of Hausa should be favoured.

Relativization out of indirect object
and the resumptive pronoun strategy

The indirect NP object in Hausa is introduced by an introducer wà (approximately 'for) and the complex [wa NP] is referred to as dative phrase.

subjacency violation in (262) can be saved if a resumptive pronoun (*másù*) appears in place of gap (t_i) as in (263).

(263) Taáboóbbí-*n* [dà₁ . Alí yá ø sán mùtúmi-*n*
 cigarette-the RC which Alí 3MS NF know man-the
 tts PERF

[dà_j e_j zâi yíi [màsù]₁⁵⁰ kwaálif]]
 RC who will do for them packets

(The cigarettes which Alí knew the man who will make packets for them)

But an alternative agreement-oriented account proposed in this chapter, and which captures the morphosyntax of Hausa, finds (262) quite acceptable and argues that the use of [*màsù*] (or what Tuller refers to as resumptive pronoun) in (263) is simply to avoid an apparent representational vagueness cause by

50 We would like to observe that [*màsù*] is not a single pronoun but a dative phrase substituting for another dative phrase, i.e. [wa t].

the dative phrase [wà t]. The representational vagueness follows from the fact that superficially, it cannot be ascertained whether wà takes t or kwaálif as a following object. The vagueness is however cleared if wà appears with long vowel as wàa, indicating that it must be followed by t (trace) and not kwaálif (noun). The wà/wàa distinction which is responsible for the vagueness is expressed as follows. The introducer dative and its complement NP in a dative phrase stand in an agreement relation: the introducer assigns a Dative Case to the NP. The introducer comprises a stem w-⁵¹ and a vowel -a (short) or -aa (long). The introducer stem w- takes a short vowel -a if followed by a lexical noun or anaphor complement and long vowel -aa if followed by the trace of the NP complement as shown below.

51 Notice that the introducer stem w- changes to m- if the following object is pronoun (cf. [wà taáboóbif] v. [má sù]). The introducer stem m- must always take a short vowel form -a to accommodate a following object pronoun. Notice also that there is no instance when m- appears with a long vowel i.e. *maa in order to accommodate a trace t. Thus, the dative structure *[maa t] does not occur in the language.

- (264) (a) wà taáboóbbif
noun
- (b) wà kânsà
anaphor
- (c) wàa t
trace

In the light of this descriptive generalization, we revisit (262) above. Before the movement of taáboóbbif, the noun object of wà, (262) is as (265).

(265) Alí yá á sán mùtúmi-n

(Ali knew the man

[_{S'} dà_i t_i zâi yí [wà taáboóbbif] kwaálíí]

who will make for the cigarettes packet)

After the relativization of taáboóbbif, (265) becomes (266).

(266) Taáboóbi-n [_{S'}RC dáj Alí yá ø sán mutúmi-n

(The cigarettes (that) Ali knew the man

[_{S'}RC dáj t_izai yi [wàa t_j] kwaálií]]

who will make for packets)

(266) is admissible contrary to Tuller's judgement in (262). The well-formedness of (266) follows from the fact that the introducer stem w- assumes a long vowel form (wàa) since it is followed by the trace of the indirect object taáboóbií. However, a representational vagueness is bound to arise if the introducer takes a short vowel form, thereby appearing as wà as in Tuller's (262). Superficially, the introducer wà will appear to have taken kwaálií as its noun complement as shown in the partial structure (267).

(267) [wà kwaálií]

The situation in (267) is possible considering the fact that wà and kwaálií are superficially adjacent to one another and more especially if the introducer does not take the

appropriate long vowel to indicate the presence of the trace of its moved complement. The indepth morpho-syntactic account presented above has not been captured in Tuller's analysis. Her account which is wholly subjacency simply assumes that the movement of the indirect object NP taáboóbií had crossed more than one bounding node and must therefore be seen to have violated the subjacency condition. The so called resumptive pronoun strategy adopted by Tuller to resume (262) is also not a true case of resumptive pronoun strategy since, as we have pointed out earlier (see footnote 50), másù is not a pronoun but a dative phrase. To avoid an attendant vagueness, the dative phrase [wàa t] is replaced with an appropriate equivalent dative phrase [má sù], comprising an introducer ma and an indirect object pronoun su. We conclude therefore that Tuller's attempt to use subjacency argument wholly to block relativization of indirect object is inconsistent with the morphosyntactic facts of Hausa.

Relativization of human direct object (i.e. yaárfínyà 'girl')

(269) •Yáarfínyà-ṛ [dà_j múkà gá mùtúmi-n
 S' RC |
 girl-the who 1PL NF PERF see man-the

[dà_i e_i zâi àuraá e_j]
 S' RC |
 RC who will marry

(The girls who we saw the man who will marry)

Tuller argues that (269) can however be 'saved' by a resumptive pronoun strategy as in (270)

(270) Yaárfínyà-ṛ [dà mú kà gá mùtúmi-n
 girl-the S' RC who 1PL NF PERF see man-the

[dà_j e_j zâi àureé tà]
 S' RC |
 RC who will marry her

(The girl who we saw the man who will marry her)

Tuller's semantic distinction between the relativization of human and non-human direct object as in (268) and (269) above is counter-intuitive since native speakers'

judgement declares (269) well-formed. The issue is that in both (268) and (269), an element has moved out of a subadjacency island via relativization. Relativization as a process should apply generally irrespective of whether a human direct object or non-human direct object is involved. This seems to be the case in Hausa where it is the relativizing verb that matters and not the relativized element. The nature of the evidence is such that relativizing verbs in Hausa are divided into two: those that cause representational vagueness and those that do not.

Relativizing verbs operating grades 2 and 5 cause representational vagueness, while those operating grades 1,4, and 6 do not. Grade 2 and 5 verbs⁵²

52 Grade 2 and 5 operating verbs use B-form to accommodate a pronominal object, C-form to accommodate a noun object and D-form to accommodate a following dative phrase. This distinction in grade forms had been pointed out in chapter one and is illustrated as follows:

<u>Grade</u>	<u>A-form</u>	<u>B-form</u>	<u>C-form</u>	<u>D-form</u>
2	-aa	-ee	-i	-aa
5	-aã	-aã	-aã	-aã

(d) Jírgí-_n dà mú kà gá òàràayí-_n
 [_{S'} dà e sú kà kaáyá̃r shí]
 N

(The train which we saw the robbers that
 derail it).

The selection of B-form as a substitute for the A-form is not arbitrary. It is agreement governed. Notice that B-form shares with A-form the features [+Long, -Dative] which it does not share with C- and D-forms. It should also be pointed out that the requirement for a following pronoun object as substitute for the vague null object e was misunderstood by Tuller to mean having a resumptive pronoun in place of gap!

Relativizing verbs operating grades 1,4 and 6 on the other hand do not cause any representational vagueness since in the case of these verbs, a single grade form (B-form) is used for trace, zero object and pronoun object. The distribution of the grade forms for grades 1,4 and 6 as pointed out in chapter one is as follows.

(273)

<u>Grade</u>	<u>A-form</u>	<u>B-form</u>	<u>C-form</u>	<u>D-form</u>
1	-aa	-aa	-a	-aa
4	-ee	-ee	-e	-ee
6	-oo	-oo	-oo	-oo

Grade form substitution is not possible with grades 1,4, and 6 relativizing verbs since their B-forms do not agree with A-, C- and D-forms in certain features. For example, A-forms of grades 1,4, and 6 carry the feature [-Transitive] which is not shared with B-form. B-form carries the feature [+Transitive]. C-forms of grades 1,4 and 6 carry the feature [-Long] which is not shared with B-form. B-form is [+Long]. D-forms of grades 1,4, and 6 carry the feature [+Dative] which is not shared with B-form. B-form is [-Dative]. Since no feature agreement can be established between B-forms and other grade forms (A-, C- and D-forms) to warrant grade form substitution, then the B-forms of grades 1,4, and 6 must not trigger any representational vagueness, and indeed they do not as shown by the well-formedness of example (274).

(274) (a) Líttaáfi-n dà_j ká ø sán mùtúmi-n
 book-the that 2MS NF know man-the
 PERF

[dà_i e_i yá ø rúbùutaá e_j]
 S' RC IB
 who 3MS NF write
 PERF

(The book that you know the man who wrote)

(b) Kitsò-n dà mú kà gá màatá-ř
 hair-do that 1PL NF see woman-the
 the PERF

[dà e tá ø kuúshèe e]
 S' RC 4B
 that 3FS NF find fault
 PERF with

(The hair-do that we saw the woman who finds
 fault with)

(c) Rigímà-ř dà mú kà gá dillaáli-n
 RC
 trouble- that 3PL NF see broker-the
 the PERF

[dà e yá ø tárkoó e]
 S' 6B
 that 3MS NF invite
 PERF

(The trouble that we saw the broker who invited)

A descriptive generalization can now be made regarding direct object (human or non-human) relativization out of a subadjacency island: If relativizing verb operates A-form of grade 2 or 5, representational vagueness is experienced and a substitution with B-form of the same grade instantly clears the structure. Notice that this substitution, referred to here as grade form substitution, is not equivalent to resumptive pronoun strategy. If relativizing verb operates grades 1,4, and 6, no vagueness arises and so grade form substitution is not required.

5.4.1.1 Wh- interrogation in Hausa

One of the major typological divisions of question types in Hausa is the wh-question whose main syntactic characteristic is the conspicuous presence of an interrogative word in an interrogative clause. The interrogative word, commonly referred to as wh-phrase in English, appears in Hausa in various forms such as mèè (what), wàa (who), yaàyàa (how), ináa (where), yàushè (when), dón mèè (for what, why). An interrogative

A wh-question clause in Hausa may contain two wh-phrases as in the sentence wàa yá sáyóó mèe (who bought what?) whose structure is (277).

(277) [CP Spec [wàa yá sáyóó mèe]]
 CP who 3MS buy^{6C} what
 NF
 PERF

One of the two wh-phrases must move to Spec,CP and by Superiority Condition⁵⁴ (Chomsky 1973:246), wàa moves to Spec,CP as shown in (278).

(278) [CP waa₁ [t₁ yá sáyóó mèe]]
 CP ↑] 6C
 who 3MS buy what
 NF
 PERF

Wh-interrogation out of subjacency islands

Tuller (1986:80), commenting on the asymmetry regarding facts of extraction out of subjacency islands, argues that while elements may be extracted by wh-interrogation out of wh islands,

⁵⁴ Chomsky (1973:246) defines Superiority as follows:

... the category A is "superior" to the category B in the phrase marker if every major category dominating A dominates B as well but not conversely.

Haegemann (1991:438) points out that Superiority is a structural notion defined in terms of c-

they may not be extracted by *wh*-interrogation out of *wh*-islands. Tuller's position is illustrated as follows.

- (279) (a) *Wàné lfttáafi_i káø sán
 which book 2MS know
 NF
 PERF
- [CP wàa_i e_i yáø rúbùtaá_{IB} e_j]
 who 3MS write
 NF
 PERF

(Which book do you know who wrote)

- (b) *Wàné mùtùm_j káø sán
 which man 2MS know
 NF
 PERF
- [CP mée_i e_j yáø rúbùtaá_{IB} e_i]
 what 3MS write
 NF
 PERF

(Which man do you know what he wrote?)

command and that in structures, subjects are consequently superior to objects.

(c) *Wáne mùtum_j káø báa ni litáafi-n

which man 2MS give me book-the
NF
PERF

[dá_i e_j yáø rúbuútaá e]
CP IB

that 3MS write
NF
PERF

(Which man did you give me the book that wrote?)

(d) * [wáa_i céewáa e_i yáá gá sárkíi]
CP

who saying that 3MS see king
NF
PERF

yáø báa ni màamáakíi?
3MS give me surprise
NF
PERF

(Who, saying that (he) saw the king, surprised me?)

Tuller did not say why the sentences in (279) are excluded but simply claims that relativization has some property which enables it (relativization) to violate

subjacency and this property is not available to wh-interrogation. The property is indeed the use of resumptive pronoun or gap strategy (independently sanctioned by Hausa) to circumvent subjacency. I will argue that Tuller's conclusion on wh interrogation out of subjacency islands is not entirely correct since constructions involving wh interrogation out of subjacency islands, including all of (279a-c) are perfectly acceptable, indicating that they too must have utilized the null subject and null object provision (or the gap strategy) for circumventing subjacency violation. Or in our own terms, they must have contained verbs that do not produce representational vagueness as a result of moving their objects.

A major argument in support of why wh-interrogation out of wh islands is possible in Hausa follows from the fact that both relativization and wh-interrogation are A'-movements which are well motivated and with clear conceptual necessity. Relativization and wh-interrogation are A'-movements because they involve movement into SPEC, a non-argument or A'-position. Both movements are also well motivated and conceptually necessary in that

relativization is necessary in the formation of relative clauses and so also wh interrogation in the formation of interrogative or question clauses.

Another argument is the realization that the behaviour of the Hausa verb does not change in respect of either relativization or wh- interrogation. That is to say, the verb takes an appropriate grade form to mark the presence of the trace of its moved direct object, whether such movement is via relativization or wh-interrogation. Extending our earlier morpho-syntactic argument to (279), we find that the verb involved is rúbùutaá, a grade 1 verb. The fact that grade 1 operating verbs use same grade forms (i.e. aa) for a following trace, a zero object and a pronoun object, makes them essentially protected from the representational vagueness triggered by verbs that do not have such sameness in grade form for trace, zero object and object pronoun. This explains the acceptability of (279) (a), (b) and (c). On the other hand, (279d) is excluded for a different reason altogether. Consider the following analysis. A typical question clause such as wàa yá gá sárkíí (who saw the king), cannot serve as sentential subject as shown in (280).

(280)

•[wàa yáǎ gá sárkif] yáá báa ni màamákii
 CP
 who 3MS see king 3MS give me surprise
 NF NF
 PERF PERF

(Who saw the king surprise you?)

However, with an overt complementizer such as cêwáá introducing the question clause (i.e. cêwáa wàa yá gá sárkii), it can serve as sentential subject as shown in (281).

(281) [cêwáa wàa yáǎ gá sárkif] yáá báa ni màamákii

(That who saw the king, surprised me)

At LF, wàa (who) has to move to Spec, CP and its trace in [Spec, AGR-S''] is not properly governed because overt complementizer cêwáa (that) blocks antecedent government of t_i by wàa as illustrated by (282).

(282) * [CP Spec wàa_i [C cêewáa] [AGR-S t_i yáó gá sárkíi]]
 yáá baa ní màamáakii

(Who that saw the king surprised me?)

Thus, (279d) or (282) is an ECP violation and not a subjacency violation. Further discussion of ECP violation follows in 5.4.2.

Wh- interrogation of indirect object

Wh- interrogation of an indirect object is possible in a similar fashion argued for the possibility of relativization of same as discussed above. Consider the following example.

(283) Wàné mánòomí Alí yáó sán
 which farmer Ali 3MS know

mákkèerí- n dà zái kéeráa [wáa t] fártányàa?
 blacksmith- who will manu- for hoe
 the facture

(Which farmer Ali knew the blacksmith who will manufacture a hoe for?)

In (283), the wh- phrase wàné mánòò mfi (which farmer) is an indirect object and it gets to the matrix [Spec, CP] via wh- interrogation from the dative phrase containing it. (283) would have been a subjacency violation since the wh- phrase wàné mánòòmfi had crossed more than one bounding node. Nevertheless, (283) is well-formed considering the morphosyntactic facts of Hausa. That is to say, the long movement of the indirect object wàné mánòòmfi has no effect on the well-formedness of (283). Further more, the trace t_1 of wàné mánòòmfi is properly licenced by the introducer waa. In addition, there is a provision for substituting the dative phrase [waa t] with an equivalent dative phrase [màsà], which comprises an introducer ma and a pronoun object sa. On the whole, morphosyntactic facts of Hausa have shown that wh- interrogation of an indirect object, like the relativization of same, is possible.

5.4.2 ECP operation in Hausa

In the previous section we discussed subjacency operation in Hausa. We pointed out that Tuller's (1986) account of subjacency operation in Hausa has overlooked the important role played by agreement relations obtaining

in Hausa clause structure, thereby rendering findings in respect of distance of movement (subjacency) less accurate. We conclude that the effect of distance of movement in respect of Hausa is essentially an issue related to agreement than just related to bounding nodes or barriers in the standard sense. In this section, I will discuss ECP operation in Hausa, pointing out that here also, the phenomenon involved i.e. proper government of traces, is indeed an agreement issue in Hausa contrary to Tuller's (1986) position on same. Two issues are particularly crucial in respect of ECP operation in Hausa. The first involves lexical government and how it is represented in Hausa. The second is antecedent government which fails to hold in a configuration of that - trace. Hausa violates the that - trace filter owing to an idiosyncrasy which independently allows null subject in the language.

5.4.2.1 Lexical Government

One form of proper government is lexical government which is defined in Lasnik and Uriagereka (1988:94) as follows.

(284) A head lexically governs its complement

In standard Principle and Parameters framework, lexical government translates into an adjacency requirement between a lexical head and the complement it governs.⁵⁵

55 English provides standard adjacency requirement for lexical government as shown by the following examples.

i) Peter killed [the dog]
 V NP

ii) Peter killed [him]
 V pronoun

iii) [what]_i did Peter kill t_i
 V

In (i), the verb kill, a lexical head, is followed directly by its noun object the dog. In (ii) and (iii), the verb kill is followed directly by its pronoun object him and the trace t of its direct object what. A partial structure (iv) captures the relationship between kill and the elements in (i), (ii) and (iii) that follow it.

The verb kill c-commands the dog, him and t and also stands in sisterhood relationship with them, thereby satisfying the two conditions for adjacency. We

In Hausa, there are overt as well as null complements. Overt complements are the direct noun object and direct pronoun object. Null complements are the zero object and the trace of direct noun object. All complements are lexically governed. An idiosyncrasy of Hausa is that in addition to the adjacency requirement for lexical government, agreement relation between a head and a following complement must also be considered. The Morphology of the verb determines the form of complement (null or overt) that follows it as shown in the following examples.

(285)

(a)	wàa _i	t _i	yáø	gàyyàc _i 2C	Audù	
	who		3MS NF PERF	invite	Audu	direct noun object

(Who invited Audu?)

conclude that in the examples above, kill lexically governs the dog, him and t under adjacency.

(b) wàa_i Áudù yáø gàyyata_{2A} t_i
 who Audu 3MS invite trace
 NF
 PERF

(Who did Audu invite?)

(c) Gwámnà yáá gàyyàc_{2B}èé sù
 governor 3MS invite them
 NF
 PERF

((The) governor invited them)

Grade 2 verbal base gayyat- (invite) obligatory occurs with grade forms -aa (2A), -ee (2B) and -i (2C) for trace, direct object pronoun and direct NP object respectively. Notice that co-occurrence relationship between the verb (indicated by its grade form) and a following syntactic environment even though it satisfies adjacency requirement for lexical government, is nonetheless strictly an agreement relationship. A breach in the agreement relation produces unacceptable sentences as in (286).

(286) *wàa_i t_i yá ø gàyyàc_{2B}èé Áudù
 noun object

which determine agreement relation with a following syntactic environment (noun object, pronoun object, zero object, trace) had been exhaustively discussed in chapter four. Examples in (286) clearly show that in Hausa, lexical government cannot be an entirely adjacency requirement between a head and its complement. In Hausa, lexical government, and indeed all relations in the clause, involve agreement, and this observation further supports the claim of the present study that convergence (or well-formedness) is dependent upon full realization of all basic agreement relations in the clause.

5.4.2.2 Antecedent Government 'That'-trace effect

An embedded wh- question clause may contain an overt complementizer that in composition (287a). The complementizer may be optionally absent with movement from a non-subject position in the embedded question clause as shown in (287b).

(287) (a) Who₁ do you think that [Peter saw t₁]?
 (b) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]?
 (c) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (d) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (e) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (f) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (g) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (h) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (i) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (j) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (k) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (l) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (m) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (n) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (o) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (p) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (q) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (r) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (s) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (t) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (u) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (v) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (w) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (x) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (y) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]
 (z) Who₁ do you think [Peter saw t₁]

(b) Who_i do you think [Peter saw t_i]?

However, it must be obligatorily absent with movement from the subject position. The last requirement, according to Chomsky (1981) amounts to the that - trace filter which excludes the sequence that-t in non-pro-drop languages and whose violation in these languages results in unacceptable structures as indicated by (288).

(288) *Who_i do you think that t_i left?

The sequence that t according to Chomsky (1986), is ruled out by the Empty Category Principle (ECP) for the following reasons.

- (289) (a) That cannot assign Case to t
 (b) t must be properly governed
 (c) t is not lexically governed by a verb because it is not in an object position.

That-t filter

Tuller (1986) observes that Hausa freely allows extraction of subject out of a clause headed by overt

complementizer in apparent violation of that-t filter. This observation is justified by an example such as (290).

(290) wàa_i kákeè tsàmmaánìi

who 2MS think
NF
PERF

[céewáa t_i yaá tàfi Kánòo]
CP

that 3MS go Kano
NF
PERF

(Who do you think that went to Kano)

I explain (290) as follows. In (290), the trace t of wàa is neither lexically governed by the verb tsàmmaánìi (think) nor antecedent governed by wàa. Antecedent government is blocked by the overt complementizer ceewáa. Thus, in (290), a that-t configuration i.e. céewáa-t is created, rendering (290) an ECP violation. Now, a crucial question is how to account for the grammaticality of (290) despite an obvious ECP violation. It should be emphasized that native judgment declares (290) quite grammatical. Tuller (1986:159), commenting on (290),

remarks that "it has been argued that surface ECP violations in Hausa are the result of a general s-structure resumptive pronoun strategy which entails that the gap of that-t violations is a (null) pronoun rather than a trace and thus is not subject to the ECP." This proposal is untenable because the trace t in (290) is a clear trace which cannot be made a 'null pronoun' in order to avoid an ECP violation. In (290), wàa 'who' actually moved to matrix [SPEC,CP] leaving behind a trace in the subject position of the embedded clause. An alternative agreement-oriented account proposed in the present study will, however, handle (290), capturing both native intuition and explaining why cêwaa t is not an ECP violation. Our argument is as follows. Consider the structure (291). In this structure, the trace t of wàa occupies the subject position (or [SPEC,AGR-S''']) of the embedded clause.

(291)

Recall that in chapter four (4.2.1), we have established that spec-head agreement relation obtains between an element in [SPEC,AGR-S''] and the subject agreement element AGR-S. We argued there that this spec-head agreement relation involves sharing of the phi-features

person, gender and number between the element in [SPEC,AGR-S''] and the subject element AGR-S. We also pointed out an idiosyncrasy of Hausa (section 4.4.2) which allows null subject if AGR-S is fully present. In (291), the subject position or [SPEC,AGR-S''] is occupied by the trace t of wàa and the subject agreement element AGR-S yá is fully present. The presence of null subject (i.e. t) is hereby licenced by the overt subject agreement element AGR-S yá. Since t is independently licenced by spec-head agreement relation, it follows that both antecedent government of t by wà and that-t filter (here cêewaá - t) are ineffective. Notice that that-t filter is effective in English because English does not allow a null subject.

Purpose clause headed by don

Tuller (1986) discusses the purpose clause headed by dón (for), a preposition. The purpose clause is said to have a structure of a prepositional phrase with the preposition head (dón) modified by a complement clause (S'): [PP P S']. A structure such

as (292) below, contains a purpose clause PP and is excluded because the complement clause S' to dón contains a gap (e).

(292) *Áishà tánàa neémán mùtúm

Aisha 3FS looking man
NF CONT for

[_{PP} dón [_{S'} tà àuraá e]]

for 3FS marry
NF SUB

(Aisha is looking for a man to marry)

Tuller (1986:64) accounts for the exclusion of (292) as follows: "If the gap in the complement clause to dón is the result of wh- movement of an empty element, then the result is an empty operator in COMP, which like all empty categories must be properly governed." This observation is shown in (293).

(293) *Áishà tá nàa neémán mùtúm

[_{PP} dón [_{S'} Q₁ [PRO tà á àuraá t₁]]]

Thus, (293) is an ECP violation. The empty element Q in COMP is not governed by dón, a non-proper governor.

Hence, (293) is ruled out. But native judgement declares (237) a well-formed structure. I will now offer an alternative, non-movement, agreement-oriented account which takes into account the morphosyntactic facts of Hausa and which will show that (293) is indeed perfectly well-formed.

First, consider an elaborate structure (294) of the embedded complement clause dón tà ó auraá 'for her to marry'. The structure is intended to capture the actual relationships obtaining amongst elements in the clause.

(294)

In (294), spec-head agreement relation obtains between subject NP in [SPEC, AGR-S''] (here empty subject NP_e) and subject agreement element (AGR-S) tà. The nature of the agreement relation is such that subject NP and AGR-S share phi-features (i.e. person, gender and number

features) and an idiosyncrasy of Hausa allows null subject in the presence of an overt AGR-S. In the verbal component of the clause structure, a head-head agreement relation obtains between verbal base and AGR-O, yielding the full verb àuraá 'marry' as discussed in Chapter four (4.2.4). Verbal base - AGR-O agreement relation involves sharing of morphological features between the verbal base and AGR-O. In (294), the verbal base àur- operates grade 4 and requires a zero object. Grade form -aá (4A) carries these properties and is therefore selected by the verbal base àur- as seen in the full verb àuraá. Thus, all basic agreement relations are observed in (294). This being the case, it follows that the postulation of PRO in subject position i.e. [SPEC,AGR-S''] and an empty element 0 in [SPEC,CP] as in (293) is untenable.

In the Principles and Parameters framework, PRO must be ungoverned, thereby restricting its occurrence to ungoverned positions. But notice that the subject position in (294) is a governed position, with AGR-S tà governing the position under spec-head relation. Since Hausa independently allows null subject, it follows that

the postulation of PRO to occupy subject position in structures containing null subject is not required, more so when the subject position is governed by an overt AGR-S.

Now consider the empty element $\bar{Q}$ in [SPEC,CP]. Here a movement analysis such as Tuller's posits that there is an empty element $\bar{Q}$ in [SPEC,CP] and that the full verb is followed by a trace. This movement analysis fails to capture the fact that the full verb àuraá in (293) attracts a following zero object, an option that is available if the verbal base selects grade form A (-aá) of grade 4. Our analysis captures native speakers' intuition, thereby rendering (293) a well-formed structure. Notice however that the full verb àuraá can be followed by a trace and in which case, the grade form A (-aá) of grade 4 will still be the grade form to be chosen by the verbal base àur-. That is to say, the same grade form A (-aá) of grade 4 is used by a verbal base when followed by either a zero object or trace as previously discussed in chapter four (4.4.1). But it must be pointed out that if trace were to follow the verb

àuraá (an option preferred by Tuller), then there must be an overt antecedent for the trace. Thus, zero object and trace are in complementary distribution: where an overt antecedent cannot be established for a trace that follows a full verb, zero object is assumed. Conversely, the presence of an overt antecedent excludes a zero object. Now with this stipulation which is supported by facts of the language, we must dismiss Tuller's movement analysis which posits 'an empty antecedent for trace as counter-intuitive.

5.5 Summary

The object of the present chapter had been the determination of the effect of agreement relations on movement facts of Hausa. The chapter began with an overview of major assumptions on movement theory in universal grammar. Three assumptions of movement theory were particularly of considerable interest in the present study. They are the subjacency condition on movement, the empty category principle (ECP) and the resumptive strategies for circumventing subjacency and ECP violations. Subjacency and ECP are two well-formedness conditions for

every syntactic movement. Subjacency places restrictions on distance of movement. ECP is a condition on proper government of traces left behind by moved antecedents. The chapter offers an alternative agreement-oriented approach to movement facts of Hausa. The relevance of the alternative approach follows from the fact that it captures the idiosyncracies of Hausa in respect of movement. The agreement-oriented approach also reduces the resumptive strategies for circumventing subjacency and ECP violations to agreement issues, and in particular to 'grade form substitution'. Basic assumptions and operation of the alternative agreement-oriented approach were given in section 5.3. The chapter (section 5.4) revisits Tuller's findings in respect of movement facts of Hausa, showing how best they are handled within the proposed alternative agreement-oriented approach to movement facts of Hausa.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

In the preceding five chapters we attempted a systematic presentation of research findings on aspects of agreement relations in the clause structure of Hausa. The major goals of the study were (1) to examine the nature of syntactic agreement relations in Hausa clause structure, and (2) to determine the effects of such agreement relations on the operations of conditions on movement in Hausa. The conclusion of the study dwells on two major issues (i) implications of the study, and (ii) unresolved problems.

Implications of the present study

The study emphasizes the significant role played by agreement relations in Hausa clause structure and in the preceding chapters, arguments were presented to justify this claim. The implication of the study is two fold: (a) implication to some crucial issues in Hausa syntax and (b) implication to linguistic theory.

With respect to Hausa syntax, the study necessitates a re-think in the syntactic analysis of the

clause structure and the study of movement operations in Hausa. Evidence was given in relation to (a) the role of agreement relations in the phrase structure - the NP (chapter two); (b) reinterpretation of relations among constituents in the verbal component of the clause due to the important role played by agreement relations in the component (chapters three and four); (c) reinterpretation of movement facts of Hausa due to the role played by agreement relations (chapter five).

With respect to implication of the study for linguistic theory, we observe that the powerful role played by agreement relations in determining convergence in the clause structure, necessitates the postulation of an 'agreement module', similar to Baker's (1988) morphology module, to be incorporated into the theory of grammar. An argument for 'agreement module' is as follows: The various modules of the Principles and Parameters framework are well-formedness conditions which ensure possible structures at different levels of representation. The Projection Principle for instance is a module which ensures that subcategorization properties of lexical items are observed at all

levels of representation. Should any of the modules fail to operate at a level where it serves to ensure well-formedness of structure, the structure will not converge. It will not be admitted as a well-formed structure. Notice that observing agreement relations between agreeing pairs in a clause structure is also a necessary prerequisite for convergence. Thus, at any level of representation, structures in which agreement relations are not fully observed do not converge. Since agreement amongst constituents determines well-formedness of structures, we propose that on the basis of similarity of function with other modules of grammar, agreement should also be considered a module, 'the agreement module'. Agreement module determines well-formedness of structures by ensuring that all agreement relations between agreeing elements in the clause are fully observed. In morphologically rich languages such as Hausa, agreement module reinforces the role of bounding theory module and the Empty Category Principle (ECP) module.

Unresolved Problem

There is no doubt that the present study has given deeper and useful insights into the role of agreement relations in the determination of convergence or well-formedness in Hausa clause structure than earlier accounts of the same issue. However, the issue of full verb agreeing with null elements - trace and zero object in the verbal component of the clause structure is a major problem yet to be resolved fully. Recall that in our inventory of the various agreement relations obtaining in the clause structure in chapter four, we argued for a 'head-complement' relation in the verbal component of the clause. We said the head-complement relation is an agreement relation between full verb and any of those syntactic environments enumerated in footnote 4, chapter one. A syntactic environment is also considered a complement to the full verb in view of the fact that it must agree with the head (full verb). The agreement is marked morphologically by the grade of the verb.

An unresolved problem is that whereas 'full verb-object noun/pronoun' relation is represented structurally since accusative Case is assigned under government, the 'unusual' 'full verb-null object' relation does not involve accusative Case assignment, hence cannot be so represented structurally. Thus, a major theoretical problem which has not been resolved is how to harmonise structural or geometrical representation of agreement relations and morphological marking of same. That is to say, how can these morphologically marked agreement relations be captured structurally, i.e. be stated in X-bar theoretic terms? Perhaps we may follow ideas in Lasnik and Saito (1984) and suggest some kind of gamma marking [γ -marking] for determining satisfaction of agreement. That is to say, if the feature [$+\gamma$] is added to any element, it would mean that the element is involved in an agreement relation that is stated structurally. Where agreement relation cannot be stated structurally (i.e. in X-bar terms), the element involved in the agreement is marked

[-y]. This proposal is intended to capture the fact that agreement relations in Hausa are either both morphologically and structurally represented or only morphologically marked. The details of this proposal need to be fleshed out in another independent study.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdoulaye, M.L. (1991) *Derived Direct Objects in Hausa*. Ms. State University of New York at Buffalo.
- Abney, S. (1987) "The English Noun Phrase in Its Sentential Aspect". Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge.
- Abraham, R.C. (1962) Dictionary of the Hausa Language. London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Alain, R. (1991) "Functional Categories and Agreement". The 14th GLOW Colloquim.
- Amfani, A.H. (1995) "The 'Grade' as a functional element and reinterpretation of relations in the Hausa verbal component". In Owolabi K (ed.) pp 128-141.
- Anderson, M. (1978) "NP pre-posing in Noun Phrases". In Proceedings of the Eighth Annual Meeting of the North-Eastern Linguistic Society, ed. Mark J. Stein, 12-21. Amherst, M A.: GLSA publications.
- Authier, J-Marc, (1993) "Nonquantificational WH and weakest crossover". Linguistic Inquiry 24:161-168.
- Aoun, J., N. Hornstein, D. Lightfoot and A. Weinberg (1987) "Two types of locality". Linguistic Inquiry 18: 537-577.
- Awoyale, Y. (1995) "The role of functional categories in syntax: The Yoruba Case". In Owolabi K. (ed.) pp 113-127.
- Bagari, D.M. (1970) "Aspects of Nominalization in Hausa". M Phil Thesis, University of London.
- (1972) "NP complementation in Hausa". African Language Studies 13, 32-51.

- Bagari, D.M. (1977) "Subordinate Adverbial Clauses in Hausa". Doctoral dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles.
- Baldi, S. (1977) Systematic Hausa Bibliography. Tip. PIODA Roma: Istituto Italo-Africano.
- Baltin, M.R. (1991) "Head Movement in Logical Form". Linguistic Inquiry 22:225-249.
- Baker, M.C. (1988) Incorporation: A Theory of Grammatical Function Changing. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Bamgbose, A. (1974) "On Serial Verbs and verbal status". The Journal of West African Languages XI/1: 17-48.
- Bargery, G.P. (1934) A Hausa-English Dictionary and English-Hausa Vocabulary. Oxford.
- Bashir, A.M. (1985) "The fragments of Hausa verbal system as interpreted by F.W. Parsons and Paul Newman". B.A. dissertation, University of Maiduguri.
- Bature, A. (1990a) Prosodic Constituency and Hausa Verbs. MS. Stanford University.
- _____ (1990b) Suppressed Arguments and Implicit Roles in Hausa. Ms. Stanford University.
- Borer, H. (1983) Parametric Syntax. Dordrecht: Foris.
- Bouchard, D. (1984) On the Content of Empty Categories. Dordrecht: Foris.

- Caron, B. (1989) "The verbal system of Ader Hausa". In Current Progress in Chadic Linguistics, ed. Zygmunt Frajzyngier, 131-169. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Chomsky, N. (1977) "On Wh Movement". In Formal Syntax, eds P. Culicover, T. Wasaw and A. Akmajian. New York: Academic Press.
- _____ (1980) "On Binding". Linguistic Inquiry 11 1-46.
- _____ (1973) "Conditions on transformations". In A Festschrift for Morris Halle, eds. Anderson, S. and P. Kiparsky. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Wiston. 232-86.
- _____ (1980) Lectures on Government and Binding. Dordrecht: Foris.
- _____ (1982) Some Concepts and Consequences of the theory of Government and Binding. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- _____ (1986a) Knowledge of Language, Its Nature, Origin and Use. New York: Praeger.
- _____ (1986b) Barriers. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- _____ (1991) "Some notes on economy of derivation and representation". In Principles and Parameters in comparative grammar, ed. Robert Freidin, 417-454. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- _____ (1992) A Minimalist Program for Linguistic Theory. Ms. Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Cole, P. (1987) "Null objects in universal grammar". Linguistic Inquiry. 18,4: 597-612.

- Cole, P. (1982) "On defining bounding nodes for subjacency", Linguistic Inquiry 13: 139-45.
- Contreras, H. (1991) "On the position of subjects". In Syntax and Semantics 25, ed. Susan D. Rothstein, 63-79. San Diego, California. Academic Press Inc.
- Cook, V.J. (1988) Chomsky's Universal Grammar: An Introduction. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Crystal, D. (1980) A First Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics. London: Andre Deutsch.
- Dimmendaal, G.J. (1991) Verbs (from P. Newman and R.M. Newman's dictionary) listed by Grade and Transitivity. Ms. University of Leiden.
- Epstein, S.D. (1992) "Derivational constraints on A-chain formation". Linguistic Inquiry 23: 235-259
- Ernst, T. (1991) "A phrase structure theory for tertiaries". In Syntax and Semantics 25, ed. Susan D. Rothstein, 189-208. San Diego, California. Academic Press Inc.
- Eulenberg, J.B. (1972) "Complementation Phenomena in Hausa". Doctoral Dissertation, University of California, San Diego.
- Frampton, J. (1991) "Relativized Minimality: A Review". The Linguistic Review 8/1: 1-46.
- Fukui, N. (1987) "A theory of category projections and its applications". Doctoral Dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge.
- Fukui, N. and Speas, M. (1986) "Specifiers and Projection". MIT Working Papers in Linguistics 8: 128-172.

- Furniss, G. (1981) "Hausa Disyllabic Verbs: Comments on Base Forms and Extensions". Studies in African Linguistics 12: 97-129.
- _____ (1983) "The 4th grade of the verb in Hausa". In Studies in Chadic and Afroasiatic Linguistics, ed. E. Wolff and H. Meyer-Bahlburg, 287-300. Hamburg: Helmut Buske Verlag.
- Galadanci, M.K.M. (1969) "The simple nominal phrase in Hausa". Doctoral Thesis, University of London.
- _____ (1976) An Introduction to Hausa Grammar. Zaria: Longman Nigeria Limited.
- Garba, M.M. (1982) "Morphology of the Hausa verbs: A Case Grammar Analysis". Doctoral Dissertation, Bayero University, Kano.
- Giorgi, A. (1987) "The notion of complete functional complex: some evidence from Italian". Linguistic Inquiry 18: 511-18.
- Giorgi, A. and Longobardi, G. (1991) The syntax of noun phrases. Cambridge University Press.
- Goldsmith, J.A. (ed.) (1995) The Handbook of Phonological Theory. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Grimshaw, J. (1990) Argument Structure. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- Haegemann, L. (1992) Introduction to Government and Binding Theory. Oxford UK and Cambridge USA: Blackwell.

- Halpern, A.L. (1991) Phonological evidence for the surface non-existence of empty categories. Ms. Stanford University.
- Hayes, B. (1990) "Precompiled phrasal phonology". In The phonology-syntax connection, eds. Sharon Inkelas and Droga Zec, 85-108. Chicago and London. The University of Chicago Press.
- Hoekstra, E. (1991) "X-bar Theory and Licensing Mechanisms". The Linguistic Review 8/1: 47-73.
- Hoekstra, T. (1984) Transitivity. Dordrecht: Foris.
- _____ (1992) ECP, Tense and Islands. Ms. University of Leiden.
- Jackendoff, R.S. (1977) X-syntax: A Study of Phrase Structure. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- Jaeggli, O. and K.J. Saffir (eds) (1989). The Null Subject Parameter, Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Jaggar, P.J. (1977) "The nature and function of auxiliary verbs in Hausa". In Papers in Chadic Linguistics, ed. Paul Newman and Roxana Ma Newman 57-87. Leiden: Afrika-Studiecentrum.
- _____ (1978) "And what about ...? - Topicalization in Hausa". Studies in African Linguistics 9/1: 69-81.
- _____ (1981a) "Some unusual lexical passives in Hausa". M.A. Thesis. University of California, Los Angeles.
- _____ (1981b) "Varieties of passive in Hausa". In Studies in African Linguistics, ed. W.R. Leben, 73-77 Supp. 8.

- Jaggar, P.J. (1985) "Factors Governing the Morphological Coding of Referents in Hausa Narrative Discourse." Doctoral Dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles.
- Jaggar, P.J. and Munkaila, M.M. (1992) Evidence against the proposal that the Hausa pre-dativial final -r verb = the 'grade 5' final -r/-s verb (and an alternative analysis). Ms. University of London and University of Maiduguri.
- Junaidu, I. (1993) "Violation of constraints on movement rules in Hausa." Hausa Language, Literature and Culture. Kano: Bayero University Kano.
- Kayne, R.S. (1981) "ECP Extensions," Linguistic Inquiry 12: 93-133.
- Koopman, H. (1983) "ECP effects in main clauses," Linguistic Inquiry 14: 346-50.
- _____ (1984) The Syntax of Verbs. Dordrecht: Foris.
- Kraft, C.H. and Kirk-Greene, A.H.M. (1973). Hausa. London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Larson, R.K. (1988) "On the double object constructions." Linguistic Inquiry 19/3: 335-91.
- Lasnik, H. and M. Saito (1984) "On the nature of proper government," Linguistic Inquiry 15/2: 235-89.
- _____ (1992) Move α . Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- Lasnik, H. and J. Uriagereka (1988) A Course in GB Syntax. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.

- Leben, W.R. and D.M. Bagari (1975) "A Note on the Base Form of the Hausa Verb." Studies in African Linguistics 6: 239-248.
- Lee, E.J. (1993) "Superiority Effects and Adjunct Traces." Linguistic Inquiry 24: 177-183.
- Leiber, M. (1981) "Organization of the Lexicon." Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge.
- Lewis, M.B. (1969) Sentence Analysis in Modern Malay. Cambridge University Press, London.
- Marantz, A. (1994) On the Nature of Grammatical Relations. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- MacIntosh, M. (1984) Fulfulde Syntax and Verbal Morphology. England: Routledge and Kegan Paul Plc.
- Miko, D.D. (1982) "Adjectival Modification in Hausa." M.A. Dissertation, University of London.
- Muhammed, A. (1977) "Aspects of the syntax and semantics of noun modification by adjectives in Hausa." Doctoral Thesis, University of London.
- Munkaila, M.M. (1981) "The behaviour of Hausa transitive verbs." B.A. dissertation, University of Maiduguri.
- _____ (1985) "Dative Construction in Hausa." M.A. Thesis, University of London.
- _____ (1990) "Indirect Object Movement in Hausa." Doctoral Thesis, University of London.
- Newman, P. (1968) "Ideophones from a syntactic point of view." Journal of West African Linguistics 2:107-117.
- _____ (1971) "Transitive and Intransitive in Chadic Languages." Afrikanische Sprachen und Kulturen 6: 188-200. Deutsches Institut für Afrika. Hamburg.

Newman, P. (1973) "Grades, Vowel-Tone Classes and Extensions in the Hausa Verbal System." Studies in African Linguistics 4/3: 297-346.

(1982) "Grammatical Restructuring in Hausa: Indirect objects and possessives." Journal of African Languages and Linguistics 4: 59-73.

(1983) "The Efferential (Alias 'causative') in Hausa." In Studies in Chadic And Afroasiatic Linguistics, eds. E. Wolff and H. Meyer-Bahlburg 391-418. Hamburg: Helmut Buske Verlag.

(1991) Facts Count: An Empricist looks at Indirect objects in Hausa. Ms. Indiana University.

(1995) "Hausa Tonology: Complexities in an "Easy" Tone Language." In Goldsmith, J.A. (ed.): pp 762-781.

Newman, P. and R.G. Schuh (1974) "The Hausa Aspect System." Afro-Asiatic Linguistics 1/1: 1-38.

Newman, P. and R.M. Newman (1977) Modern Hausa-English Dictionary. Ibadan: University Press Limited.

(1981) "The Question morpheme q in Hausa." Afrika und Ubersee, band LXIV: 35-46.

Ngozi, A.I. (1989) "Towards the description of questions in universal grammar: The example of Igbo and Hausa". M.A. Dissertation, University of Jos.

- Owolabi, K. (1976) "Noun-Noun Constructions in Yoruba: A Syntactic and Semantic Analysis".
Doctoral Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- _____ (1995) "More on Yoruba prefixing morphology".
In Owolabi, K.(ed.) pp 92-112.
- _____ (ed.) (1995) Language in Nigeria: Essays in Honour of Ayo Bamgbose. Ibadan: Group Publishers.
- Ouhalla, J. (1991) "Functional categories and the head parameter". The 14th GLOW Colloquium.
- Parsons, F.W. (1960) "The Verbal System in Hausa: Forms, Function and Grades". Afrika und Ubersee Band XLIV/1: 1-36.
- _____ (1962) "Further observations on the 'causative' grade of the verb in Hausa". Journal of African Languages 1/3. 153-272.
- _____ (1971/72) "Suppletion and Neutralization in the verbal system of Hausa". Afrika und Ubersee Band LV/1-2: 49-97; 188-208.
- Perlmutter, D.M. and Soames, S. (1979) Syntactic Argumentation and the Structure of English. University of California Press.
- Pollock, J-Y (1989) "Verb movement, UG and the Structure of IP". Linguistic Inquiry 20/3: 365-424.
- Pullum, G.K. and Postal, P.M. (1979) "On an inadequate defence of trace theory". Linguistic Inquiry 10: 689-706.

- Quirk, R. and S. Greenbaum (1973) A University Grammar of English. United Kingdom: Longman.
- Radford, A. (1981) Transformational Syntax: A students' guide to Chomsky's Extended Standard Theory. Cambridge University Press.
- (1988) Transformational Grammar. Cambridge University Press.
- (1990) "On the syntax of determiners in English". Paper presented at the 4th International Symposium on the description and/or comparison of English and Greek, Aristotle University of Thessoloniki.
- Riemsdijk, H. van and E. Williams (1986) Introduction to the Theory of Grammar. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- Ritter, E. (1991) "Two functional categories in noun phrases: Evidence from modern Hebrew". In Syntax and Semantics 25, ed. Susan D. Rothstein, 37-62. San Diego, California: Academic Press Inc.
- Rizzi, L. (1982) Issues in Italian Syntax. Dordrecht: Foris.
- (1986) "Null objects in Italian and the theory of pro". Linguistic Inquiry 17: 501-58.
- (1990) Relativized Minimality. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press.
- Robert, M. (1981) "Movement and Binding". Linguistic Inquiry 12: 215-243.

- Rufa'i, A. (1977) "Grammatical Agreement in Hausa".
Doctoral Thesis, Georgetown University,
USA.
- Schwartz, L., Newman, P. and Sani, S. (1988). "Agreement
and scope of modification in Hausa
coordinate structures". In Papers from
the 24th Annual Regional Meeting of the
Chicago Linguistic Society, pp 278-290.
- Selkirk, E. (1977) "Some Remarks on noun phrase structure".
In Formal Syntax, eds. P. Culicover, T.
Wasaw and A. Akmajian. New York: Academic
Press.
- Sells, P. (1984) "Syntax and Semantics of resumptive
pronouns". Doctoral dissertation,
University of Massachusetts.
- _____ (1985) Lectures on contemporary syntactic
theories, Center for the study of
languages and information.
- Skinner, N. (1977) A Grammar of Hausa for Nigerian
Secondary Schools and Colleges. Zaria:
The Northern Nigerian Publishing Company
Limited.
- Speas, M. (1990) Phrase Structure in Natural Language.
Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Spencer, A. (1991) Morphological Theory: An Introduction
to Word Structure in Generative Grammar.
Basil Blackwell.
- Sportische, D. (1981) "Bounding nodes in French". The
Linguistic Review 1/2: 219-46.

- Stowell, T. (1981) "Origins of phrase structure". Doctoral Dissertation. Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge.
- Thompson, S.A. (1988) "A discourse approach to the cross-linguistic category 'adjective'. In Explaining Language Universals, ed. John A. Hawkins 167-185. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Tuller, L. (1983) "Datives in Hausa". In Proceedings of NELS 14, eds. C. Jones and P. Sells, 447-60. Umass, Amherst.
- _____ (1986) "Bijective Relations in Universal Grammar and the Syntax of Hausa". Doctoral Thesis, University of California, Los Angeles.
- _____ (1989) "Variation in Focus Constructions". In Current Progress in Chadic Linguistics, ed. Zygmunt Frajzyngier, 9-33. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- _____ (1991) AGR-drop and VP focus-fronting in Hausa. Ms. University of Leiden.
- _____ (1990) Restricted Argument Structure in Hausa. Ms. University of Leiden.
- Uwalaka, M.A. (1988) The Igbo Verb: A Semantico-syntactic Analysis. Beitrage Zur Afrikanistik, WEIN.
- _____ (1995) "X⁰-Movement and Igbo Complex Predicates". In Owolabi, K. (ed.) pp 156-175.
-1"
- Yusuf, M.A. (1991) "Aspects of the morphosyntax of functional categories in Hausa". Doctoral Dissertation, University of Essex.

- Zaenana, A., Engdahl, E., and Malting, J. (1981)
"Resumptive pronouns can be syntactically
bound." Linguistic Inquiry 12: 679-82.
- Zec, D. and Inkelas, S. (1990) "Prosodically Constrained
Syntax." In Sharon Inkelas and Dregga Zec
(eds.) pp365-378.
- Zec, D. and Inkelas, S. (eds.) (1990) The Phonology-
Syntax Connection. Chicago and London.
The University of Chicago Press.

APPENDIX

This appendix contains samples of Hausa regular and irregular verbs and their meanings. The regular verbs are grouped in accordance with the grades they operate. The verbs are extracted from Dimmendaal's list of verbs (from Paul Newman and Roxana Ma Newman's (1977) dictionary) listed by grade and transitivity.

1 IRREGULAR VERBS

<u>Verb</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
kòoshí	intransitive	be replate
wúni	"	spend a day
bárii	transitive	1. leave, leave off 2. let, allow
bíyaá	"	1. pay, 2. fulfil
fí	"	exceed, surpass
gánif	"	1. see, 2. look at, watch
jí	"	1. hear, 2. understand 3. listen 4. feel, taste, smell
jíraá	"	wait for
kíraá	"	1. call, summon 2. invite
kí	"	refuse
háu	intransitive/ transitive	1. be in excess 2. go up, increase in price
háu	"	1. mount, climb, ride 2. begin
rígaá	"	precede

2 REGULAR VERBS
A. GRADE 1

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
faafaat-	1	intransitive	faáfàataá (1A)	struggle, have a hard time with
gangar-	1	"	gángàraá (1A)	descend down slope, roll down, flow down
gaz-	1	"	gázàa (1A)	fall short, not be enough
jirg-	1	" "	jírgàa (1A)	move a short distance away
kurđ-	1	"	kúrdàa (1A)	crawl through, pass underneath
kookaãrt-	1	"	koókàãrtaá (1A)	try hard, exert oneself
kuukuut-	1	"	kuúkùutaá (1A)	try hard
laf-	1	"	láfàa (1A)	die down (fire, wind, dispute)
nis-	1	"	nífsàa (1A)	heave a sigh
turz-	1	"	túrzàa (1A)	exert one's utmost effort
aikat-	1	transitive	áikàtaá (1B) áikàtà (1C)	do, perform, act
kuul-	1	"	buúlàa (1B) buúllà (1C)	1. bore hole, 2. gore (with horn)

2 REGULAR VERBS

A. GRADE I

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
barz-	1	"	bárzàa (1B) bárzà (1C)	grind coarsely
cuur-	1	"	cuúràa (1B) cuúrà (1C)	knead into balls
daf-	1	"	dáfàa (1B) dáfà (1C)	stuck unto, affix
dak-	1	"	dákàa (1B) dákà (1C)	pound (grain), beat someone or something
dar-	1	"	dàràa (1B) dàrà (1C)	exceed slightly
daats-	1	"	daátsàa (1B) daátsà (1C)	chop or cut into pieces (wood or grass)
kiṙg-	,	"	kiṙgàa (1B) kiṙgà (1C)	count up
'yant-	1	"	'yántàa (1B) 'yántà (1C)	free someone from slavery.

Verbal Base	Grade	Transitivity	Operating Grade Forms	Meaning
daay-	2	transitive	dàayaá (2A) dàayeé (2B) dàayi (2C)	strip (back, skin)
dook-	2	"	dòokaá (2A) dookeé (2B) dooki (2C)	beat, hit, thrash
dirkaak-	2	"	dirkaákàa (2A) dirkàakeé (2B) dirkàaki (2C)	approach with determination
fizg-	2	"	fizgaá (2A) fizgeé (2B) fizgi (2C)	grab
hang-	2	"	hàngaá (2A) hàngéé (2B) hàngi (2C)	1. see something from a far, in the distance 2. foresee
rook-	2	"	ròokaá (2A) ròokeé (2B) ròoki (2C)	beg, ask, request
shaak	2	"	shàakaá (2A) shàakeé (2B) shàaki (2C)	sniff at something

Verbal Base	Grade	Transitivity	Operating Grade Forms	Meaning
sungum-	2	"	sùngúmàá (2A) sùngùmeé (2B) sùngùmí (2C)	lift (heavy or large load)
tsiikar-	2	"	tsiikàràá (2A) tsiikàreé (2B) tsiikàrí (2C)	tickle someone's sides
yaudar-	2	"	yàudàràá (2A) yàudàreé (2B) yàudàrí (2C)	deceive, trick

C. GRADE 3

Verbal Base	Grade	Transitivity	Operating Grade Forms	Meaning
ankaã-	3	Unaccusative	ànkáãà (3C)	take notice, realize, pay attention
balag-	3	"	bàlágà (3C)	reach puberty
bur-	3	"	bùrà (3C)	be ripe
kaasait-	3	"	kàasáità (3C)	become important, full grown
nuk-	3	"	nùká (3C)	become ripe by storing
nuun-	3	"	nùuná (3C)	ripe, mature, be cooked

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
rik	3	Unaccusative	riká (3C)	be fully developed, ripe
taraar-	3	"	táraára (3C)	drip
wuyaat-	3	"	wúyaátà (3C)	become difficult, become scarce
yankwan-	3	"	yànkwánà (3C)	become withered, emaciated.
zuraar-	3	"	zúraára (3C)	trickle or slide down (of water)

D. GRADE 4

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
baab-	4	intransitive	baábèe (4A)	break off relations, friendship
bingir-	4	"	bingireé (4A)	topple over, fall over on side.
daar-	4	"	daàrèe (4A)	crumble, fall apart, crack (especially of earthen pot)
kanjam-	4	"	kánjameé (4A)	become thin
kauc-	4	"	káucèe (4A)	dodge, avoid, slip aside
kook-	4	"	koókèe (4A)	fade (of colour)
rincaab-	4	"	ríncàabeé (4A)	become too much, too numerous

Verbal Base	Grade	Transitivity	Operating Grade Forms	Meaning
sulluð	4	Intransitive	súllúðeé (4A)	slip away, escape
tsaag-	4	"	tsaágèe (4A)	become split, cracked
wark-	4	"	wárkèe (4A)	be cured, recover from illness
binn-	4	transitive	bínnèe (4Aand B) bínnè (4C)	1. bury 2. full a hole
ðambar-	4	"	ðámðàreé (4Aand B) ðámðàrè (4C)	tear or strip off
cir-	4	"	círèe (4AandB) círè (4C)	pull out
ðaam-	4	"	ðáámèe (4AandB) ðáámè (4C)	tighten, straighten, make taut
faaf-	4	"	faáfèe (4AandB) faáfè (4C)	scrape out inside of gouged or pumpkin
fyaac-	4	"	fyaáçèe (4AandB) fyaáçè (4C)	blow one's nose
kuush-	4	"	kuúshèe (4AandB) kuúshè (4C)	find fault with
kyaal-	4	"	kyaálèe (4AandB) kyaálè (4C)	ignore (person or thing)

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
saac-	4	transitive	saáccèe(4AandB) saáccè (4C)	steal steal
taac-	4	"	taáccèe (4AandB) taáccè (4C)	strain, filter

E. GRADE 5

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
baay-	5	transitive	baáyáǎ̃ (5AandB) baáyáǎ̃ (5C)	1. give 2. betray someone
fadak-	5	"	fáǎ́kárǎ̃ (5AandB) fáǎ́kárǎ̃ (5C)	teach, tell, cause to realize
kaay-	5	"	kaáyáǎ̃ (5AandB) kaáyáǎ̃ (5C)	1. knock down, fell 2. defeat, overcome
kaw-	5	"	káwáǎ̃ (5AandB) káwáǎ̃ (5C)	1. put aside, remove to another place 2. shift, alter position
san-	5	"	sánáǎ̃ (5AandB) sánáǎ̃ (5C)	inform someone
sadauk-	5	"	sáǎ́ukárǎ̃(5AandB) sáǎ́ukárǎ̃ (5C)	1. volunteer(time) 2. sacrifice life

F. GRADE 6

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
bull-	6	intransitive	búlloó (6A)	appear suddenly or unexpectedly
farfad-	6	"	fárfádoó (6A)	recover from unconsciousness or illness
zalzal-	6	"	zálzáloó (6A)	hang out tongue from panting
tark-	6	transitive	tárkoó (6AandB) tárkoó (6C)	Bring trouble upon oneself.

G. GRADE 7

<u>Verbal Base</u>	<u>Grade</u>	<u>Transitivity</u>	<u>Operating Grade Forms</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
auk-	7	Unaccusative	àukú (7C)	happen, occur, arise
faar-	7	"	fàarú (7C)	happen, occur
jiit-	7	"	jiitú (7C)	be on good terms with someone
shaak-	7	"	shàakú (7C)	be fond of someone, be good friends
wanz-	7	"	wànzú (7C)	1. happen, occur 2. be eternal
zak-	7	"	zàkú (7C)	be eager, anxious.